

UNIVERSIDAD
POLITÉCNICA
DE MADRID

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros Industriales
Máster Universitario en Ingeniería Industrial

Master's Thesis
**Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting for Monocular
Endoscopic Video Reconstruction of Surgical Scenes**

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March, 2025

*“We don’t see things as they are,
we see them as we are.”*

– Anaïs Nin

Acknowledgements

This thesis represents the culmination of everything I have learned throughout my academic journey, from my earliest studies to the completion of my Double Master's in Industrial Engineering and Automatic Control & Robotics at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM). This achievement stands as the most significant milestone in my life so far, not only academically but personally, as it embodies years of dedication, resilience, and bold decisions.

One of those pivotal decisions was to take a day off from my first job as an engineer in Barcelona to visit UPM's Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería Industrial. At the time, I was debating whether to pursue the double master's at UPM or staying at Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), where I had completed my undergraduate studies. Choosing to resign from the UPC program—without even knowing whether UPM would accept me—was a risky decision. Today, I can confidently say it was one of the best decisions of my life. To my past self, who dared to take that leap, thank you for your courage. Without it, none of this would have been possible.

My two years in Madrid have been transformative. At UPM, I delved into topics close to my heart, such as computer vision—the core of this thesis—and grew both intellectually and professionally. Simultaneously, joining a startup at the start of the double master's program taught me invaluable technical and workplace skills. Most importantly, these years introduced me to incredible people who shaped my experience in ways I could never have imagined.

First and foremost, I extend my deepest gratitude to Professor Hideo Saito of Keio University's HyperVision Research Laboratory (HVRL) in Japan, where this work was conducted. His wisdom, guidance, and respect for my initial research proposal made this project possible. Thank you for providing the facilities, data, and expertise that enabled this work. Additionally, I would like to thank my UPM supervisor, Prof. Antonio Barrientos, for granting me the opportunity to undertake this research and for his valuable recommendations, which helped me achieve the highest quality in my work.

I am also deeply grateful to the friends I have made during my stay in Japan, particularly those at the residence. Thank you for the countless unforgettable moments on the other side of the world, in a culture so vastly different from what we are accustomed to in Europe. The experiences we shared, many of them amusing and peculiar, will forever stay with me.

To my friends from the double master’s program, I cannot thank you enough for making this challenging journey—balancing studies and work—much more bearable. Your support, our shared struggles during exams, and the trips we embarked on together in such a short time have forged bonds that I know will endure beyond this chapter of our lives. Within the group of people I have met thanks to pursuing the double master’s program, I would like to express my gratitude to UPM for being part of the ATHENS Network. This opportunity enabled me to study at four different European universities, meet incredible people from various countries across Europe, and share unforgettable experiences with them. Some of these friends have even visited me in Japan, making this journey even more special.

To my friends from Barcelona, thank you for always making me feel at home whenever I return. Despite having moved away, I still feel like a part of the family we built together, and your constant support remains unchanged, no matter how much time passes.

Moving on to my family, I wish to extend my deepest gratitude to my mother for everything. For the boundless love she gives me, the unwavering support in her own way as a Chinese mother, and her immense sacrifices to provide me with the best education possible. This entire section could be filled with acknowledgments to her alone, but to keep it concise and to also express my appreciation for others, I will refrain from doing so. Nevertheless, she knows how much I value her. Additionally, I want to thank every member of my family who has played a crucial role in my personal growth and academic development.

A special thanks goes to my partner, whose support and encouragement were essential throughout this last year of relentless study and work. Her presence, especially during my most demanding times—even watching over me during video calls to keep me focused on this thesis—meant more than words can express.

I would also like to extend my gratitude to the startup where I have worked over the past two years and where I will continue after completing my double master’s degree. Thank you for allowing me to take a semester off to travel to Japan and fully dedicate myself to this research, enabling me to achieve the best possible results. I am especially grateful to my colleagues who took on my responsibilities during my absence.

Finally, I would like to make a special mention of Eduard Alentorn Gelí, whose suc-

cessful arthroscopic surgery not only improved my health but also introduced me to this type of operation, sparking the motivation that ultimately led to the creation of this thesis.

To everyone who has contributed to my journey, whether through guidance, support, or companionship, I extend my deepest appreciation. This thesis would not have been possible without you.

Executive Summary

The growing use of **Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS)** has significantly transformed the field of medicine, enabling safer and more efficient procedures compared to traditional open surgeries. However, the reliance on **two-dimensional (2D)** visualization in many of these interventions introduces critical limitations in surgeons' spatial perception, complicating the accurate interpretation of patient anatomy and increasing procedural risks. In this context, **3D reconstruction** of surgical scenes emerges as a key solution to enhance intraoperative understanding, facilitate surgeon training, and potentially assist in the development of autonomous robotic systems.

This work presents an innovative methodology based on **Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting for Monocular Endoscopic Video Reconstruction of Surgical Scenes**. Within this highly challenging framework, one of the greatest challenges lies in the **dynamic** and **deformable** nature of **soft tissues**, caused by surgical manipulation or patient respiration. These factors limit the applicability of traditional solutions and even most deep learning-based approaches, which are primarily designed for static environments.

Although **Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF)**, another novel method, can model changes in appearance and geometry, it is constrained by its **high computational cost** and inability to achieve **real-time rendering**. In contrast, **3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS)** positions itself as the only viable solution, enabling **deformation modeling** through adaptive adjustments of Gaussian parameters (position, orientation, scale) across frames, all with reduced computational demands.

This challenge is evident in current research, where early attempts at 3D reconstruction in minimally invasive surgery are emerging. Methods such as EndoGaussian, SurgicalGaussian, and Deform3DGS address specific issues, including tissue deformation and tool occlusion. Among current methods, **Deform3DGS** stands out, achieving **training times of one minute per scene** and positioning itself as a practical option for real-time intraoperative applications.

Despite this, Deform3DGS faces significant limitations in handling **regions occluded by surgical instruments**, leading to artifacts and undesirable outcomes such as extensive **blackened areas** in reconstructions. Addressing this problem, this project proposes **InDeform3DGS**, an enhanced system that integrates a **Model Optimization module** into the original Deform3DGS. This module leverages **inpainted video data** from the raw input to **refine visual fidelity** through feedback mechanisms.

The proposed method encompasses an **end-to-end pipeline** where the input is a monocular endoscopic video. To prepare for 3D Gaussian Splatting, essential preprocessing files (e.g., depth maps, camera poses) must be generated through an **automated pipeline**. This aspect is critical in the current context, as no existing method provides an end-to-end pipeline, relying instead on pre-existing datasets.

This work explains the prior **comparative study** of existing techniques to design an optimal pipeline for surgical scenes. Following this analysis, the **development, implementation, and optimization** of each preprocessing module are presented. The pipeline components begin with **video dehazing**, as electrocautery in laparoscopic surgery generates haze that reduces visibility. Next, surgical tools—responsible for occluding areas of interest (human tissue regions)—are **detected and segmented** to mask them. Once identified, **inpainting** is applied to occluded areas, removing tools and filling them with contextually coherent visual information. Finally, **depth estimation** and **camera pose estimation** are incorporated, both essential inputs for 3D Gaussian Splatting.

After optimizing the first part of the pipeline for laparoscopic environments, a **comparative analysis** between Deform3DGS and InDeform3DGS is conducted. It is worth noting that modifying Deform3DGS to **directly use inpainted videos** and depth estimation (without tool masks per frame) yielded **unsatisfactory results**, as it generated reconstructions faithful to the inpainted video—which is imperfect—resulting in oversimplified tissue behind tools. To leverage this **partially imperfect yet valuable data**, the **Model Optimization** is modified by introducing a **Total Loss Function** focused solely on occluded regions, enhancing visual, structural, and temporal coherence in 3D reconstructions.

Tests on the EndoNeRF dataset and three custom datasets generated via the developed pipeline demonstrate that InDeform3DGS achieves **superior visual quality** in most cases compared to Deform3DGS. This is supported by a quantitative comparison using a custom metric combining **NIQE** and **BRISQUE** (for occluded regions), **PSNR** (to ensure non-tissue areas remain unaffected), and **MUSIQ** (overall quality). The results show that **InDeform3DGS** improves the **Final Score**—defined for reconstruction quality—by **up to 25%** over Deform3DGS in visual terms.

However, InDeform3DGS introduces additional computational costs and underper-

forms with very **low-resolution monocular endoscopic videos**, as measured by the proposed metric.

Figure R1 Qualitative comparison between Deform3DGS and InDeform3DGS on a Keio University dataset. Note that in Frame 0, Deform3DGS fails to handle the surgical tool, leaving visible artifacts, while InDeform3DGS reconstructs the area and reveals underlying tissue. In Frame 70, Deform3DGS retains a black region due to prolonged occlusion, whereas InDeform3DGS removes the tool and reconstructs the yellow tissue edge with greater visual coherence.

Overall, this work proposes a **novel approach** for 3D reconstruction of monocular endoscopic surgical videos using Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting. The end-to-end pipeline and InDeform3DGS framework overcome the primary limitation of Deform3DGS, delivering superior reconstructions through optimized inpainting integration.

Keyword: Reconstrucción 3D, Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting, Minimally Invasive Surgery, Computer Vision, Deep Learning, Depth Estimation, Camera Pose Estimation, Inpainting, Feature Detection, Image Segmentation, Image Dehazing, Model Optimization, Batch Processing

UNESCO codes:

- 1203.04 – Artificial Intelligence
- 2209.94 – Computer Vision, Image and Video Analysis
- 3314.84 – Biomedical Engineering
- 1203.10 – Computer-Assisted Learning
- 3304.17 - Real-Time Systems
- 3304.95 - 3D Graphics, Virtual Reality, and Augmented Reality

Resumen Ampliado

El creciente uso de la **Cirugía Mínimamente Invasiva (MIS)** ha transformado significativamente el campo de la medicina, permitiendo procedimientos más seguros y eficientes en comparación con las cirugías abiertas tradicionales. Sin embargo, la dependencia de la **visión bidimensional (2D)** en muchas de estas intervenciones introduce importantes limitaciones en la percepción espacial del cirujano, dificultando la interpretación precisa de la anatomía del paciente y aumentando los riesgos asociados a la intervención. En este contexto, la **reconstrucción 3D** de escenas quirúrgicas emerge como una solución clave para mejorar la comprensión del entorno operatorio, facilitar el entrenamiento de cirujanos y, potencialmente, asistir en el desarrollo de sistemas robóticos autónomos. Esta investigación aborda este desafío proponiendo un método basado en *Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting* para reconstruir escenas quirúrgicas a partir de video endoscópico monocular.

Para ello, se contó con las instalaciones del *HyperVision Research Laboratory (HVRL)* de la Universidad de Keio en Japón, así como con el conjunto de datos empleado para validar la tecnología propuesta.

La decisión de emplear el método de **3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS)** para realizar la solución mencionada se fundamenta en su superioridad para abordar las limitaciones de los enfoques existentes, desde métodos basados en visión por computadora tradicional hasta métodos basados en aprendizaje profundo. Su ventaja radica en parámetros de **velocidad** y **eficiencia computacional**: a diferencia de *Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF)*, otro método relevante en reconstrucción 3D, 3DGS es capaz de reducir drásticamente los tiempos de entrenamiento, pasando de horas o días (NeRF) a un **orden de minutos**. Además, permite renderizar en tiempo real con calidad visual comparable.

Asimismo, uno de los mayores desafíos en la reconstrucción de escenas quirúrgicas es la naturaleza **dinámica** y **deformable** de los tejidos blandos, que cambian constantemente debido a la manipulación quirúrgica, la respiración y el flujo sanguíneo. Las soluciones

tradicionales de reconstrucción 3D, diseñadas para escenarios estáticos, resultan ineficaces en estos entornos. Por otro lado, aunque NeRF puede modelar cambios en apariencia y geometría, su alto costo computacional lo descarta para aplicaciones en tiempo real. En este marco, 3DGS se posiciona como la **única solución viable** al permitir modelar deformaciones mediante la adaptación de parámetros de los gaussianos en cada cuadro, optimizando posición, orientación y escala con un costo computacional reducido.

Este aspecto es notorio en el campo de investigación, donde se observan los primeros intentos de reconstrucción 3D aplicada a cirugías mínimamente invasivas. Métodos como **EndoGaussian**, **SurgicalGaussian** y **Deform3DGS** han abordado desafíos específicos, incluyendo deformación de tejidos y oclusión de herramientas. Sobre los métodos actuales, destaca Deform3DGS, que logra tiempos de entrenamiento de un minuto por escena, posicionándose como alternativa viable para aplicaciones intraoperatorias en tiempo real.

Una vez definido el método para obtener el *Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting*, se consideró la obtención de la reconstrucción 3D únicamente a partir de video endoscópico monocular. Para ello, se realizó un estudio exhaustivo de técnicas existentes para preparar los inputs necesarios. Es importante señalar que los resultados relacionados con eficiencia computacional reportados en este trabajo están vinculados a las capacidades del equipo utilizado: un **Lenovo Legion Pro 7i Gen 8**.

El pipeline de procesamiento del video monocular consta de las siguientes etapas: primero, se aplica un *dehaze* al video, ya que en ciertas intervenciones de cirugía laparoscópica se emplea electrocauterio, lo que genera neblina dificultando la visibilidad del cirujano. A continuación, se **detectan** los instrumentos quirúrgicos, responsables de la oclusión en las áreas de interés, que corresponden a las regiones de tejido humano. Esta detección va acompañada de la **segmentación de los instrumentos** para enmascararlos, de modo que, una vez identificadas las áreas no deseadas, se aplica *inpainting* a dichas zonas de oclusión eliminando las herramientas y rellenándolas con información visual coherente con el resto de la escena. Finalmente, se incorporan la **estimación de profundidad** y la **estimación de la pose de la cámara**, dos entradas fundamentales para el proceso de *3D Gaussian Splatting*.

Para cada componente mencionado, se terminó eligiendo los métodos que se desglosan a continuación:

1. **Dehaze de Video:** Al comparar técnicas tradicionales, se optó por el enfoque *Dark Channel Prior (DCP)* junto con el *Guided Filter*, donde se asume que al menos un canal de color tiene píxeles con valores muy bajos en regiones sin neblina para estimar la cantidad de niebla presente en cada píxel. Con esta propiedad se genera un mapa de transmisión que indica cuánto se debe corregir la imagen, el cual puede ser ruidoso y se corrige con el *Guided Filter*, que suaviza la

transmisión mientras mantiene los bordes nítidos. Teniendo este mapa filtrado, se consigue eliminar la neblina en los videos endoscópicos monoculares, con un tiempo de procesamiento de 4.50 segundos por imagen.

Es importante mencionar que no se consideraron las técnicas basadas en aprendizaje profundo debido a la falta de un conjunto de datos quirúrgicos específicos para la tarea.

2. **Detección de Instrumentos Quirúrgicos:** En la segunda etapa correspondiente a la segmentación se decidió emplear **SAM2 (Segment Anything Model 2)**, ya que supera a otros métodos en métricas de segmentación temporal ($\mathcal{J}\&\mathcal{F}$ y \mathcal{G}). Esta superioridad se basa en que, para esta versión, su estructura basada en memoria, garantiza la coherencia *inter-frame*, corrigiendo en última instancia las deficiencias de segmentación observadas en YOLOv11.
3. **Inpainting de Video:** Después de comparar métodos tradicionales (como Ast Marching, Navier-Stokes, Fast Structure Reconstruction), en los cuales se visualizaban artefactos y fallos, se decidió descartar este enfoque. En el enfoque que emplea deep learning se compararon dos propuestas altamente conocidas para esta tarea, una **DeepFillv2** y la otra **STTN (Spatial-Temporal Transformer Network)**; se optó por STTN debido a su capacidad superior para preservar detalles anatómicos y su rendimiento mejorado en PSNR (+2.4%), SSIM (+1.3%) y Ewarp (-19.7%) en Youtube-VOS.
4. **Estimación de Profundidad:** Se implementó **Depth Anything V2**, el método más novedoso al día de realización de este trabajo, que utiliza transformers y un esquema teacher-student para generar etiquetas sintéticas de alta calidad. En los conjunto de datos NYU-D y KITTI alcanza 0.984 en δ_1 , con errores mínimos (AbsRel: 0.045, RMSE: 1.861), confirmando su superioridad respecto a DPT, ZoeDepth y otros métodos.
5. **Estimación de Pose de Cámara:** Se descartaron métodos tradicionales (SfM, COLMAP) por sus limitaciones en escenas quirúrgicas dinámicas. Por tanto, según el enfoque basado en deep learning, se eligió **MonST3R (Monocular Spatio-Temporal 3D Reconstruction)**, un modelo basado en transformers que emplea optimización global y pérdidas de alineación, flujo óptico y suavidad, logrando estimaciones robustas incluso en secuencias con estructuras deformables; siendo, al igual que Depth Anything V2, el método más novedoso al día de realización del trabajo.
6. **Reconstrucción con *Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting*:** Pese a que Deform3DGS demuestra ser el método más eficiente, se decidió realizar una compara-

tiva entre SurgicalGaussian y Deform3DGS empleando el mismo conjunto de datos de EndoNeRF, para observar la calidad de los renderizados de ambos métodos. Los resultados muestran que Deform3DGS es un 62.93% más rápido en la tarea “Pulling” y 46.83% más rápido en la tarea “Cutting”, con una mejora del 35.88% en PSNR en “Pulling”. Además, en 40,000 iteraciones, Deform3DGS obtiene un PSNR de 42.8937 en 20 minutos, mientras que SurgicalGaussian solo alcanza 39.6336 en 1 h 47 min.

Por tanto, se concluyó emplear **Deform3DGS**, ya que permite reconstrucciones más detalladas en menor tiempo, con mejoras en la distribución de puntos (Motion-Aware Point Fusion, MAPF) y en la modelación de deformaciones (Flexible Deformation Modeling, FDM). Sin embargo, se identificaron **limitaciones** en regiones perpetuamente ocluidas por instrumentos quirúrgicos, problemática que se aborda en el proyecto.

En la figura R2, se muestra cómo los componentes previamente presentados, al emplear los métodos con mejor rendimiento en el contexto de escenas quirúrgicas, permiten obtener los resultados deseados. Este procesamiento previo a la generación del *3D Gaussian Splatting* se define como la Fase 1 del *pipeline* global.

Por otro lado, a dicha figura, le acompaña la figura R3, el cual muestra la arquitectura del sistema de InDeform3DGS, el método propuesto en este trabajo para obtener el *Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting* (Fase 2 del *pipeline* global).

Conociendo los métodos a emplear para cada componente, así como el flujo para obtener el conjunto de datos preparado para *3D Gaussian Splatting*, se procedió a su desarrollo e implementación. El desarrollo se puede desglosar por componentes:

- **Módulo de *dehazing*:** Se implementó el Dark Channel Prior (DCP) con Guided Filter con una **interfaz interactiva** que permite ajustar **6 parámetros en tiempo real** para ajustar según la escena quirúrgica. Comparando el DCP con Guided Filter sin esta calibración de parámetros con el DCP con Guided Filter con la calibración de parámetros, se encontró que la entropía aumentó un 3.19% para una escena sin haze, y un 7.74% en la escena con haze. Asimismo, en ambas escenas, la implementación del *dehazing* con calibración de parámetros, aumentó aproximadamente un 113% en varianza laplaciana y el Dark Channel Score, se redujo en 32.06% en la escena sin haze y un 38.07% en la escena con haze. Como se ve, todas las métricas muestran que el *dehaze* con calibración de parámetros mejoró la visibilidad y nitidez de la imagen comparado con el *dehaze* sin calibración de parámetros.
- **Módulo de Detección de Herramientas:** Se entrenó un modelo YOLOv11, empleando una **optimización de hiperparámetros** con **Optuna** en 20 pruebas.

Figure R2 Diagrama del *pipeline* propuesto para la reconstrucción de video endoscópico monocular utilizando *Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting*. Cada etapa del procesamiento está etiquetada con el método correspondiente, incluyendo YOLOv11 para la detección de características, SAM2 para la segmentación de imágenes, DepthAnythingV2 para la estimación de profundidad y STTN para el inpainting de video. También se destacan pasos adicionales como la eliminación de neblina en el video con DCP + GF y la reconstrucción 3D final con InDeform3DGS.

Figure R3 Arquitectura del Sistema InDeform3DGS.

La mejor prueba corresponde al ensayo 11, con un $mAP@[0.50:0.95]$ de 0.752. Los hiperparámetros más influyentes fueron *translate* (25%), *shear* (23%) e *imgsz* (20%). La matriz de confusión mostró que la clase *cautery* logró un 100% de precisión, con un 2% de confusión con *Forceps*. Por otro lado, *Forceps* alcanzó un 88% de precisión, aunque con un 67% de confusión con el fondo, mientras que *suction* obtuvo un 71% de precisión. Cabe mencionar que el conjunto de datos de *Roboflow* utilizado para el entrenamiento es de tamaño reducido, lo que puede afectar la generalización y precisión del modelo en escenarios más complejos.

- **Módulo de Segmentación:** Se empleó SAM2 para la segmentación de imágenes. Dado que el módulo de detección presentaba inconsistencias, se desarrolló un **algoritmo de consistencia temporal** para mejorar la precisión de las máscaras de herramientas quirúrgicas, el cual mostró que la combinación de ambas funcionaba correctamente. Además, se implementó un **procesamiento en lotes** de 50 cuadros para optimizar el balance entre precisión y eficiencia.
- **Módulo de *Inpainting* de Video:** Se implementó el inpainting usando STTN, también, al igual que el módulo *dehazing*, habilitando **parámetros ajustables** para optimizar la coherencia espaciotemporal. Asimismo, se desarrolló el sistema en modo de **procesamiento por lotes** el cual redujo un tiempo 22.46% y RAM un 82.42% respecto a emplear procesamiento cuadro por cuadro.
- **Módulo de Estimación de Profundidad:** Se utilizó *Depth Anything V2*, adoptando un enfoque de **procesamiento en lotes** que redujo el tiempo en un 41.3%, aunque aumentó el uso de GPU en un 164.8% respecto a realizar en procesamiento cuadro por cuadro. Sin embargo, debido a una **disminución en la precisión** de la estimación de profundidad, se optó por utilizar la versión estándar del modelo.
- **Módulo de Estimación de Poses:** Se implementó *MonST3R*, un modelo basado en aprendizaje profundo. Al igual que varios componentes, el **procesamiento en lotes** redujo el tiempo en un 40.64% y el uso de memoria en un 45.68%, sin afectar la estabilidad de las trayectorias generadas.
- **Módulo de Deformable 3DGS:** Con el conjunto de datos preparado, se exploraron dos enfoques para aprovechar la información única proporcionada por el componente de *inpainting*.

El primero, denominado **Modified Deform3DGS**, consistió en modificar el código original de Deform3DGS para permitir el procesamiento de video en formato RGB, profundidad y estimación de pose de la cámara, **eliminando la necesidad de máscaras**, dado que no existen oclusiones.

El segundo método, denominado **InDeform3DGS**, se centró en la optimización del modelo (*Model Optimization*), incorporando un **cálculo de pérdidas** basado en la comparación con el video procesado mediante *inpainting*, descrito a continuación:

1. **Similitud** ($L_{\text{similarity}}$): Alinea regiones inpainteadas.
2. **Profundidad** ($L_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$): Mejora geometría en oclusiones.
3. **Iluminación** ($L_{\text{illumination}}$): Consistencia lumínica.
4. **Diversidad** ($L_{\text{diversity}}$): Evita soluciones triviales con VGG16.
5. **Suavizado de bordes** ($L_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$): Transiciones naturales.
6. **Consistencia temporal** ($L_{\text{time-consistency}}$): Reduce el parpadeo visual.
7. **Ruido** (L_{noise}): Minimiza artefactos.

Disponiendo de todos los métodos desarrollados y optimizados, se llevó a cabo la **integración del software** basada en una **arquitectura modular y escalable**, garantizando también la mantenibilidad y la facilidad de expansión. El código principal y único a ejecutar, sin contar los scripts auxiliares, es `main.py`, el cual fue diseñado con una estructura modular y escalable, permitiendo la independencia de cada componente. Asimismo, se empleó programación orientada a objetos (OOP) para instanciar y ejecutar cada etapa según los requerimientos del usuario.

Mediante la integración de todos los componentes en una arquitectura de software unificada y modular, el sistema quedó preparado para la fase de pruebas, con el objetivo de validar los resultados generados por el *framework* desarrollado.

Para la realización de los experimentos, se estableció un diseño experimental estructurado. En primer lugar, dicho diseño contempla la descripción del entorno experimental, detallando desde los conjuntos de datos empleados para evaluar el *framework* hasta las métricas de evaluación utilizadas para determinar si se logra una mejora o si, por el contrario, se produce un deterioro en la calidad de la reconstrucción 3D.

Los conjuntos de datos utilizados en este trabajo incluyen los conjuntos de datos *Pulling* y *Cutting* de EndoNeRF, los cuales presentan interacciones diferentes con el tejido. Además, se emplearon tres escenas distintas del conjunto de datos de la Universidad de Keio. A diferencia de EndoNeRF, que ya proporciona máscaras de herramientas quirúrgicas, estimaciones de profundidad y estimaciones de pose, los conjuntos de datos de la Universidad de Keio parten de datos en crudo, contando únicamente con el video endoscópico monocular. Por lo tanto, estos últimos pasaron por la fase 1 del *pipeline* global para generar un conjunto de datos listo para la reconstrucción con *3D Gaussian Splatting*.

Para medir las diferencias entre el método propuesto y el método original, se emplearon las métricas **NIQE** (*Natural Image Quality Evaluator*), **BRISQUE** (*Blind/Referenceless Image Spatial Quality Evaluator*), **PSNR** (*Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio*) y **MUSIQ** (*Multi-scale Image Quality Transformer*). Las dos primeras fueron utilizadas para evaluar la calidad de las regiones correspondientes a las herramientas quirúrgicas, donde no hay una referencia disponible. PSNR se empleó para evaluar las regiones que contienen tejido, asegurando que la reconstrucción en estas zonas no se degrade respecto a Deform3DGS original. Finalmente, MUSIQ se utilizó para evaluar la calidad de la imagen completa, proporcionando un análisis tanto local como global mediante su arquitectura basada en transformadores. Como métrica adicional, se definió un nuevo indicador denominado **Final Score**, que combina las métricas mencionadas y se define de la siguiente manera:

$$\text{Final Score} = 0.8 \cdot (0.5 \cdot \text{MUSIQ} - 0.25 \cdot \text{NIQE} - 0.25 \cdot \text{BRISQUE}) + 0.2 \cdot \text{PSNR}$$

Respecto a los experimentos realizados, se llevaron a cabo un total de 12 pruebas, descritas a continuación:

- **Test 1:** Línea base con Deform3DGS utilizando el conjunto de datos "Pulling" de EndoNeRF.
- **Test 2:** Variante Modified Deform3DGS, que introduce directamente el video inpainted en Deform3DGS sin necesidad de utilizar máscaras de herramientas, con el conjunto de datos "Pulling" de EndoNeRF.
- **Test 3:** Análisis del impacto de cada función de pérdida individualmente en el conjunto de datos "Pulling" de EndoNeRF, variando sus pesos de 0.1 a 1.0 en incrementos de 0.1.
- **Test 4:** Optimización bayesiana de los pesos de las funciones de pérdida en el proceso de optimización del modelo con el conjunto de datos "Pulling" de EndoNeRF.
- **Test 5:** Línea base con Deform3DGS utilizando el conjunto de datos "Cutting" de EndoNeRF.
- **Test 6:** InDeform3DGS con los pesos optimizados del Test 4 en el conjunto de datos "Cutting" de EndoNeRF.
- **Test 7:** Línea base con Deform3DGS para la escena 1 del conjunto de datos de la Universidad de Keio.
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- **Test 10:** InDeform3DGS con los pesos optimizados del Test 4 para la escena 3 de la Universidad de Keio.
- **Test 11:** Línea base con Deform3DGS para la escena 4 del conjunto de datos de la Universidad de Keio.
- **Test 12:** InDeform3DGS con los pesos optimizados del Test 4 para la escena 4 de la Universidad de Keio.

Una vez finalizadas las pruebas, se realizó un análisis comparativo de los resultados en pares de experimentos. Las diferencias porcentuales obtenidas se presentan en la Tabla 1.

Test	Tiempo Total	NIQE	BRISQUE	MUSIQ	PSNR	Final Score
Test 1 → Test 2	-22.45%	+6.01%	+7.51%	+3.35%	-2.59%	-4.46%
Test 1 → Test 4	+79.1%	-6.52%	+1.78%	+4.14%	+0.17%	+5.97%
Test 5 → Test 6	+66.0%	-7.97%	-0.48%	+0.94%	+35.24%	+24.99%
Test 7 → Test 8	+24.2%	-82.6%	-1.22%	+3.83%	+0.03%	+26.1%
Test 9 → Test 10	+48.8%	-0.36%	-0.04%	+1.2%	-0.18%	+3.46%
Test 11 → Test 12	+28.5%	+0.82%	+1.19%	+0.42%	+0.0096%	-1.79%

Table 1 Comparación porcentual del uso del modelo **Deform3DGS** frente a **InDeform3DGS** en todos los conjuntos de datos presentados. Las celdas en verde indican mejoras, mientras que las celdas en rojo indican deterioros.

En la Tabla 1 se pueden observar los siguientes aspectos clave:

- Se evidencia que InDeform3DGS introduce un costo computacional adicional en todos los casos, debido a la incorporación del *Model Optimization* propuesto.

Cabe destacar el menor incremento porcentual registrado entre el Test 11 y el Test 12, lo que se debe a que, en este último, se emplea una imagen con tamaño reducido a 224×224 en lugar de 512×512 , como ocurre en los otros dos conjuntos de datos de la Universidad de Keio.

- InDeform3DGS tiende a mejorar la calidad visual en la mayoría de los casos en las regiones ocluidas por las herramientas quirúrgicas. Sin embargo, esta mejora no se observa de manera significativa en el Test 12, lo que indica que a baja resolución, InDeform3DGS no ofrece beneficios notables en dichas zonas.
- InDeform3DGS mantiene consistentemente el valor de PSNR en las áreas que contienen tejido, lo que indica que la incorporación del *Model Optimization* no degrada el rendimiento del modelo original Deform3DGS.

Asimismo, cabe destacar el cambio observado en el Test 6, que experimenta un incremento del 35.26%, atribuido a la corrección introducida por InDeform3DGS.

En el Test 5, utilizando el conjunto de datos *Cutting* de EndoNeRF con el método Deform3DGS, se identificó un problema de reconstrucción incompleta en la zona izquierda de la imagen, lo cual fue corregido en la versión mejorada del modelo.

- Respecto a MUSIQ, InDeform3DGS muestra mejoras en todos los casos, lo que indica que los resultados presentan una calidad superior tanto en términos estéticos—proporcionando imágenes más naturales—como en términos técnicos, considerando aspectos como la nitidez, el ruido y la eliminación de artefactos no deseados.

En la Figura R4 se ilustra el problema presentado por Deform3DGS en las **zonas de oclusión prolongada**. Se observa que, en el cuadro 70, el modelo Deform3DGS genera una **región negra** debido a la falta de información, mientras que InDeform3DGS es capaz de reconstruir el tejido correspondiente a dicha zona previamente ocluida.

Asimismo, se evidencia el problema de Deform3DGS en la reconstrucción de **zonas con oclusión de corta duración**. En el cuadro 0, aunque Deform3DGS comienza a generar una reconstrucción con mayor coherencia visual, su rendimiento no es equiparable al de InDeform3DGS, que consigue **delinear con precisión los bordes**, diferenciando claramente los tres tipos de tejido visibles en la imagen ampliada del cuadro 0.

Figure R4 Comparación cualitativa entre Deform3DGS (Test 7) e InDeform3DGS (Test 8) en la Escena 1 del conjunto de datos de la Universidad de Keio para los cuadros 0 y 70. En el cuadro 0, Deform3DGS no maneja correctamente la herramienta quirúrgica, dejando artefactos visibles, mientras que InDeform3DGS reconstruye la zona y revela el tejido subyacente. En el cuadro 70, Deform3DGS mantiene una región negra debido a la oclusión prolongada, mientras que InDeform3DGS elimina la herramienta y reconstruye el borde del tejido amarillo con mayor coherencia visual.

Tras la finalización de los experimentos y su análisis detallado, este trabajo se consolida como un enfoque novedoso para la reconstrucción 3D de videos endoscópicos monoculares de escenas quirúrgicas mediante *Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting*. La metodología

propuesta aborda con éxito la **ausencia de un proceso de preparación de conjunto de datos** específicos para *3D Gaussian Splatting* en este dominio, proporcionando un pipeline automatizado de extremo a extremo que genera conjuntos de datos listos para su uso en InDeform3DGS.

En cuanto a la segunda etapa del proceso, **InDeform3DGS** ha demostrado resolver la principal limitación identificada en Deform3DGS: la reconstrucción de regiones afectadas por oclusiones recurrentes de herramientas quirúrgicas en cirugías mínimamente invasivas, dando por alcanzado el objetivo central de este proyecto.

Palabras clave: Reconstrucción 3D, Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting, Cirugía mínimamente invasiva, Visión por computadora, Aprendizaje profundo, Estimación de profundidad, Estimación de la posición de la cámara, Relleno de imágenes (Inpainting), Detección de características, Segmentación de imágenes, Eliminación de niebla en imágenes, Optimización de modelos, Procesamiento por lotes.

UNESCO codes:

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- **3314.84 – Ingeniería Biomédica**
- **1203.10 – Enseñanza Con Ayuda de Ordenador**
- **3304.17 - Sistemas en Tiempo Real**
- **3304.95 - Gráficos 3D, realidad virtual y realidad aumentada**

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List of Acronyms

- 3DGS:** 3D Gaussian Splatting
- NeRF:** Neural Radiance Fields
- PSNR:** Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio
- MIS:** Minimally Invasive Surgery
- MRI:** Magnetic Resonance Imaging
- CT:** Computed Tomography
- HVRL:** HyperVision Research Laboratory
- AR:** Augmented Reality
- VR:** Virtual Reality
- RL:** Reinforcement Learning
- FDA:** U.S. Food and Drug Administration
- SDG:** Sustainable Development Goals
- GPU:** Graphics Processing Unit
- ML:** Machine Learning
- AI:** Artificial Intelligence
- Omniverse:** NVIDIA Omniverse
- HCI:** Human-Computer Interaction
- API:** Application Programming Interface

- TDA**: Topological Data Analysis
- SfM**: Structure-from-Motion
- MVS**: Multi-View Stereo
- SIFT**: Scale-Invariant Feature Transform
- SURF**: Speeded-Up Robust Features
- ORB**: Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF
- MLP**: Multi-Layer Perceptron
- CNN**: Convolutional Neural Network
- GAN**: Generative Adversarial Network
- LiDAR**: Light Detection and Ranging
- GPS**: Global Positioning System
- NBI**: Narrow-Band Imaging
- SH**: Spherical Harmonics
- RNN**: Recurrent Neural Network
- GA-Net**: Guided Aggregation Net for End-to-End Stereo Matching
- SSD**: Signed Distance Function
- RF**: Random Forest
- CNN-MVS**: Convolutional Neural Network Multi-View Stereo
- FastNeRF**: High-Fidelity Neural Rendering at 3000 FPS
- Deblur-NeRF**: Deblurring Neural Radiance Fields
- AlignNeRF**: High-Fidelity Neural Radiance Fields
- MVSNet**: Multi-View Stereo Network
- Point-MVSNet**: Point-Based Multi-View Stereo Network
- EndoGS**: Deformable Endoscopic Tissue Reconstruction
- Free-SurGS**: SfM-Free 3D Gaussian Splatting for Surgery

- EndoGaussian**: Real-Time Gaussian Splatting for Endoscopic Scenes
- SurgicalGaussian**: Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting for Surgical Scenes
- Deform3DGS**: Flexible Deformation Modeling for Fast 3D Reconstruction
- APP_bbox**: Average Bounding Box Precision
- AbsRel**: Absolute Relative Error
- CAP**: Context-Aware Propagation
- COCO**: Common Objects in Context
- COLMAP**: Structure-from-Motion Pipeline
- CUDA**: Compute Unified Device Architecture
- DCP**: Dark Channel Prior
- DINOv2**: Distilled and Improved Vision Transformer
- DPT**: Depth Prediction Transformer
- DUST3R**: Dense Unsupervised Structure from Motion with Transformers
- Ewarp**: Flow Warp Error
- FDM**: Flexible Deformation Modeling
- FFmpeg**: Fast Forward Moving Picture Experts Group
- FSR**: Fast Structure Reconstruction
- Git**: Global Information Tracker
- GitHub**: Git Repository Hosting Service
- IDE**: Integrated Development Environment
- IoU**: Intersection over Union
- KITTI**: Karlsruhe Institute of Technology and Toyota Technological Institute Dataset
- LGTSM**: Long-Term Spatio-Temporal Memory
- MAPF**: Motion-Aware Point Fusion
- mAP**: Mean Average Precision

MonST3R: Monocular Spatio-Temporal 3D Reconstruction

MOS: Mean Opinion Score

MOSE: Multi-Object Segmentation Evaluation

NMS: Non-Maximum Suppression

NVMe: Non-Volatile Memory Express

PCIe: Peripheral Component Interconnect Express

PnP: Perspective-n-Point

RAM: Random Access Memory

RANSAC: Random Sample Consensus

ROI: Region of Interest

SAM2: Segment Anything Model 2

SSIM: Structural Similarity Index Measure

SSI Loss: Scale- and Shift-Invariant Loss

STTN: Spatial-Temporal Transformer Networks

TFM: Trabajo de Fin de Máster

ViT: Vision Transformer

VINet: Video Inpainting Network

VS Code: Visual Studio Code

YOLO: You Only Look Once

List of Symbols

$I(x)$: Input foggy image

$J(x)$: Clear image to be recovered

A : Atmospheric light

$t(x)$: Transmission map

$J_{\text{dark}}(x)$: Dark channel

$\mathcal{J}\&\mathcal{F}$: Overlap precision and contour quality metric

\mathcal{G} : Generalization metric

$\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3$: Depth estimation accuracy metrics

RMSE: Root Mean Square Error

log10: Logarithmic depth error

α : Opacity in Gaussian Splatting

Σ : Covariance matrix in Gaussian Splatting

μ : Center of a 3D Gaussian

J : Jacobian of the projective transformation

\mathcal{L} : Loss function in Gaussian Splatting

B : Stereo baseline

d : Stereo disparity

f : Focal length in stereo vision

z : Depth in stereo vision

$\mathcal{L}_{\text{D-SSIM}}$: Loss based on Differentiated Structural Similarity Index

$L_{\text{similarity}}$: Similarity: Aligns inpainted regions

$L_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$: Depth: Improves geometry in occlusions

$L_{\text{illumination}}$: Illumination: Ensures lighting consistency

$L_{\text{diversity}}$: Diversity: Avoids trivial solutions using VGG16

$L_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$: Edge Smoothing: Natural transitions

$L_{\text{time-consistency}}$: Temporal Consistency: Reduces visual flickering

L_{noise} : Noise: Minimizes artifacts

Introduction

The first chapter establishes the broader context for this research, detailing the motivation behind the study, its relevance, and the significance of addressing the challenges associated with 3D reconstruction in surgical scenes. Additionally, it outlines the objectives of the thesis, highlights the key contributions made throughout the project, and provides an overview of the document's structure to guide the reader effectively.

1.1 Background

The emergence of **Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS)** has revolutionized modern medicine due to its numerous advantages over traditional open procedures, which are directly associated with a considerable reduction in postoperative pain, shorter hospital stays, faster recovery times, lower risks of infection, among other improvements Cleveland Clinic 2023.

While some MIS procedures, such as brain surgeries which they rely on preoperative imaging techniques like **Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)** or **Computed Tomography (CT)** scans instead of intraoperative camera feeds, a significant number of minimally invasive interventions are heavily dependent on real-time visual feedback. Procedures like **laparoscopy**, **arthroscopy**, and **endoscopy** are prime examples, accounting for approximately 34.17 million interventions in North America, representing 10.05% of the U.S. population in 2024 (Shah et al. 2018) (North Kansas City Hospital 2024) (The Insight Partners 2023). Endoscopy alone constitutes 17.4 million of these procedures in the United States, with the number rising considerably when including Mexico and Canada. This trend continues on an upward trajectory, with global endoscopy procedures expected to reach 207.59 million by 2030, emphasizing the continuous growth and increasing adoption of MIS techniques worldwide (Grand View Research 2024).

Within this framework, the present work is developed as a response to the challenges

posed by MIS, particularly in reconstructing surgical scenes in three dimensions using monocular endoscopic video. The research has been conducted at **Keio University**, one of Japan’s most prestigious institutions, ranked **165th globally**, **5th in Japan**, and **17th in Asia**, due to its strong focus on research and innovation across various disciplines (EduRank 2024).

Part of Keio’s research excellence is driven by the **HyperVision Research Laboratory (HVRL)**, a pioneering lab in the field of **computer vision** led by **Professor Hideo Saito**, an internationally recognized expert in computer vision and **augmented reality**. His academic impact is numerically reflected in his **Google Scholar profile**, where his work has been cited over **8,000 times** with an **h-index of 43**, highlighting the extensive influence and depth of his contributions to the field (Google Scholar 2024).

Moreover, although the HVRL has conducted numerous cutting-edge research projects across diverse areas, it also stands out for its contributions to significant advancements in medical applications, particularly in improving surgical interventions through computer vision technologies. Notable contributions include **Haowen Hu et al.**’s study on *”Multi-Camera Multi-Person Tracking and Re-Identification in an Operating Room”* (Hu et al. 2022), **Ryo Fujio et al.**’s work on *”Surgical Tool Detection in Open Surgery Videos”* (Fujio et al. 2022), and **Mizuki Obayashi et al.**’s research on *”Multi-View Surgical Camera Calibration with Non-Feature-Rich Video Frames: Toward 3D Surgery Playback”* (Obayashi et al. 2023), all of which were supervised by Professor Hideo Saito, showcasing his extensive knowledge in the field and the lab’s strong connection to medical institutions, such as hospitals and medical schools, which provide valuable datasets and testing grounds for their innovations.

Beyond its contributions to medical applications, the HVRL has a long-standing history in **3D reconstruction research**, with groundbreaking projects that explore novel technologies. One such recent project involves the use of **event cameras** combined with the **Gaussian Splatting** technique, which emerged just a year before this thesis began, in July 2023 (Kerbl et al. 2023). Building on this method, **Hiroyuki Deguchi et al.** proposed an innovative approach to 3D reconstruction and view synthesis presenting *”E2GS: Event Enhanced Gaussian Splatting”* in June 2024 (Deguchi et al. 2024).

In this context, the present study is developed in a highly technically qualified laboratory with extensive knowledge of novel 3D reconstruction techniques and privileged access to hard-to-obtain data to contribute to this growing type of intervention, which still present significant challenges. One of the most critical issues in **camera-assisted surgeries** is the difficulty in achieving accurate **spatial perception** due to the limitations of **two-dimensional imaging**, **occlusion** caused by surgical instruments that prevents the surgeon from adequately seeing the target areas, and **visual fatigue** from prolonged viewing of surgical images on monitors, which can increase surgery times and the risk of errors (Liu et al. 2023).

To date, the **3D reconstruction of surgical scenes** remains a relatively explored area of research, presenting unique challenges such as **soft tissue deformation** and the **constant movement of surgical tools**. This is evident from the limited number of references available in academic databases like Web of Science, which lists only 20 relevant works using the *3D AND (Surgical Scene) AND (deform*) AND (reconstruction) AND (tissue) NOT (print*)*, with the earliest appearing in 2016 by Wei-Che Lin and Kai-Tai Song, who proposed the use of endoscopic imagery and real-time 3D reconstruction to estimate contact force during Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS) without requiring physical force sensors (Lin and Song 2016). Overcoming these challenges carries significant **technical** and **medical implications**, as it presents the potential to revolutionize surgical procedures by improving the **learning curve for surgeons** through the use of **virtual reality**, a field that reached **\$4.8 billion** in Europe alone by **2024** (International Data Corporation (IDC) 2024). Additionally, 3D reconstruction can pave the way for **autonomous surgical robots** by creating a **digital twin** of the human body, enabling robots to be trained through **reinforcement learning** on simulation platforms like **NVIDIA Omniverse** (fig. 1.1), which allows simultaneous training of multiple robots, accelerating the learning process and increases the robots' robustness by exposing them to a broader range of scenarios.

Figure 1.1 Robots training simultaneously with RL in a simulated Omniverse environment (NVIDIA 2024b).

The leading robot in this field is the **Da Vinci Surgical Robot** (fig. 1.2), recognized as the first robotic surgical system to receive approval from the **U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA)** for use in general laparoscopic procedures (Pugin, Bucher, and Morel 2011). In **2023** alone, it accounted for **2.29 million interventions**, showing an **annual growth of 21.81%** compared to **2022** (Statista 2024), reflecting the growing awareness among hospitals of the advantages of using the Da Vinci robot, particularly due to its greater **precision and control** during surgery, which contributes to reducing operative risks. Moreover, the Da Vinci system offers faster **patient recovery times**,

compensating for the initial investment by lowering **hospitalization days**, reducing the need for **follow-up interventions**, and shortening **surgical durations**, ultimately opening new horizons for the number of procedures that can be performed daily and making robotic surgery more accessible to a broader population (Gutiérrez 2024).

Figure 1.2 Surgeon performing Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS) using the Da Vinci robot. (Operarme 2024).

1.2 Motivation

The decision to pursue this master’s thesis project originated from a personal and growing interest in **computer vision**, which had already been explored during my undergraduate thesis titled *”Perception Module for a Robot Based on the DepthAI Platform”* (Xu 2022). **Computer vision** is widely acknowledged as a fast-evolving discipline with extensive applications across various sectors, such as **retail**, **autonomous vehicles**, **robotics**, and **medical imaging**, which has **become** the focus of this work. This field demonstrates remarkable progress by enabling the replication of the human visual system’s integration of eyes and brain, and in some cases, even surpassing the natural limitations of human perception, thereby opening new possibilities for **automation** and **precision** in critical tasks.

Building on the exploration of the field, the focus on **Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS)** was influenced by a personal experience with shoulder surgery. After suffering from recurrent shoulder dislocations due to a *Bankart lesion*, a tear in the glenoid labrum caused by repeated dislocations, and a *Hill-Sachs lesion*, a fracture in the humeral head, it became necessary to undergo surgery. It must be recognized that, at first, the idea of undergoing such a procedure caused significant anxiety due to the invasive nature of traditional open surgery. However, during consultations with Dr. Eduard Alentorn Gelí, the **minimally invasive approach** of **arthroscopic surgery** was introduced (fig. 1.3). The technique, previously unknown to me, was explained in detail, leading to

a deeper understanding of its **advantages**, which I personally experienced through a **rapid recovery** and highly **positive results**, allowing for the **reengagement** of physical activities that had previously been restricted by frequent shoulder dislocations.

Figure 1.3 Shoulder arthroscopy surgery (Bangalore Shoulder Institute 2024).

Parallel to this personal experience, a growing fascination with **3D reconstruction techniques**, particularly *Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF)*, further influenced the selection of this thesis topic. The subsequent development of **Gaussian Splatting**, a method that significantly enhances NeRF by offering faster and more efficient reconstructions, presented a promising area of exploration, ultimately guiding the focus towards **medical applications**. Given the increasing adoption of **virtual reality (VR)** and **augmented reality (AR)** in healthcare, along with advancements in **reinforcement learning** platforms such as *NVIDIA's Omniverse*, the potential use of **3D reconstructions of surgical environments** for training purposes was identified as highly valuable. These technological advancements could eventually enable **fully autonomous surgical procedures** with high precision, enhanced efficiency, and minimal error rates, making such procedures more accessible to a broader population and addressing both **patient needs** and **healthcare system demands**, as reflected in the annual surgical statistics referenced earlier.

The potential contributions of **digital twins** in surgical environments extend beyond **robotic systems**, particularly in the short term, as the development of fully autonomous surgical robots is expected to take longer due to **technical, ethical, and regulatory challenges**. Nevertheless, aligning digital twin use cases with existing healthcare practices is more likely to be standardized and certified in the near future. Key applications include the use of **digital twins** for **preoperative planning** and **surgical simulations**, which can significantly reduce **human error** during procedures. Additionally, **digital twins** can facilitate **learning processes**, not only by advancing **robotic autonomy**, but also by improving **surgeon training** through **virtual reality (VR) environments**. Reducing **human error** remains a critical priority, as demonstrated in a study conducted

by the *University Hospital of Álava*, which reported that, out of 1,000 surgeries, 2.2% resulted in major complications, a figure that must be minimized (Guerra et al. 2011). Furthermore, improving **precision** and **efficiency** through better **preoperative planning** would make surgical procedures more accessible to a broader population by shortening **postoperative recovery periods** and enabling faster **patient discharge**.

Given its significant potential, it is essential to acknowledge that this field of research remains in its early stages, with the first major work on **surgical digital twins** published in 2019 by Su et al., proposing a novel multicamera approach for dynamic 3D reconstruction of surgical cavities (Su, Huang, and Hannaford 2019). The limited number of contributions identified in academic databases, as previously mentioned, highlights both the **novelty** of the topic and the need for further **research** in this area. Consequently, this thesis aims to contribute to the long-term objective of developing more **accurate** and **realistic digital twins** that can enhance current **practices** and, ultimately, address the **challenges** identified previously.

1.3 Objectives

The primary objective of this master’s thesis is to develop a comprehensive method that transforms raw monocular endoscopic video into a **deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting representation** for reconstructing **surgical scenes with surgical tools removed**. This method must be sufficiently robust to be applicable across a wide range of **Minimally Invasive Surgeries (MIS)**.

To achieve the primary objective, the following specific objectives have been defined:

- **Conduct** a thorough **review of state-of-the-art 3D reconstruction methods**, with a particular focus on techniques that address **tissue deformation**. This review will identify their strengths, limitations, and relevance to the proposed system, serving as a foundation for the methodological framework.
- **Analyze** and **select** appropriate **algorithms and techniques** for key components of the system, which include **object detection**, **image segmentation**, **depth estimation**, **video inpainting**, and **camera pose estimation**. The selected methodologies will be integrated to ensure compatibility and optimal system performance.
- **Design** and **implement** a fully **automated preprocessing pipeline** capable of processing **raw monocular endoscopic video** to produce intermediate outputs, such as inpainted frames, depth maps, and camera poses. This pipeline will provide the essential data for constructing the final 3D representations.

- **Optimize** the **computational efficiency** and **scalability** of the pipeline to address the high computational demands associated with processing endoscopic video and generating deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting representations.
- **Develop** and **optimize** the system for generating **deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting representations** of **surgical environments**. The system must accurately capture and reconstruct the surgical scene while ensuring the effective removal of occlusions caused by surgical tools. It must also maintain compatibility across a variety of MIS scenarios.
- **Evaluate** the developed system across diverse **minimally invasive surgical contexts** using established performance metrics. These metrics will include reconstruction accuracy, depth estimation error, spatial consistency, and measurable perceptual quality.

1.4 Work Contributions

The completion of the previously defined objectives has led to a set of contributions that advance the current state of the art in the reconstruction of surgical scenes from monocular endoscopic video. These contributions are outlined as follows, detailing the specific advancements achieved throughout the development of this work:

1. **Development of a Surgical Tool Detection Algorithm:** An algorithm was developed to detect surgical tools present in raw monocular endoscopic video using YOLOv11, the most recent version of the YOLO family of object detection models, which significantly surpasses previous YOLO models in terms of inference time, mean Average Precision (mAP), model size (measured in MB), and computational efficiency (measured in GFLOPS and latency).
2. **Practical Reuse and Enhancement of Existing Algorithms:** A thorough review of existing algorithms and techniques was conducted to identify the most suitable approaches for each stage of the pipeline, including video dehazing, image segmentation, depth estimation, video inpainting, and camera pose estimation. Beyond the review, significant adaptations and improvements were implemented, focusing particularly on enhancing computational efficiency in tasks such as inpainting, depth map generation, and segmentation.
3. **Development of an Automated Pipeline for Raw Monocular Endoscopic Video Processing:** A fully automated pipeline was designed and implemented to process raw monocular endoscopic video and generate intermediate outputs necessary for the deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting process. The pipeline includes surgical tool detection, segmentation, inpainting, depth estimation, and camera pose

estimation. This workflow ensures that clean, preprocessed data is provided as input for the 3D reconstruction system.

- 4. Development and Optimization of a Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting System:** An existing deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting method called Deform3DGS was adapted and optimized to address the problem of tool occlusions in surgical scene reconstruction. By incorporating an inpainting process applied to the raw video frames and integrating it into the original system architecture, the reconstructed 3D representations were significantly improved in terms of accuracy and completeness. This new enhanced approach, referred to as the **InDeform3DGS** method, ensures that the system can handle challenging occlusions caused by surgical tools, resulting in more accurate and visually coherent 3D reconstructions.

1.5 Structure of the Document

This document is divided into six chapters, followed by a bibliography that provides the references used throughout the research and two appendices that detail additional relevant aspects of the project. The structure of the document is outlined as follows:

- **Chapter 1 - Introduction:** The first chapter provides the overall context in which this research was conducted, outlining the motivation behind the study, its relevance, and the importance of addressing the challenges associated with 3D reconstruction in surgical scenes. This chapter also presents the objectives of the thesis, the contributions made throughout the project and the structure of the document to guide the reader.
- **Chapter 2 - Literature Review:** This chapter offers a comprehensive review of the theoretical foundations relevant to the research. It begins by contextualizing the use of endoscopic videos in Minimally Invasive Surgeries (MIS) and providing an overview of the core concepts of MIS and endoscopic video technology. The chapter then presents an analysis of different 3D representation methods, followed by a detailed examination of the most relevant 3D reconstruction techniques, ranging from traditional approaches to those based on deep learning. Subsequently, it focuses on the application of 3D Gaussian Splatting in surgical scenes, exploring its potential contributions as well as the challenges it faces in this field.
- **Chapter 3 - Methodology:** Chapter 3 details the hardware and software employed in the development of the system. The software section is broken down by the core components of the automated pipeline, explaining the reasons behind the selection of each algorithm and providing the theoretical background for their application.

- **Chapter 4 - System Development:** This chapter presents the complete architecture of the developed system. It includes a detailed description of how the hardware components were configured to ensure the system's functionality. Furthermore, it outlines the development and optimization of each core component of the system, describing the integration process that led to the creation of a fully automated pipeline for 3D Gaussian Splatting in surgical scene reconstruction.
- **Chapter 5 - Results and Discussion:** Chapter 5 focuses on the validation and evaluation of the developed system. It begins by explaining the validation methods and comparison criteria, followed by a detailed description of the performance metrics chosen for evaluation and the reasons for their selection. The chapter then defines the tests conducted on the system and presents the results obtained, followed by a critical discussion of the findings.
- **Chapter 6 - Conclusions:** The final chapter summarizes the achievements of this thesis, highlighting the contributions made to the state of the art and the research objectives accomplished. It also addresses the limitations and challenges encountered throughout the project and outlines potential directions for future work to further improve the system and expand its applicability.

The document includes two appendices that provide additional insights into the organizational and technical aspects of the project:

- **Appendix A - Temporal Planning and Budget:** This appendix presents the organizational aspects of the project, including a detailed timeline of the work conducted and an estimated budget to complete the research.
- **Appendix B - Applications and Impact Assessment:** This appendix examines the professional, legal, and societal implications of the research, highlighting its impact on surgical training, AI-assisted procedures, and healthcare efficiency, while aligning with relevant Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
- **Appendix C - Code Repository and Experimental:** This appendix includes the official repository of the project along with the logs of the tests conducted in the presented work.

Literature Review

This chapter provides a comprehensive review of the theoretical foundations central to the research. It begins by contextualizing the use of endoscopic videos in Minimally Invasive Surgeries (MIS) and offering an overview of the core concepts of MIS and endoscopic video technology. The chapter then analyzes various **3D representation methods**, distinguishing between **explicit** and **implicit** approaches, while discussing their respective strengths and limitations. Following this, it examines the most relevant **3D reconstruction techniques**, ranging from **traditional methods** to advanced **deep learning-based approaches**. Finally, the chapter provides a detailed exploration of **3D Gaussian Splatting** applied to surgical scenes along with its practical applications. The chapter concludes by addressing the challenges associated with this approach.

2.1 Endoscopic Videos in Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS)

2.1.1 Origin and Use of Endoscopic Videos in Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS)

Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS) covers a wide range of techniques aimed at reducing surgical trauma, recovery time, and post-operative complications by minimizing the size of incisions and the extent of internal tissue damage. Although the common perception is that these techniques involve making small incisions to insert cameras for visualization, allowing surgeons to perform procedures similar to traditional open surgeries, there are various MIS approaches that do not rely on endoscopic cameras. For instance, percutaneous interventions use imaging techniques such as fluoroscopy, ultrasound, computed tomography (CT), or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) for guidance. However, a significant number of MIS procedures incorporate endoscopic imaging systems to improve

the surgeon's ability to visualize internal organs during procedures that involve complex anatomical structures, such as **laparoscopic cholecystectomy**, **hysterectomy**, and **robot-assisted prostatectomy** (Cleveland Clinic 2023).

The origin of endoscopic videos can be traced to early developments in medical instrumentation designed to visualize internal body cavities without the need for large incisions. The earliest attempts at endoscopy date back to Hippocrates (460–370 BC), who employed a **rectal speculum** (fig. 2.1a), a tubular device typically made of metal or plastic, inserted into the rectum to separate the walls of the anal canal, thereby allowing visualization of internal structures (Bernard 2007). Further evidence of ancient interest in minimally invasive practices can be observed in the excavations of the Roman city of Pompeii, which was buried by a volcanic eruption in 79 A.D., revealing a **vaginal speculum** (fig. 2.1b) and additional instruments resembling modern laparoscopic trocars (Bernard 2007).

Figure 2.1 Ancient Roman Surgical Tools (Claude Moore Health Sciences Library, University of Virginia 2007).

The first significant step toward modern endoscopy came from Phillip Bozzini in 1806, who invented the "Lichtleiter" or "light conductor" (fig. 2.3), a device that used candle-light and mirrors to inspect body cavities, marking the transition from direct observation to instrument-based visualization. Inspired by Bozzini's work, the French surgeon Antoine Jean Desormeaux developed a similar device for urological examinations in the 1850s, using an alcohol-turpentine flame as a light source, which posed a significant risk of burns. Another attempt to improve endoscopic visualization was made by Adolph Kussmaul, a German physician, who in 1868 focused on examining the esophagus and stomach using a gasoline lamp for illumination. Significant advancements followed with the introduction of electric light sources and cooling mechanisms by Maximilian Nitze, who in 1877 created the first urethroscope with an integrated light source, laying the foundation for clinical endoscopy (Spaner and Warnock 1997).

The use of endoscopy for surgical purposes began to gain traction in the early 20th century, with Georg Kelling performing the first documented laparoscopic procedure. In 1901, Kelling introduced the concept of "**celioscopy**" by using a modified cystoscope to

Figure 2.2 Illustration of Philipp Bozzini (1779-1809) and the Lichtleiter (Chirurgische Klinik Frankfurt Höchst 2006).

inspect the abdominal cavity of a dog after insufflating the abdomen with air. Around that same period, in 1910, Hans Christian Jacobaeus expanded on Kelling's work by performing 17 diagnostic laparoscopic procedures on human patients suffering from ascites, a contribution that earned him widespread recognition as the "inventor of human laparoscopy and thoracoscopy" (Alkatout et al. 2021).

Years later, during the mid-20th century, technological advancements in optics and illumination further transformed endoscopic procedures. The development of the **Hopkins glass rod-lens system** by Harold Hopkins in the 1950s significantly improved image quality by transmitting light more efficiently through a series of glass rods, enhancing image clarity by a factor of 80 compared to previous optical systems. Around the same period, **fiber-optic technology**, pioneered by Harold Hopkins and Narinder Kapany, introduced a flexible and more efficient method for transmitting light through thin glass fibers, enabling the creation of flexible endoscopes. The combination of glass rod-lens optics and fiber optics established the foundation for modern endoscopic systems, improving the safety, accuracy, and usability of endoscopic tools in clinical practice (Nakayama 2017).

The transition to **solid-state camera technology** and portable video systems did not occur until the 1980s, marking a significant turning point in laparoscopic surgery as it provided surgeons with an external view of the surgical field without the need to maintain direct eye contact with the scope. However, the widespread adoption of laparoscopic

surgery occurred in the late 1980s and early 1990s, led by Arnold Pier and Friedrich Götz, who performed laparoscopic appendectomies on hundreds of patients, reporting low conversion rates to open surgery, with conversion required in only 2% of cases. Similarly, Erich Mühe in Germany and Jacques Perissat in France contributed to the popularization of laparoscopic cholecystectomy, demonstrating the safety and feasibility of the procedure. Their presentations at major surgical conferences in 1989, where they showcased the undeniable benefits of laparoscopic surgery, including smaller, less painful incisions, faster recovery times, and reduced hospital stays, generated significant interest in laparoscopic techniques, leading to an unprecedented expansion across nearly all major surgical specialties (Nakayama 2017).

Figure 2.3 Illustration of an upper endoscopy procedure using a flexible endoscope (Asian Institute of Gastroenterology 2024).

Today, endoscopic videos form an essential component of modern Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS). The integration of real-time visualization, high-definition imaging, and robotic-assisted technology has enabled surgeons to perform increasingly complex procedures with enhanced precision and safety. Furthermore, the incorporation of **three-dimensional (3D) imaging** and **augmented reality** into surgical systems has significantly improved the ability to navigate intricate anatomical structures. As technology continues to evolve, Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS) is expected to incorporate even more sophisticated features, such as **artificial intelligence (AI)**, ensuring that video-assisted procedures remain at the forefront of surgical innovation.

2.1.2 Types of Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS)

Minimally Invasive Surgery (MIS) can be classified according to various criteria, but two primary criteria most relevant to the work presented are highlighted below: the type of access used to reach internal structures and the imaging guidance employed during the procedure.

Classification Based on Access Type

The type of access used in MIS refers to how surgeons reach internal organs and structures. Depending on the procedure, access can be achieved through natural orifices, small incisions, or specialized instruments. Each approach offers unique advantages depending on the target area and the complexity of the procedure (Peters, Ellison, and Matthews 2006).

1. **Endoscopy:** Refers to the procedure of inserting a thin, flexible tube equipped with a camera and light source through natural body orifices, such as the mouth, nose or urethra, to visualize internal structures. It is commonly used for diagnostic and therapeutic procedures in gastroenterology, pulmonology, and urology. Examples may include bronchoscopy (inspection of the airways), colonoscopy (inspection of the colon) and hysteroscopy (examination of the uterus).
2. **Laparoscopy:** Involves accessing the abdominal cavity through small incisions to perform surgical procedures. A laparoscope, equipped with a camera, provides a magnified view of internal organs, allowing for precision during surgery. Common procedures include appendectomy, cholecystectomy and hernia repair.
3. **Thoracoscopy:** MIS where the thoracic cavity is accessed through small incisions in the chest wall, used for diagnosing and treating conditions within the lungs, pleura, and mediastinum.
4. **Arthroscopy:** Allows the examination and treatment of joint conditions. Small incisions are made to insert a camera and specialized instruments into the joint. Common procedures include knee arthroscopy and shoulder arthroscopy.
5. **Percutaneous Surgery:** It involves accessing internal structures through a small puncture in the skin, typically guided by imaging techniques, commonly used in interventional radiology and cardiology for procedures such as angioplasty and biopsy.
6. **Robotic Surgery:** Employs advanced robotic systems, such as the da Vinci Surgical System, to enhance the precision and reach of minimally invasive procedures. Surgeons control robotic arms equipped with surgical instruments and a high-definition camera, allowing for greater maneuverability and accuracy.

7. **Transluminal Surgery:** Also referred to as NOTES (Natural Orifice Transluminal Endoscopic Surgery), is a minimally invasive surgical technique that involves accessing internal organs through a natural body orifice, such as the mouth, anus, vagina or urethra, and then perforating the wall of an internal organ to reach another area of the body (fig. 2.4). This approach eliminates the need for external incisions, reducing surgical trauma and improving recovery times.

Figure 2.4 Transluminal surgery (NOTES) with four types of access to the abdominal cavity: (a) Transoral, through the esophagus; (b) Transanal, through the colon; (c) Transurethral, through the male reproductive organ; and (d) Transvaginal, through the vagina (Tyson and Humphreys 2014).

Classification Based on Imaging Guidance

MIS techniques can also be classified based on the type of imaging guidance used during the procedure. Imaging systems provide real-time visualization, which assists surgeons in navigating through internal structures and performing interventions with more accuracy (Berch 2014).

1. **Video Endoscopy:** It is the most common form of imaging guidance in MIS. It involves inserting a small camera into the body to provide real-time visualization of internal structures, allowing surgeons to perform precise interventions.
2. **Ultrasound (US):** By using high-frequency sound waves, it creates images of internal organs. It is commonly used to guide percutaneous interventions such as biopsies, catheter placements, and drainages.

3. **Fluoroscopy:** Provides real-time X-ray imaging, making it essential for guiding procedures such as angioplasty, stent placements, and spinal injections.
4. **Computed Tomography (TC):** CT imaging, with its 3D visual details, may enable surgeons to better plan and approach complex procedures. This mainly applies to surgeries in oncology and trauma surgery.
5. **Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI):** MRI provides high-resolution images of soft tissues, making it particularly useful for guiding procedures in neurosurgery, orthopedics, and cardiology.
6. **Surgical Navigation Systems:** Surgical navigation systems use advanced positioning technologies to guide surgeons in real time, functioning similarly to GPS systems. These systems are particularly valuable in procedures where precision is critical, such as orthopedic, neurosurgical, and ENT (Ear, Nose, and Throat) surgeries.

2.1.3 Modern Endoscopic Videos

Building on the classification framework presented in the previous section, which highlights the significant role of video endoscopy in MIS, the current endoscopic systems are introduced. These systems differ in both designs and capabilities, as each serves specific clinical purposes depending on the type of procedure and the complexity of the surgical field.

1. **Monocular Endoscopic Videos:** These are the most basic and widely used video systems in MIS due to their simplicity and cost-effectiveness. These systems consist of a single camera attached to an endoscope, providing a two-dimensional (2D) view of the surgical field. Monocular systems are commonly used in routine procedures where depth perception is less critical, such as gastrointestinal endoscopy, bronchoscopy, and hysteroscopy (Zhong et al. 2024).
2. **Stereo Endoscopic Videos:** Stereo endoscopic systems utilize dual-camera configurations to capture three-dimensional visual information, replicating human binocular vision and enabling depth perception, which is critical for complex surgical procedures that require precise tissue and instrument manipulation. Such systems are commonly used in procedures such as laparoscopic suturing, thoracic surgery or robot-assisted surgery (Zhong et al. 2024). A noteworthy example is the ENDO-EYE FLEX 3D system developed by Olympus, which incorporates a dual-lens design for image capturing and display the captured images on a specialized 3D monitor (Olympus America 2024). The surgical team, equipped with polarized glasses, can perceive the operative field in three dimensions, thereby enhancing spatial awareness

(fig. 2.5). It is worth noting that this system has been approved by the FDA for clinical use since 2013 (U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) 2013), and two years prior, the first intervention using this system was performed at the Hospital Clínic de Barcelona by Dr. Antonio de Lacy and his team (Barnaclínic+ 2011).

Figure 2.5 Surgical team performing MIS using a stereo endoscopic system with polarized glasses (Melaka Fertility Centre 2024).

3. **3D Endoscopic Videos:** While the term "3D" was introduced in the previous point, a clear distinction must be made, as 3D endoscopic systems differ fundamentally from stereo systems due to the fact that 3D endoscopic systems generate volumetric reconstructions of internal organs by integrating high-resolution imaging data (Zhong et al. 2024). To achieve accurate 3D reconstructions, it is worth noting that these systems integrate advanced technologies, such as Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF). Despite their potential, the adoption of 3D endoscopic systems in clinical settings remains limited due to their technical complexity. Consequently, they are predominantly in the research phase, though there is increasing interest within the scientific community, evidenced by an annual growth rate of 77.98% in publications on this topic, number that was obtained by filtering the Web of Science database using the search terms *3D AND (surgical scene) AND reconstruction* over the past three years. Notable contributions in this field include:

- **EndoNeRF:** Employs Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) to reconstruct 3D endoscopic scenes from stereoscopic videos, particularly for deformable tissues (Wang et al. 2022).
- **EndoPerfect:** Combines NeRF with stereoscopic vision to achieve 3D reconstruction in endoscopic sinus surgery (ESS) (Chen et al. 2025).

- **EndoSurf:** Utilizes a signed distance function (SDF) field to enhance surface representation, offering superior reconstruction quality compared to EndoNeRF (fig. 2.6) (Zha et al. 2023).
- **Other methods based on 3D Gaussian Splatting, which are explored in the subsequent section.**

Figure 2.6 3D meshes extracted from EndoNeRF and EndoSurf method (Zha et al. 2023).

Furthermore, these imaging systems can integrate advanced technologies to enhance surgical visualization for specific clinical tasks. For instance, the use of fluorophores can be used to highlight specific tissue structures or pathologies, a feature required for procedures such as the detection of neoplastic lesions, mapping of sentinel lymph nodes, and assessment of blood perfusion in anastomoses (Yang et al. 2021). On the other hand, the use of Narrow-Band Imaging (NBI), which utilizes narrow-band light to enhance the visualization of mucosal surface architecture and microvascular patterns, can be particularly effective in differentiating between benign and malignant lesions. NBI’s key applications include early detection of gastrointestinal cancers, such as colorectal cancer and Barrett’s esophagus, and guiding targeted biopsies (Maeso et al. 2010).

2.2 3D Reconstruction of Surgical Scenes from Endoscopic Videos

2.2.1 3D Representation Methods

Similar to the diverse methods available for 2D representations, 3D representations also employ a variety of approaches, which can be categorized into explicit and implicit methods, each exhibiting unique characteristics (Niu et al. 2024).

Explicit 3D Representation Methods

Explicit 3D representations are those that directly encode the geometry of a scene through discrete elements such as point clouds, voxels, and meshes, providing a structured and precise method for capturing spatial information.

1. **Point Cloud Representation:** Consists of a collection of points within a defined coordinate system, which captures the spatial distribution of an object or scene. It is noteworthy that each point not only contains 3D coordinates but may also incorporate additional attributes, such as reflection intensity or flight time. These attributes are particularly relevant in techniques like Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR), where the distance to a surface is determined by measuring the time elapsed for a laser pulse to return to the sensor. As an explicit 3D representation method, point clouds inherently provide direct 3D depth information of the target scene, preserving complete spatial geometric details. However, they lack the ability to represent the connectivity relationships between points (Niu et al. 2024). To address this limitation, numerous deep learning approaches have been proposed:

- **PointNet:** Consists of a deep neural network architecture that is used for feature extraction from point clouds, capable of performing tasks such as object classification, object part segmentation and semantic scene segmentation (Qi et al. 2017a).
- **PointNet++:** Introduced in the same year as its predecessor, PointNet++ differs in the incorporation of hierarchical feature learning, allowing the model to capture both local and global features by processing point clouds at multiple scales, leading to improved performance (Qi et al. 2017b).
- **RfD-Net:** Known as Reconstruction from Data Network, it is a neural network architecture designed for semantic instance reconstruction in 3D scenes. By processing and understanding point clouds, objects in the scene are identified and geometrically reconstructed, creating detailed point clouds that accurately represent the 3D structure of objects in a scene (fig. 2.7) (Nie et al. 2020).

Figure 2.7 RfD-Net network architecture with an illustrative pipeline of the progression from input point clouds to instance meshes (Nie et al. 2020).

- **Diffusion Models:** Luo et al. explored the application of diffusion models, traditionally used in image generation, to the generation of 3D point clouds, as

this 3D representation method has an unordered and variable nature. Specifically, the method transforms an initial set of random points into a structured 3D point cloud through a reverse diffusion process, progressively refining the shape to match the underlying object geometry (Luo and Hu 2021).

- **Point Cloud Segmentation with Weighted Random Forest:** A segmentation algorithm that combines a Support Vector Machine (SVM) for initial segmentation and a Weighted Random Forest for refinement. It improves segmentation accuracy by assigning weights to decision trees based on their performance, effectively handling noise and outliers in complex 3D scenes (Zhao et al. 2024).

2. **Voxel Representation:** A voxel, or volume pixel, is a data structure that divides 3D space into a grid of cubes, with each cube representing a discrete unit of volume. The state of each voxel is binary, either occupied or empty, which provides a simple and efficient way to represent 3D objects as a grid of voxels (Niu et al. 2024). Key developments in voxel-based methods include:

- **3D ShapeNets:** Proposes a Convolutional Deep Belief Network (CDBN) to represent 3D objects as probabilistic distributions in a voxel grid. The model is capable of performing object recognition tasks and completing 3D shapes from 2.5D depth maps, which are images containing depth information but only from a single perspective (Wu et al. 2015).
- **3D-R2N2:** Based on a recurrent neural network architecture that reconstructs 3D shapes from multiple images without requiring labeled data, making it applicable in diverse scenarios (Choy et al. 2016).
- **ShapeHD:** This method combines depth convolution networks with adversarial learning to enhance the quality of 3D voxel reconstructions from single images (fig. 2.8) (Wu et al. 2018).

Figure 2.8 Comparison of 3D object reconstructions from single-view RGB inputs using different methods: DRC (3D), AtlasNet, and ShapeHD, with ShapeHD showing improved voxel-based rendering quality. (Wu et al. 2018).

Although voxels provide a regular and easy-to-manipulate structure, they suffer from high memory requirements, especially when representing detailed shapes. Optimiza-

tions such as octree structures have been proposed to reduce memory consumption by adaptively subdividing space.

3. **Mesh Representation:** Meshes are composed of vertices, edges, and faces, typically triangles, representing 3D object surfaces. Additionally, mesh-based methods are widely used in computer graphics, 3D modeling, and medical imaging due to their ability to capture detailed surface structures (Niu et al. 2024). Key developments in mesh-based methods include:

- **Pixel2Mesh:** Based on a neural network approach that combines 2D convolutions to extract features from the image and graph convolutional networks (GCNs), thereby generating 3D models in the form of meshes (fig. 2.9) (Wang et al. 2018).

Figure 2.9 Comparison of 3D object reconstructions using Pixel2Mesh with individual components (Unpooling, ResNet, Normal, Laplacian, Edge Length) and the full model, demonstrating the contributions of each component to the final mesh quality. (Wang et al. 2018).

- **Pixel2Mesh++:** Builds upon an enhanced version of its predecessor, utilizing multiview images rather than a single image to produce 3D models with greater accuracy and detail (Wen et al. 2019).

Implicit 3D Representation Methods

Implicit 3D representations encode 3D scenes through continuous functions, enabling the direct generation of explicit scenes during post-rendering without the need for intermediate reconstruction steps. These methods have gained significant popularity due to their capability to efficiently model complex and dynamic scenes while minimizing memory storage requirements (Niu et al. 2024). The following are some of the most common implicit 3D representations:

1. **Occupancy Networks:** Proposes a new approach for representing 3D shapes by using neural networks to predict the spatial occupancy of points within a 3D vol-

ume. This representation is based on an implicit occupancy function, where a neural network evaluates whether a given point in 3D space is inside or outside the volume of the object. The architecture consists of an encoder that processes the input data (e.g., 2D images or 3D point clouds) to produce a feature vector, and a decoder, which maps this feature vector along with 3D coordinates to a binary occupancy value. The object’s surface is defined as the set of points where the occupancy function meets a predefined threshold, facilitating accurate and continuous 3D geometry reconstruction without the need for discrete representations like voxels or meshes (fig. 2.10) (Mescheder et al. 2019).

Figure 2.10 Comparison of 3D shape representations using explicit methods (voxel grids, point clouds, meshes) and implicit representation with occupancy networks.(Mescheder et al. 2019).

2. **Signed Distance Function (SDF):** DeepSDF, unlike occupancy networks, which rely on an occupancy field, it utilizes a signed distance function (SDF). The SDF value at a point x represents the shortest distance to the object’s surface, with the sign indicating whether the point lies inside (negative) or outside (positive) the object. The object’s surface is mathematically defined as the set of points where $SDF(x) = 0$ (Park et al. 2019).
3. **Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF):** Introduced by Mildenhall et al. in 2020, NeRF revolutionized 3D scene representation and rendering by integrating not only 3D geometry but also the visual appearance (color and texture) of a scene derived from 2D images. To achieve this, NeRF employs a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) neural network to map inputs (3D point and viewing direction) to outputs (color and density). Additionally, to render an image from a novel viewpoint, NeRF casts rays from the camera through each pixel, samples points along these rays, and queries the neural network to predict the color and density at each sampled point. These

values are then combined through volumetric rendering to compute the final pixel color. It is worth noting that NeRF is particularly effective in handling complex lighting conditions and viewpoint-dependent effects, although this capability comes at the cost of significant computational expense (Mildenhall et al. 2020).

4. **3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS):** Proposed by Kerbl et al. in 2023, this method utilizes 3D Gaussians—ellipsoids defined by position, covariance matrix (encoding shape, size, and orientation), color, and opacity—as fundamental primitives for scene modeling. Unlike NeRF, the training process does not rely on neural networks but instead follows a structured workflow comprising three key stages: Gaussian initialization, parameter optimization, and adaptive density control. For rendering, the method employs differentiable rasterization to project the 3D Gaussians onto a 2D plane (Kerbl et al. 2023).

2.2.2 Most Relevant 3D Reconstruction Techniques

Having introduced the various approaches for representing scenes in 3D space, the most relevant techniques for 3D reconstruction are now highlighted. These techniques are divided into two main categories: traditional methods based on multiview geometry and deep learning-based methods. It should be noted that reconstruction techniques that rely on specialized hardware systems, such as LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging), for directly capturing 3D scene geometry are excluded from this work, as the focus is placed on monocular imaging.

Traditional 3D Reconstruction Techniques

Traditional methods rely on the principles of multiview geometry to reconstruct 3D scenes from multiple 2D images. These methods typically involve image depth data acquisition, feature extraction, and stereo matching to generate a 3D model (Niu et al. 2024).

1. **Image Depth Data Acquisition:** Depending on the setup, depth data can be obtained through monocular vision, binocular vision, or multiocular vision:
 - **Monocular Vision:** In traditional algorithms, multiple images captured by a single moving camera are required to obtain depth data. By utilizing multiple images from different viewpoints, pixel correspondence and epipolar geometry are employed to infer the 3D structure of a scene. Among the most widely recognized methods for this purpose are Structure-from-Motion (SfM) and Multi-View Stereo (MVS).
 - **Binocular Vision:** By taking advantage of stereo camera disparity, disparity maps are generated, from which depth information is derived. This configuration is designed to mimic human stereoscopic vision, resulting in a more robust

depth estimation compared to monocular systems. The depth calculation is performed using the following equation (LearnOpenCV 2023):

$$z = \frac{f \cdot B}{d} \quad (2.1)$$

Where:

z : the depth of the point in the scene,

f : the focal length of the cameras,

B : the baseline distance between the cameras,

d : the disparity between corresponding points in the stereo images.

As shown in equation 2.1, the calculation of d in binocular vision requires pixel correspondence between the images and the use of epipolar geometry to constrain the search space for matches. On the other hand, although monocular vision also uses pixel correspondence and geometric principles, the results are less accurate due to the need to infer depth information from camera motion, which introduces scale ambiguity and increases sensitivity to correspondence errors.

- **Multicocular Vision:** More than two cameras are utilized to capture the same scene from multiple angles simultaneously. Depth information is obtained by analyzing the disparities across the resulting multitude of images.

In the table 2.1, a comparison of monocular, binocular, and multicocular vision is presented, highlighting their key features, configurations, and applications.

2. **Feature Extraction:** This is a fundamental step as it performs the task of identifying keypoints or regions in images for stereo matching. Various methods have been developed to improve robustness and accuracy:

- **Harris Corner Detection:** Based on detecting corners in images, as these points exhibit significant intensity variations in multiple directions. It is commonly employed for tasks such as image matching, object tracking, and 3D reconstruction. While the algorithm is robust to rotations and variations in lighting, it is sensitive to noise and lacks scale invariance.
- **SIFT (Scale-Invariant Feature Transform):** One of the most widely recognized algorithms in the field of computer vision, SIFT was developed by David Lowe in 1999. It is used to detect and describe local features in images to identify and match keypoints between images even when there are changes

Tabla 2.1 Comparison of Monocular, Binocular, and Multiocular Vision (Niu et al. 2024).

Feature	Monocular Vision	Binocular Vision	Multiocular Vision
Number of Cameras	1 (single camera)	2 (fixed, calibrated cameras)	More than 2 (distributed cameras)
Camera Configuration	Moving to capture multiple views	Fixed and calibrated, captures two perspectives	Fixed, distributed network covering multiple angles
Disparity	Requires camera motion, disparity inferred from sequential frames	Intrinsic, directly computed between two images	Intrinsic, combines disparities across multiple pairs
Scale Ambiguity	Yes, cannot determine absolute depth without additional information	No, absolute scale defined by baseline	No, absolute scale and robust to occlusions
Depth Accuracy	Low, depends on motion and feature matching	High, based on direct disparity computation	Very high, due to fusion of multiple disparities
Common Applications	Large-scale modeling, basic reconstructions	Augmented reality, real-time robotics navigation	Dense modeling, cinematic production

in scale, rotation, lighting, or perspective. The technical details of its operation are explained below (Lowe 1999):

- (a) **Scale-Space Extrema Detection:** The SIFT algorithm begins by detecting keypoints in the image at different scales. This is achieved by creating a scale pyramid, where the image is repeatedly blurred using Gaussian filters of varying intensities (fig. 2.11). The differences between these blurred images are computed to identify regions of interest. Keypoints are then detected as local maxima or minima in this scale-space representation, ensuring they are stable across different scales.
- (b) **Precision in Keypoint Localization:** Once potential keypoints are identified, their precise locations are refined using interpolation techniques. Additionally, unreliable keypoints, such as those with low contrast or located on edges, are filtered out using a curvature test based on the Hessian matrix, improving the robustness of the detected keypoints.
- (c) **Orientation Assignment:** To achieve rotation invariance, each keypoint is assigned a dominant orientation based on the gradient directions in its neighborhood. A histogram of gradient orientations is constructed, and the peak of this histogram determines the keypoint's orientation.
- (d) **Construction of the SIFT Descriptor:** Finally, a descriptor is created for each keypoint by dividing its neighborhood into smaller subregions. Within each subregion, a histogram of gradient orientations is computed,

Figure 2.11 Visual representation of a 5-level scale pyramid. (Wikipedia contributors 2024).

weighted by the gradient magnitude. These histograms are concatenated to form a 128-dimensional descriptor vector, which is then normalized to make it invariant to changes in illumination. This descriptor uniquely represents the keypoint and is used for matching across different images.

- **SURF (Speeded-Up Robust Features):** Developed in 2006 by Herbert Bay, SURF is one of the most popular algorithms in computer vision and is considered a faster alternative to SIFT while maintaining a high level of robustness. Although it shares similar concepts with SIFT, SURF introduces significant improvements in terms of speed and efficiency (Bay, Tuytelaars, and Van Gool 2006).
 - (a) Instead of using Gaussian convolutions like SIFT, SURF employs box filters applied through integral images. This allows for much faster computations, making SURF ideal for real-time applications.
 - (b) Another major difference is the detection of keypoints. While SIFT uses the Difference of Gaussians (DoG), SURF relies on Haar wavelet responses in the horizontal (x) and vertical (y) directions to identify changes in image intensity. These calculations are performed at different scales, enabling the detection of keypoints at multiple resolutions.
 - (c) Regarding orientation assignment, SURF uses a circular window around the interest point to compute wavelet responses. These responses are weighted with a Gaussian window and divided into angular sectors. The dominant orientation is determined by summing the responses in each sector, ensuring that the descriptor is rotation-invariant.
 - (d) Finally, to construct the descriptor, SURF divides a region around the

interest point into a 4×4 grid of subregions. In each subregion, the wavelet responses in the x and y directions, as well as their absolute values, are calculated. These values are combined to form a 64-dimensional descriptor, which is normalized to improve invariance to changes in illumination.

- **ORB (Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF):** It is a feature detection and description algorithm for images, developed by Ethan Rublee et al. in 2011. Its operation is broken down into three parts (Rublee et al. 2011):
 - (a) Detection of keypoints using the FAST detector (Features from Accelerated Segment Test).
 - (b) Assignment of orientation to each keypoint to make it rotation-invariant.
 - (c) Generation of binary descriptors using an improved version of BRIEF (Binary Robust Independent Elementary Features).

ORB is presented as an efficient alternative to algorithms such as SIFT and SURF, as it offers similar performance but with much lower computational cost, making it suitable for real-time applications.

In the tables 2.2 and 2.3, a comparison of the performance of the three most recognized feature extraction and matching techniques, SIFT, SURF, and ORB, can be observed by comparing the original image with scaling and shearing deformations. As shown in the tables, ORB, being the most recent algorithm, demonstrates significantly lower computational costs compared to SIFT. However, while SIFT exhibits a lower match rate for the scaled image, it achieves the highest match rate for the sheared image. This indicates that, despite being the oldest algorithm, SIFT remains a viable option, and the choice of algorithm should be guided by the specific requirements of the application.

Tabla 2.2 Results of feature matching between an image and its scaled version using SIFT, SURF, and ORB (Karami, Prasad, and Shehata 2017).

Method	Time (sec)	Kpnts1	Kpnts2	Match rate (%)
SIFT	0.25	248	1210	31.8
SURF	0.08	162	581	36.6
ORB	0.02	261	471	49.5

Tabla 2.3 Results of feature matching between an image and its sheared version using SIFT, SURF, and ORB (Karami, Prasad, and Shehata 2017).

Method	Time (sec)	Kpnts1	Kpnts2	Match rate (%)
SIFT	0.133	248	229	62.89
SURF	0.049	162	214	59.04
ORB	0.026	261	298	51.88

3. **Stereo Matching:** Involves establishing correspondences between keypoints in multiple images to calculate depth from disparities. At present, the commonly used stereo matching methods include:

- **Gray-Based Stereo Matching Method:** Based on comparing pixel intensities (grayscale) in the images to find correspondences and estimate the depth of the scene. Despite being easy to implement and computationally efficient, it only works well in scenes with rich textures and intensity variations, making it a poor choice for images with noise or uniform texture.
- **Feature-Based Stereo Matching Method:** Focuses on using distinctive features of the images to find correspondences between them. It involves using the feature extraction algorithms presented earlier to detect keypoints. Once detected, the features are matched between the two images to calculate the disparity and, ultimately, the depth of the scene. For matching, each detected keypoint has a descriptor that encodes local information around the point, which is used for comparison. Techniques for comparing descriptors include k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) to find the most similar descriptors, a ratio test to filter ambiguous or incorrect matches, and RANSAC (Random Sample Consensus) to remove outliers and estimate a robust geometric model.
- **Deep learning-based stereo matching algorithm:** Although belonging to the section on "Traditional 3D Reconstruction Techniques", stereo matching can also be performed using deep learning. This is the case with GA-Net (Guided Aggregation Net for End-to-End Stereo Matching), which introduces a novel architecture combining guided aggregation and deep learning to improve the accuracy and efficiency of stereo matching (Zhang et al. 2019).

An example of work that integrates these three steps is "Incremental SfM 3D reconstruction based on monocular images" (Yin and Yu 2020). This approach introduces an enhanced method for incremental 3D reconstruction using monocular images and Structure-from-Motion (SfM). It incorporates a filtering algorithm based on local image correlation to remove incorrect matches and combines features from SIFT and ORB to improve point correspondence (fig. 2.12). Additionally, it employs bundle adjustment techniques and dense reconstruction with optimized optical flow, resulting in a significant reduction in reconstruction time and reprojection errors while maintaining high visual quality.

Deep Learning-Based 3D Reconstruction Techniques

Deep learning has significantly transformed the field of 3D reconstruction, offering a distinct advantage over traditional techniques discussed earlier. These approaches utilize

Figure 2.12 Point correspondence visualization using a combination of SIFT and ORB keypoint detectors (Yin and Yu 2020).

neural networks and prior knowledge to streamline the reconstruction process, eliminating the reliance on complex mathematical formulations and precise camera calibration. Key advancements in this domain are outlined below:

1. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in Multi-View Stereo (MVS):

Several notable works employ CNNs for 3D reconstruction from multiple views. Among these, the following stand out:

- (a) **MVSNet:** A pioneering work proposed by Yao Yao et al. in 2018, which uses an end-to-end deep learning approach to infer depth maps from multiview images, overcoming the limitations of traditional MVS methods (Yao et al. 2018). Below are the stages of the MVSNet workflow:
 - **Feature Extraction:** An 8-layer 2D CNN is used to extract deep features from the input images, which are downsampled to 1/4 of the original resolution without losing important contextual information.
 - **Cost Volume Construction:** Using a differentiable homographic transformation, 2D features are transformed into a 3D cost volume. To handle multiple views, a variance-based cost metric is proposed, combining features from all source images into a single cost volume.
 - **Cost Volume Regularization:** The cost volume is regularized using a 3D CNN with a U-Net-like structure to remove noise and refine the depth estimation.
 - **Depth Map Estimation and Refinement:** An initial depth map is computed using a soft argmin operation over the regularized cost volume.

The depth map is refined using a residual learning network that combines the reference image and the initial depth map to enhance edges and details.

- (b) **Point-MVSNet:** Inspired by MVSNet, though its difference lies in its representation of the 3D scene and its depth inference approach. While MVSNet uses 3D cost volumes and is less memory-efficient, Point-MVSNet operates directly on point clouds, avoiding volumetric representation and significantly reducing memory usage. Additionally, Point-MVSNet follows an iterative (coarse-to-fine) approach to refine depth, enabling more precise and detailed reconstruction, especially in complex regions (fig. 2.13) (Chen et al. 2019).

Figure 2.13 PointMVSNet pipeline: Progressive 3D reconstruction from coarse to refined predictions, resulting in a high-fidelity final prediction (Chen et al. 2019).

- (c) **MVSNet++:** Proposed to address some limitations of MVSNet, such as the lack of spatial information in depth estimation and the need for additional post-processing to generate smooth 3D models. To achieve this, it introduces a depth-based attention pyramid that fuses information at multiple scales, improving the localization of 3D points. Furthermore, it incorporates instance normalization to generate more consistent depth maps without increasing model complexity and uses a curriculum learning approach with specific loss functions to guide training progressively (Chen et al. 2020).

2. **NeRF:** This section is distinguished from the previous one due to its significant relevance in the field, as discussed in the section on implicit 3D representation methods, of incorporating the visual appearance of a scene derived from 2D images. Since its introduction, there have been many works aiming to improve the original paper, with 353 studies indexed in Web of Science in 2024 under the filter *Neural Radiance Fields*, addressing various limitations and seeking practical applications of this proposal. Below are some notable examples:

- **Deblur-NeRF:** Addresses the challenge of NeRF with blurry images by introducing a Deformable Sparse Kernel (DSK) module, which models spatially

varying blur kernels by deforming a canonical kernel (Ma et al. 2022). With this approach, it jointly optimizes NeRF and DSK to restore a sharp scene, being the first method to handle blur in NeRF inputs (fig. 2.14).

Figure 2.14 Comparison of blurry source views and generated novel views using NeRF and Deblur-NeRF. (a) Input images exhibiting camera motion blur and defocus blur. (b) Novel views synthesized by NeRF, retaining blurriness. (c) Novel views generated by Deblur-NeRF, demonstrating effective deblurring and enhanced sharpness (Ma et al. 2022).

- **Point-NeRF:** Combines point clouds generated by MVS (Multi-View Stereo) with NeRF to improve the efficiency and accuracy of scene reconstruction by leveraging explicit geometric information from point clouds to optimize the implicit representation of NeRF (Xu et al. 2023).
- **AligNeRF:** Improves the reconstruction of high-frequency details in 3D scenes with minimal computational cost by introducing a feature alignment and perceptual loss-based approach to correct camera calibration errors and subtle scene movements. Additionally, by combining an MLP with convolutional layers, AligNeRF achieves a more accurate representation of fine textures and edges while maintaining the efficiency and scalability of the original NeRF. It is particularly useful in scenes with alignment errors or unmodeled movements, improving visual quality without significantly increasing rendering time (Jiang et al. 2022).
- **FastNeRF:** Proposes an approach 3000 times faster than the original NeRF in terms of rendering time by introducing scene factorization into two MLPs and efficient caching, maintaining visual quality (Garbin et al. 2021).

3. **3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS):** Despite not using convolutional neural networks (CNNs), 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS) distinguishes itself from traditional methods by adopting a data-driven approach to encode three-dimensional scenes using Gaussian primitives. This approach allows scenes to be optimized holistically,

without relying on rigid workflows such as camera calibration or surface triangulation. Such flexibility allows 3DGS to effectively handle challenging scenarios, including sparse data and complex lighting conditions, making it more aligned with the adaptive and robust characteristics of deep learning techniques. The technical workflow of 3DGS is outlined below (Kerbl et al. 2023):

- (a) **Scene Capture and Camera Calibration:** A static scene is captured through images, and a sparse point cloud is generated using the Structure from Motion (SfM) algorithm.
- (b) **Scene Representation with 3D Gaussians:** Each point in the initial point cloud is replaced by a 3D Gaussian, defined by a position (mean) μ , a covariance matrix Σ , and an opacity α . These Gaussians are used to represent volumes in space due to their differentiability and ability to support continuous optimization.
- (c) **Projection of 3D Gaussians to 2D:** The 3D Gaussians are projected into 2D for subsequent rendering. This projection is performed in camera space using a view transformation W to obtain the projected covariance Σ' :

$$\Sigma' = JW\Sigma W^T J^T \quad (2.2)$$

where J is the Jacobian of the projective transformation.

- (d) **Optimization of 3D Gaussian Parameters:** Parameters such as position μ , opacity α , covariance Σ , and spherical harmonic (SH) coefficients for color are optimized using stochastic gradient descent (SGD). A combined loss function is employed to guide the optimization, which includes \mathcal{L}_1 to account for local details and D-SSIM (Differentiated Structural Similarity Index) to measure the similarity between two images in terms of luminance, contrast, and structure, preserving global structure and image features:

$$\mathcal{L} = (1 - \lambda)\mathcal{L}_1 + \lambda\mathcal{L}_{\text{D-SSIM}} \quad (2.3)$$

where $\lambda = 0.2$.

- (e) **Adaptive Density Control of 3D Gaussians:** The density of 3D Gaussians is increased in under-represented areas by cloning 3D Gaussians in those regions. The cloned Gaussians are moved in the direction of the position gradient to better cover the geometry. Additionally, for large Gaussians with high variability, they are split into smaller Gaussians, distributing their scale and position to better represent geometric variability.
- (f) **Rendering with Tile-Based Rasterization:** The screen is divided into

Figure 2.15 Schematic of adaptive density control for 3D Gaussians (Kerbl et al. 2023).

16×16 tiles, and 3D Gaussians outside the view frustum are culled (discarded). The remaining Gaussians are sorted by depth and assigned to the corresponding tile based on their screen position. Finally, blending α is applied to combine the color and opacity contributions of each Gaussian in depth order.

- (g) **Continuous Optimization and Density Control:** An iterative optimization process allows the parameters of the 3D Gaussians to converge toward values that minimize the loss function. Dynamic adaptive density control is used to adjust the density of 3D Gaussians according to the geometric needs of the scene. Notably, the method supports anisotropic splatting, which adjusts the covariance matrices Σ of the Gaussians to represent complex, non-symmetric shapes. Additionally, spherical harmonics are used to encode lighting and color information based on the viewing direction, rather than fixed RGB values, due to their storage efficiency, smooth interpolation, and ability to model light reflections and refractions on curved surfaces.

Figure 2.16 Pipeline for image generation using Gaussian Splatting (Kerbl et al. 2023).

Despite being a relatively recent technology, with its development occurring just last year (2023), 144 papers related to 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS) have already been published in 2024, as indexed in WebOfScience using the filter (*Gaussian Splatting*) AND 3D. This demonstrates the research community's strong interest

and underscores the potential of 3DGS as a powerful and impactful technology. Below are some notable works that build upon 3DGS:

- **DrivingGaussian:** Extends 3DGS to the domain of dynamic urban scene reconstruction, particularly focused on autonomous driving applications (Zhou et al. 2024b). To address the challenges of urban scenes with dynamic objects, geometric complexity, and lighting changes, DrivingGaussian decomposes the scene into static background and dynamic objects, reconstructing each part separately. The static background is modeled incrementally and progressively using sequential bins, while dynamic objects are handled through a graph that allows individual reconstruction of each moving object and restores their precise positions and occlusion relationships within the scene. Additionally, it incorporates a LiDAR prior to obtain more detailed reconstructions and maintain panoramic consistency across multiple cameras, significantly outperforming other methods in dynamic driving scene reconstruction.
- **DepthSplat:** Its extension is based on connecting 3DGS with monocular and multiview depth estimation, introducing two main innovations: a monocular depth branch leveraging pre-trained features and a multiview branch for feature matching (Xu et al. 2024). Unlike the original 3DGS, DepthSplat integrates these two branches to obtain more robust depth maps, especially in challenging regions such as occlusions and reflective surfaces.
- **LightGaussian:** Focuses on compression and performance optimization, introducing three main innovations: Gaussian Pruning & Recovery, SH Distillation, and Vector Quantization (Fan et al. 2024). Unlike the original 3DGS, LightGaussian identifies and removes Gaussians with the least global significance for scene reconstruction, reducing redundancy while preserving visual quality. The method calculates the significance of each Gaussian based on its contribution to training pixels, its opacity, and its volume, and then applies a recovery stage to maintain quality. Additionally, it uses knowledge distillation to compress spherical harmonic coefficients and vector quantization to further reduce model size. As a result, LightGaussian achieves a 15x compression (reducing storage from 782MB to 45MB) while increasing performance from 144 to 237 FPS, maintaining visual quality comparable to the original 3DGS.
- **4D Gaussian Splatting (4DGS):** Designed for dynamic scenes, it introduces two main innovations: a spatio-temporal structure encoder based on HexPlane and a Gaussian deformation decoder (fig. 2.17) (Wu et al. 2024). Unlike the original 3DGS, which is limited to static scenes, 4D-GS maintains a single set of canonical 3D Gaussians that are deformed for each time instant using a Gaussian deformation field. The spatio-temporal encoder connects nearby

3D Gaussians to predict more accurate motions using decomposed 4D neural planes, while the lightweight decoder predicts the position, rotation, and scale deformation of each Gaussian. As a result, 4D-GS achieves real-time rendering (82 FPS at 800×800 resolution on an RTX 3090) while maintaining high visual quality and storage efficiency (18MB), significantly outperforming other methods in dynamic scene reconstruction. The method also enables object tracking and editing in 4D scenes due to its explicit representation, although it has limitations with very large motions or dramatic scene changes.

Figure 2.17 Architecture of 4D Gaussian Splatting (4DGS): The framework integrates spatial-temporal encoding of 3D Gaussians G with timestamps t , utilizing a Multi-Head Gaussian Deformation Decoder to predict position (Δx , Δy , Δz), rotation (Δr), and scaling (Δs) deformations. The deformed Gaussians G' are then rendered through splatting for dynamic scene representation (Wu et al. 2024).

The following table (table 2.4) provides a comparison between NeRF and 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS). CNNs in Multi-View Stereo are excluded from this comparison as they do not incorporate the concept of visual appearance, which is essential for the scope of this work.

3D Gaussian Splatting approach is selected for its significant advantages in the domain of dynamic surgical scenes. 3DGS enables real-time rendering, a critical requirement during surgical procedures, while also requiring substantially less training time compared to NeRF. Furthermore, 3DGS effectively addresses occlusions caused by surgical instruments through advanced depth initialization strategies and mask-guided training techniques.

2.2.3 3D Gaussian Splatting in Surgical Scenes

Despite being a relatively recent innovation, 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS) has already seen significant advancements proposed by the research community, with 144 papers published in 2024, as previously mentioned, exploring a wide range of improvements and

Tabla 2.4 Comparison between NeRF and 3D Gaussian Splatting (Zhou et al. 2024a).

Aspect	NeRF	3D Gaussian Splatting
Input	2D images + camera parameters (position and orientation).	3D point cloud generated from 2D images and SFM.
Output	Rendered images using volume rendering.	Rendered images using Gaussian projection (splatting).
Rendering	Volume rendering (integration of density and color along the ray).	Projection of 3D Gaussians into 2D (α -blending).
Optimization	Gradient descent to minimize reconstruction loss.	Gradient descent to adjust Gaussian parameters.
Training time	Slow (hours or days for complex scenes).	Fast (minutes for simple scenes).
Real-time rendering	No (depends on scene complexity).	Yes (up to 200 FPS on modern hardware).
Visual quality	High quality, especially in fine details and lighting effects.	Good quality, but may lose details in complex textures.
Applications	Virtual reality, cinema, gaming, high-precision 3D reconstruction.	Scientific visualization, fast reconstruction, real-time applications.
Limitations	Requires long training times. Not suitable for real-time rendering. Depends on the quality of input images.	Lower quality in fine details and complex textures. Depends on the quality of the initial point cloud. Less suitable for complex lighting effects.

applications of the technology. Among these, the use of 3DGS for 3D reconstruction of surgical scenes has emerged. Although this application represents a highly specialized niche, several works have already begun to focus on this area:

1. **EndoGSLAM:** Introduces three main innovations: a simplified representation of 3D Gaussians (replacing SH coefficients with a simple color attribute and using uniform scaling), a pre-filter to handle localized lighting characteristic of endoscopy, and a partial refinement strategy based on keyframes. Unlike the original 3DGS, EndoGSLAM reduces the number of parameters to optimize by 86% (from 59 to 8 parameters per Gaussian), enabling real-time processing of endoscopic sequences. The method iteratively expands 3D Gaussians into previously unobserved regions and partially refines the reconstructed surgical field, achieving rendering at over 100 FPS while maintaining high visual quality and camera tracking accuracy. As a result, EndoGSLAM achieves a better balance between intraoperative availability and reconstruction quality than traditional or neural SLAM approaches, being capable of processing RGB-D streams at 3 FPS in its high-quality version or in real-time in its speed-optimized version. It is noteworthy that it does not handle tissue deformations (Wang et al. 2024).

2. **Free-SurGS:** Eliminates the dependency on Structure-from-Motion (SfM), introducing two main innovations: an optical flow-based pose estimation system and a consistency verification for rigid and reliable points. Unlike the original 3DGS, which requires precise camera poses and SfM point clouds, Free-SurGS jointly optimizes camera poses and scene representation using optical flow as a guide for Gaussian projection. The method compensates for the limitations of traditional photometric loss (especially problematic in surgical scenes due to minimal textures and photometric inconsistencies) through an optical flow loss term that aligns the projection flow derived from 3D Gaussians with robust optical flow. As a result, Free-SurGS achieves more accurate and faster reconstruction (1 hour of training vs. 5-50 hours of previous methods) while maintaining real-time rendering (60 FPS), significantly outperforming other methods in novel view synthesis and pose estimation in surgical scenes. However, it does not handle tissue deformations (Guo et al. 2024).

3. **EndoGaussian:** Designed for the reconstruction of endoscopic surgical scenes with tissue deformation. EndoGaussian introduces two main innovations: Holistic Gaussian Initialization (HGI) and Spatio-temporal Gaussian Tracking (SGT) (fig. 2.18). HGI uses depth estimation models to densely initialize 3D Gaussians, while SGT employs a deformation field composed of encoding voxels and a lightweight deformation decoder to model tissue dynamics. The method achieves superior reconstruction quality (PSNR of 37.849) with only 2 minutes of training using the EndoNeRF dataset, achieving real-time rendering at 195 FPS (100 times faster than previous methods). EndoGaussian works with both binocular and monocular inputs and significantly outperforms previous methods such as EndoNeRF, EndoSurf, and Ler-Plane, making it suitable for intraoperative applications (Liu et al. 2024).
**Note: PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio) quantifies the quality of image or video reconstruction by measuring the ratio between the maximum possible power of a signal and the power of corrupting noise. Higher PSNR values indicate better reconstruction quality, representing lower levels of distortion and noise in the output.*

4. **EndoGS:** Also designed for the reconstruction of deformable endoscopic tissues. Its innovations lie in a dynamic representation based on deformation fields, a depth-guided supervision strategy with spatio-temporal masks, and surface-aligned regularization terms. Unlike the original 3DGS, EndoGS uses a lightweight MLP along with HexPlane planes to predict the deformation of 3D Gaussians over time, while handling instrument occlusions with binary masks and spatio-temporal importance maps. The method incorporates spatial and temporal total variation losses to prevent color drift in unseen areas and surface alignment regularization to improve geometry in occluded regions. As a result, EndoGS achieves high-quality reconstruction (PSNR of 37.935) with real-time rendering (70 FPS), significantly outper-

Figure 2.18 Illustration of the proposed EndoGaussian framework, including a) Holistic Gaussian Initialization, b) Spatio-temporal Gaussian Tracking, and c) Optimization. (Liu et al. 2024).

forming previous methods such as EndoNeRF and ForPlane in both visual quality and rendering speed (Zhu et al. 2024).

5. **SurgicalGaussian:** Introduces three main innovations: a Gaussian initialization strategy based on depth maps (GIDM), an MLP-based deformation field to model tissue movement, and specific regularizations to handle occlusions and deformations. Unlike the original 3DGS, SurgicalGaussian uses depth maps and instrument masks to initialize 3D Gaussians instead of relying on Structure-from-Motion (SfM), enabling better reconstruction in areas occluded by surgical instruments. The method employs an MLP network to predict Gaussian deformations, along with deformation consistency and color smoothing regularizations to manage occlusions and complex movements. As a result, SurgicalGaussian achieves high-fidelity reconstruction (PSNR of 38.783) with real-time rendering (≥ 80 FPS) while consuming less than 4GB of GPU memory, significantly outperforming other methods in the reconstruction of dynamic surgical scenes (Xie et al. 2024).
6. **Deform3DGS:** A novel framework for fast 3D reconstruction, which introduces two key innovations: Motion-Aware Point Fusion (MAPF) for dense point cloud initialization and Flexible Deformation Modeling (FDM) using learnable Gaussian basis functions for efficient tissue deformation representation. The framework achieves state-of-the-art performance with remarkable metrics: 338.8 FPS rendering speed, PSNR of 37.90, and requires only 1 minute of training time per scene, making it $2\times$ faster than EndoGaussian in both training and rendering, and $10\times$ faster than LerPlane. FDM’s efficiency comes from its use of learnable Gaussian basis functions that model deformations through efficient linear combinations, while MAPF improves reconstruction stability by selectively fusing points with intensive motions

(Yang et al. 2024b).

In Table 2.5, a comparative analysis of the discussed methods is presented, with two methods standing out: **SurgicalGaussian** and **Deform3DGS**. SurgicalGaussian stands out due to its PSNR value, which is the highest among all methods, while Deform3DGS is distinguished by its extremely fast rendering speed. However, it is important to note that the PSNR value reported for Deform3DGS does not correspond to the same scene used in SurgicalGaussian. Despite this difference, the PSNR value remains high, ensuring that visual details are preserved. Nevertheless, the primary reason Deform3DGS is the preferred method is its remarkable 1-minute training time per scene, making it suitable for real-time intraoperative applications—a critical requirement for turning this possibility into reality. Additionally, it is worth noting that in the "Methodology" section, a numerical comparison between SurgicalGaussian and Deform3DGS, the two top-performing methods, will be conducted under the same conditions to ensure an objective evaluation.

Tabla 2.5 Comparison of Gaussian Splatting-Based Methods for Surgical Scenes.

Method	Main Innovations	Deform.	FPS ¹	PSNR ²
EndoGSLAM	Simplified Gaussian representation Pre-filter for lighting Partial refinement using keyframes	No	≥ 100	Not applicable
Free-SurGS	Pose estimation via optical flow Consistency verification	No	60	Not applicable
EndoGaussian	Holistic Gaussian Initialization Spatio-temporal Gaussian Tracking	Yes	195	37.849
EndoGS	Deformation fields Depth-guided supervision Aligned regularization	Yes	70	37.935
SurgicalGaussian	Depth-based initialization MLP deformation field Specific regularizations	Yes	≥ 80	38.783
Deform3DGS	Motion-Aware Point Fusion (MAPF) Flexible Deformation Modeling (FDM) Learnable Gaussian basis functions	Yes	338.8	37.90 ³

¹FPS: Frames per second (rendering speed)

²PSNR: Evaluated on the EndoNeRF dataset

³PSNR for Deform3DGS was evaluated on a different subset of EndoNeRF scenes

2.2.4 Practical Applications of 3D Gaussian Splatting in Surgical Scenes

3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS), initially introduced as an innovative technique for efficient and high-quality 3D reconstruction in computer graphics and vision, has shown remarkable potential in the field of surgical scene analysis. Its ability to generate highly detailed and adaptive 3D reconstructions has enabled its application across various aspects of surgical practice. These applications capitalize on 3DGS's strengths in modeling deformable structures and enabling real-time processing, addressing critical challenges in surgical workflows. Below are some of the key practical applications of 3DGS in surgical scenes (Stoyanov 2012):

- **Preoperative Planning:** 3DGS can generate patient-specific 3D anatomical models from endoscopic video data, allowing surgeons to visualize complex anatomies and plan surgical strategies in detail. In Minimally Invasive Surgeries (MIS), where access is limited, these accurate 3D reconstructions help identify critical structures such as blood vessels or tumors. By integrating these models with virtual simulation tools, surgeons can rehearse procedures, evaluate different approaches, and reduce intraoperative uncertainties, ultimately improving surgical outcomes.
- **Intraoperative Navigation and Guidance:** The real-time 3D reconstruction capability of Gaussian Splatting makes it an invaluable tool for intraoperative navigation. During laparoscopic or robotic-assisted surgeries, 3DGS can process monocular video feeds from endoscopes to create 3D maps of the surgical field. These maps enhance spatial awareness by providing depth information and tracking the positions of surgical instruments and tissues. For example, integrating these maps with augmented reality (AR) overlays allows surgeons to visualize hidden structures or avoid critical areas, enhancing precision and safety during procedures.
- **Tool-Tissue Interaction Analysis:** 3DGS is highly effective in tracking and analyzing interactions between surgical instruments and deformable tissues. By generating real-time 3D models of the surgical site, the technique can monitor how tissues respond to tool movements, enabling precise manipulation in delicate procedures. This capability is particularly beneficial in robotic-assisted surgeries, where haptic feedback is limited, as it provides visual cues for assessing tissue deformation and force application.
- **Surgical Training and Education:** 3DGS is transforming surgical training by providing realistic and dynamic 3D representations of surgical environments. Trainees can interact with deformable models that mimic real human anatomy,

practicing complex techniques in a controlled setting (Guerrero-Antolino, Gutiérrez-Sánchez, and Millán-Scheidig 2024). For instance, surgical simulators incorporating 3DGS can simulate scenarios such as suturing or tumor resection, where tissue deformation is critical (fig. 2.19). These tools enhance the learning experience by offering immediate feedback and enabling repetitive practice without the need for cadavers or live patients.

Figure 2.19 Two surgeons interacting through augmented reality (AR) using a 3D holographic model of a heart (DICOM Director 2023).

- **Autonomous Robot Training:** 3DGS plays a crucial role in advancing autonomous robotic systems in surgery by providing highly accurate 3D reconstructions for training algorithms. Autonomous surgical robots require precise spatial and contextual understanding of their environments to perform complex tasks. 3DGS enables the creation of realistic and deformable training datasets, allowing robots to learn tool-tissue interactions, anticipate anatomical variations, and refine their decision-making processes in a simulated environment. Furthermore, real-time integration with robotic platforms can support autonomous execution of predefined surgical tasks, such as suturing or tissue dissection, with minimal human intervention.
- **Postoperative Analysis and Documentation:** 3DGS also finds utility in postoperative applications by generating detailed 3D reconstructions of surgical outcomes. These models can be used to evaluate the success of procedures, compare pre- and postoperative anatomies, and document surgeries for medico-legal purposes. Additionally, they enable researchers to systematically analyze surgical techniques and outcomes, contributing to the optimization of clinical practices and the development of evidence-based surgical protocols.

2.2.5 Current Challenges in 3D Reconstruction of Surgical Scenes

The reconstruction of surgical scenes into accurate and dynamic 3D models remains a critical challenge in medical imaging and computer vision. Despite significant advancements, such as those discussed earlier, several limitations persist, primarily due to the unique and complex nature of surgical environments. These challenges are categorized below to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current research gaps (Zhang, Zhong, and Gu 2018).

- **Handling Deformable and Dynamic Structures:** Surgical scenes often involve soft tissues and organs that undergo significant deformations due to surgical manipulation, respiration, or blood flow. Traditional 3D reconstruction methods, which typically assume rigid or quasi-static environments, struggle to accurately capture these non-linear changes. Developing algorithms capable of modeling both large-scale and fine-grained deformations in real-time, while maintaining computational efficiency, is a critical area of research.
- **Limited Field of View and Occlusions:** Most of the Minimally Invasive Surgeries (MIS) rely on cameras with narrow fields of view, limiting the amount of visible anatomical information. Additionally, frequent occlusions caused by surgical instruments or overlapping tissues disrupt scene continuity, resulting in incomplete or fragmented reconstructions. Advanced algorithms that can infer hidden structures and integrate partial views into cohesive 3D models are essential to address this challenge.
- **Image Quality and Noise:** Surgical imaging is often compromised by variable lighting conditions, specular reflections from wet surfaces, and artifacts such as motion blur or low resolution. These factors degrade input data quality and reduce the reliability of reconstructed models. Robust pre-processing techniques and noise-resilient reconstruction algorithms are necessary to mitigate these issues and improve model accuracy.
- **Real-Time Constraints:** Real-time processing is a critical requirement in Minimally Invasive Surgeries (MIS), where immediate feedback is essential for decision-making. While many state-of-the-art 3D reconstruction techniques offer high accuracy, their computational intensity makes them unsuitable for real-time applications. Striking a balance between reconstruction accuracy and processing speed remains a key focus of ongoing research.
- **Integration with Surgical Tools and Workflow:** For 3D reconstruction to be practically useful, it must seamlessly integrate into the surgical workflow. This

involves accurately tracking tools within a dynamic and deformable environment, which is particularly challenging when instruments occlude key anatomical structures. Additionally, ensuring that reconstructed models are interpretable and actionable for surgeons adds another layer of complexity.

- **Validation and Standardization:** Validating 3D reconstruction methods in surgical scenes is challenging due to the lack of standardized benchmarks and datasets that reflect the complexity of real-world scenarios. While datasets like SCARED and EndoVis provide valuable insights, they often fail to capture the full range of anatomical and procedural variations encountered in clinical practice. Establishing universal standards for evaluating model accuracy and usability remains an unresolved issue (Maier-Hein et al. 2017).
- **Ethical and Privacy Concerns:** The collection and processing of surgical video data raise significant ethical concerns, particularly regarding patient privacy. Anonymizing sensitive data while preserving critical features necessary for reconstruction is a complex task. Furthermore, the lengthy and complicated regulatory approval processes for new healthcare technologies can slow the adoption of innovative approaches (Yang et al. 2017).

Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodological framework employed in this research, detailing the hardware and software components required for the development of Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting for Monocular Endoscopic Video Reconstruction. The chapter begins by specifying the **hardware configuration**, describing the computational resources utilized, including GPU acceleration, memory requirements, and storage considerations. It then introduces the **software development environment**, specifying the programming tools, libraries, and frameworks essential for implementing the proposed approach.

Following this, a structured **video processing pipeline** is presented, covering each stage from raw endoscopic video input to the final 3D reconstruction. At each stage, a comparative study of existing methods is conducted to determine the most suitable approach for the surgical context. The chapter first addresses **video dehazing**, where traditional image processing techniques are evaluated, and the *Dark Channel Prior (DCP)* with *Guided Filter* is ultimately selected for its computational efficiency and robustness in handling surgical haze. Next, **feature detection** is analyzed, comparing various object detection models, leading to the selection of *YOLOv11* due to its balance between accuracy and inference speed in detecting surgical instruments. Similarly, **image segmentation** approaches are studied, and *Segment Anything Model 2 (SAM2)* is chosen based on its superior temporal consistency and segmentation accuracy.

These segmentations are leveraged in **video inpainting**, where different inpainting techniques are assessed, and *Spatial-Temporal Transformer Networks (STTN)* is identified as the most effective model for reconstructing occluded regions while preserving anatomical details. The chapter further examines **depth estimation**, where *Depth Anything V2* is selected after an evaluation of monocular depth estimation models, highlighting its state-of-the-art performance in generalizing across diverse scenes. Additionally, **camera pose estimation** methodologies are compared, and *MonST3R* is adopted for its ability to accurately estimate camera motion in dynamic surgical environments.

Finally, the chapter discusses the implementation of **Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting**, providing a comparative analysis of existing methods, including *SurgicalGaussian* and *Deform3DGS*. The selection of *Deform3DGS* is justified based on its enhanced computational efficiency and improved reconstruction fidelity in deformable surgical environments. The chapter concludes by summarizing the methodological contributions of this research and identifying key challenges in processing monocular endoscopic videos for high-fidelity 3D reconstruction.

3.1 Hardware Configuration

This section details the hardware employed for this work. It should be noted that the hardware requirements are limited to a single portable computer, as the scope of this work focuses on advancing the field of creating an accurate and realistic surgical digital twin, as discussed in the motivation section. Consequently, as this study is conducted within a simulation environment, the only necessary hardware is the laptop described below (Lenovo 2025):

- **Model:** Lenovo Legion Pro 7i Gen 8 laptop (fig. 3.1).
- **Processor (CPU):** Responsible for managing the core computations and ensuring the efficient execution of tasks across multiple threads. This Lenovo model is equipped with a **13th-generation Intel Core i7-13700HX processor**, featuring 16 cores (8 performance cores and 8 efficiency cores) and 24 threads. It operates at a base frequency of 2.1 GHz, with a maximum boost frequency of 5.0 GHz.
- **Graphics Processing Unit (GPU):** Dedicated to performing intensive parallel computations, particularly for tasks related to deep learning, 3D reconstruction, and 3D Gaussian splatting. This laptop is equipped with an **NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4070**, which includes 8 GB of GDDR6 VRAM and is built on NVIDIA's Ada Lovelace architecture.
- **Memory (RAM):** Provides the temporary storage required to handle intermediate data and ensure smooth multitasking. This system includes **32 GB of DDR5 RAM**, clocked at 5600 MHz.
- **Storage:** The system features a **1 TB NVMe SSD**. Non-Volatile Memory Express (NVMe) enables faster data transfer by directly interfacing with the CPU over the PCIe bus, while Solid-State Drive (SSD) technology ensures durability and rapid access to large datasets, significantly reducing loading and read/write times during experiments.

As a reference, approximately **300 MB** of storage is required for textitEndoNeRF Pulling dataset used in this project, including all preprocessing, training, and rendering steps, with the latter two accounting for **150 MB**. For longer monocular endoscopic videos, a larger storage capacity must be considered to accommodate larger intermediate files and outputs.

- **Display:** The laptop features a **16-inch 2560 × 1600 WQXGA screen** with a **refresh rate of 240 Hz** and a **brightness of 500 nits**. While the display does not directly influence computational performance, it allows for detailed visualization of reconstruction outputs and rendered scenes. These outputs are evaluated using quantitative metrics, which will be explained later, as well as through qualitative personal assessments.

Figure 3.1 Top view of the Lenovo Legion Pro 5i Gen 8 laptop (Lenovo 2025).

It is worth noting that, given the computationally intensive nature of the tasks performed in this research, such as training deep learning models, 3D Gaussian splatting operations, and other processes, the system requires a constant power supply. It was observed that a fully charged battery alone was insufficient for extended operations, particularly during prolonged model training or rendering processes. To ensure uninterrupted performance, the laptop was connected to a power source throughout the development of the research.

Furthermore, while the results presented in this work are based on the specifications of the aforementioned laptop, it is important to highlight that any system with superior hardware capabilities is likely to achieve better efficiency and reduced processing times. Specifically, higher-tier GPUs, faster CPUs, and larger memory capacities can significantly improve the performance of Gaussian splatting operations, 3D reconstructions, and machine learning tasks.

Finally, the findings and benchmarks related to computational efficiency reported in this study are intrinsically linked to the capabilities of the Lenovo Legion Pro 7i Gen 8 laptop, as all experiments were conducted exclusively on this system.

3.2 Software Development

This section provides a detailed overview of the software tools and methodologies utilized in the project. It is divided into three main parts: **Development Environment**, **Core Libraries and Frameworks**, and **Models and Algorithms**. Each subsection outlines the specific software components and their roles in the development of *Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting for Monocular Endoscopic Video Reconstruction of Surgical Scenes*. It is worth noting that particular attention is given to the "Models and Algorithms" section, which includes an exhaustive review of existing approaches to guide the selection of the models implemented. The selection criteria were based on the relevance of the models to the surgical context, their performance in terms of accuracy and efficiency, and their compatibility with the overall pipeline.

3.2.1 Development Environment

Programming Language and Environment

Python was selected as the primary programming language for this project due to several key reasons. First, Python offers an extensive ecosystem for machine learning and image processing, which are essential components of this work. Additionally, Python stands as the preferred choice in this domain, as the original 3D Gaussian Splatting repository, along with the research works discussed in the *3D Gaussian Splatting in Surgical Scenes* section, are predominantly implemented using Python. This is further supported by a brief search on GitHub using the keyword *3D Gaussian Splatting*, which reveals that out of 472 available repositories, 197 are developed in Python, followed by C++ with only 44 repositories.

Another significant advantage of Python lies in its environment management capabilities, particularly through Anaconda, which provides an efficient solution for dependency management and version control. **Anaconda**, also used in this project, enables the creation of isolated environments, ensuring compatibility across different libraries and frameworks without conflicts, a crucial feature for complex projects involving multiple dependencies, as is the case in this work, which relies on a wide range of modules that will be presented later.

For code development and implementation, **Visual Studio Code (VS Code)** was chosen as the preferred Integrated Development Environment (IDE). VS Code offers several advantages, including its lightweight design, extensive extension ecosystem, and seam-

less integration with Git for version control. **Git**, a distributed version control system, was used in conjunction with **GitHub**, a web-based platform for hosting and collaborating on repositories, to ensure effective version control and maintain a structured development history.

3.2.2 Core Libraries and Frameworks

CUDA and GPU Acceleration

For the implementation of this work, **CUDA 12.4** was installed, as it provides the necessary infrastructure to utilize the computational power of the GPU for parallel processing tasks. Developed by NVIDIA, CUDA is an essential component for deep learning frameworks such as TensorFlow, which will be discussed later as it is used for training the Deformed 3D Gaussian Splatting model. Additionally, CUDA is widely utilized in many image processing and computer vision libraries to accelerate computationally intensive operations.

The choice of CUDA 12.4 was driven by its compatibility with the NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4070 GPU employed in this work. This GPU features a Compute Capability of 8.9, and CUDA 12.4 is specifically designed to support architectures with Compute Capability 8.x (NVIDIA 2024a).

Libraries and Dependencies

This section outlines the libraries and dependencies used in the project, categorized according to their functionality and purpose. Figure 3.2 provides a visual representation of this distinction, showcasing all the libraries and dependencies along with their respective logos, where available.

Below are the versions and a brief description of each library and dependency shown in Figure 3.2:

1. Deep Learning Frameworks and Machine Learning Libraries:

- **torch**>=2.5.1 – The core deep learning framework for defining, training, and deploying neural networks.
- **torchvision**>=0.20.1 – Provides tools for image transformations and datasets compatible with PyTorch.
- **torchaudio**>=2.5.1 – Handles audio processing tasks, ensuring compatibility with PyTorch models.
- **xformers**>=0.0.28.post3 – Optimizes attention mechanisms for transformer models to improve performance.

Figure 3.2 Functional Categorization of Libraries and Dependencies.

- `pytorch3d==0.7.8` – A specialized library for 3D deep learning operations and rendering.
- `TensorFlow==2.19.0-dev20250109` – A deep learning framework used for comparative analysis.

2. Computer Vision and Image Processing Libraries:

- `opencv-contrib-python>=4.10.0` – A comprehensive library for image processing and computer vision tasks.
- `imageio>=2.36.1` – Used for reading and writing image data in various formats.
- `imageio[ffmpeg]>=0.5.1` – Enables video processing through FFmpeg integration.
- `Pillow (PIL)==11.1.0` – A library for image loading and transformation.
- `pyiqa==0.1.13` – Image quality assessment, evaluating visual quality of processed images.
- `SAM2` – A segmentation model for precise object segmentation.
- `mmcv==1.7.2` – A foundational library for computer vision research, providing utilities for data augmentation, model building, and efficient computation in deep learning.

3. Optimization and Parameter Tuning Libraries:

- `optuna>=4.1.0` – A framework for automated hyperparameter optimization.
- `numba>=0.60.0` – Provides Just-In-Time (JIT) compilation to accelerate numerical computations.
- `scikit-optimize>=0.10.2` – A library for sequential model-based optimization, useful for hyperparameter tuning and black-box function minimization.

4. 3D Reconstruction and Point Cloud Processing Libraries:

- `open3d>=0.18.0` – A library for processing and visualizing 3D point clouds.
- `plyfile>=1.1` – Reads and writes PLY files used for 3D models.
- `trimesh>=4.5.3` – Handles 3D mesh processing and visualization.
- `diff-gaussian-rasterization-w-depth` – Used for Gaussian splatting with depth support.
- `simple-knn` – Performs efficient k-nearest neighbors search for 3D point clouds.

5. Data Analysis and Visualization Libraries:

- `numpy=1.24.3` – A core numerical library for handling large-scale data arrays and matrices.
- `pandas>=1.3.0` – A library for data manipulation and analysis, particularly for structured data.
- `matplotlib.pyplot>=3.9.3` – A widely-used library for creating static, animated, and interactive visualizations.
- `seaborn>=0.13.2` – Statistical data visualization built on top of Matplotlib for enhanced graphics.

6. System Utilities and Performance Monitoring:

- `cmake>=3.27.0` – A cross-platform build system required for compiling various dependencies.
- `ninja>=1.11.1` – A build system that ensures fast compilation of software dependencies.
- `vizer>=0.2.7` – A visualization tool for tracking model performance and intermediate results.
- `pynvml>=12.0.0` – NVIDIA’s monitoring library used to track GPU utilization and memory consumption.

7. Model-Specific Dependencies:

- `ultralytics>=8.3.48` – A package used for running the YOLO object detection models.
- `roma>=1.5.1` – Provides utilities for camera pose estimation and transformations.
- `safetensors>=0.4.5` – A secure serialization format for storing model weights efficiently.
- `tinycudann==1.7` – A CUDA-accelerated library for neural networks requiring fast inference speeds.

3.2.3 Models and Algorithms

In this section, the various components that constitute the pipeline for the development of Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting are presented. For greater clarity, the components have been categorized based on their functionalities, with each subsection explaining the justification for selecting the respective models or algorithms.

It is important to highlight that none of the works discussed in the previous “3D Gaussian Splatting in Surgical Scenes” section address the preprocessing of data prior to the

creation of 3D Gaussian Splatting; instead, they rely exclusively on pre-existing datasets. For this reason, this section presents the extensive research efforts undertaken, along with the adaptations that will be detailed later in the "System Development" section, to process any monocular endoscopic video, ensuring its suitability for Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting with optimal results and efficiency and thereby achieving the primary objective of this work.

Figure 3.3 illustrates the proposed pipeline for monocular endoscopic video reconstruction, highlighting the methods used at each stage of the process. Below, we describe these processes, including their functionality and the reasoning behind their selection. It is important to note the presence of a process labeled *InDeform3DGS*, while the original method is *Deform3DGS*. This distinction arises because *InDeform3DGS* represents the modified process developed in this work, which is detailed in the *System Development* section.

Figure 3.3 Overview of the proposed pipeline for monocular endoscopic video reconstruction using Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting. Each processing step is labeled with the corresponding method used, including YOLOv11 for feature detection, SAM2 for image segmentation, DepthAnythingV2 for depth estimation, and STTN for video inpainting. Additional steps such as video dehazing with DCP + GF and the final 3D reconstruction with InDeform3DGS are also highlighted.

Video Dehaze

The first component to analyze is **video dehazing**, which involves removing haze or fog to restore the original details of the image. To achieve this, a review of the literature revealed two potential approaches for dehazing monocular endoscopic videos of surgical scenes: one based on traditional computer vision techniques and another based on deep learning.

The deep learning-based approach was ultimately discarded, despite its robustness and impressive results, such as those demonstrated in the work "Vision Transformers for Single Image Dehazing", which was the first method to exceed 40 dB PSNR on the SOTS indoor dataset (Song et al. 2023). This decision was driven by the fact that deep learning approaches require extensive training data, and currently, there is no suitable dataset available for training dehazing models specifically for surgical environments. Consequently, a traditional computer vision-based approach was adopted. Specifically, the method proposed by He et al. in "Single Image Haze Removal Using Dark Channel Prior" was selected. This approach introduces a novel technique for haze removal based on a statistical heuristic derived from haze-free natural images. It estimates atmospheric transmission and recovers clearer, higher-contrast images without relying on additional depth information. The proposed method operates as follows (He, Sun, and Tang 2009):

1. **Hazy Image Formation Model:** The formation of a hazy image is modeled using the following equation:

$$I(x) = J(x)t(x) + A(1 - t(x)) \quad (3.1)$$

Where:

- $I(x)$: Input hazy image.
- $J(x)$: Haze-free image to be recovered.
- A : Atmospheric light, representing the contribution of haze to the image.
- $t(x)$: Transmission map indicating the proportion of unscattered light reaching the camera.

2. **Dark Channel Prior (DCP) Calculation:** The dark channel is based on the observation that, in haze-free images, at least one color channel has very low intensity values in most regions (except for the sky, which lacks dark pixels) due to the presence of shadows, colorful objects, and naturally dark materials.

In hazy images, scattered light increases these dark values, allowing the estimation of haze density. In surgical endoscopic videos during electrocautery, the generated vapor scatters light uniformly, raising the intensity of color channels. This causes dark pixels to become brighter, enabling the use of the dark channel to detect areas most affected by surgical haze.

To achieve this, a local window-based approach is used to estimate haze in a spatially adaptive manner:

$$J_{\text{dark}}(x) = \min_{c \in \{r, g, b\}} \left(\min_{y \in \Omega(x)} J^c(y) \right) \quad (3.2)$$

Where:

- $J^c(y)$: Intensity value of the color channel c (red, green, or blue) at pixel y .
- $\Omega(x)$: Local window centered at pixel x .

3. Atmospheric Light A Estimation: The atmospheric light A represents the contribution of haze to the captured image, acting as a source of scattered light that increases pixel intensity values across the scene. In the case of vapor generated by electrocautery in endoscopic videos, light scattering is relatively homogeneous, allowing A to be estimated by selecting the brightest pixels in the scene.

These pixels, typically found in regions with the highest vapor density, contain the most "airlight" (light scattered by haze), providing a reliable reference for estimating A . This estimation is performed by identifying the top 0.1% of the brightest pixels in the dark channel and extracting their values from the original hazy image:

$$A = \max_{y \in \text{top pixels}} I(y) \quad (3.3)$$

Where:

- $I(y)$: Intensity of the selected pixels in the hazy image.
- A : Estimated scattered light in the scene.

4. Transmission Map $t(x)$ Estimation: The transmission map $t(x)$ describes the proportion of light that reaches the camera without being scattered. To estimate the transmission, the input image is normalized using the atmospheric light A , and the dark channel is computed over the normalized image. The equation for estimating the transmission is:

$$t(x) = 1 - \omega \min_{c \in \{r, g, b\}} \left(\min_{y \in \Omega(x)} \frac{I^c(y)}{A^c} \right) \quad (3.4)$$

Where:

- $I^c(y)$: Intensity of the hazy image in channel c .
- A^c : Estimated atmospheric light in channel c .
- $\Omega(x)$: Local window centered at x .
- ω : Adjustment parameter (typically $\omega \approx 0.95$), which retains a small amount of haze to enhance depth perception.

Low values of $t(x)$ indicate areas with high haze density, while high values correspond to regions with little haze. This is due to the equation, where higher dark channel

values result in lower estimated transmission, suggesting greater atmospheric light scattering and thus less transmission.

5. Transmission Map Refinement Using Soft Matting:

The initial transmission map may contain artifacts and discontinuities due to local window-based estimation. To improve its accuracy and smoothness, a refinement step is applied using the *Soft Matting* technique, which preserves the edges of surgical tools and anatomical structures while smoothing gradual variations in transmission.

$$E(t) = t^T L t + \lambda(t - \tilde{t})^T (t - \tilde{t}) \quad (3.5)$$

Where:

- L : Laplacian matrix for smoothing the transmission.
- λ : Regularization parameter controlling the smoothness of the result.

6. **Haze-Free Image Recovery:** Finally, the haze-free image $J(x)$ is recovered by removing the contribution of atmospheric light and applying the refined transmission map. The recovery equation is:

$$J(x) = \frac{I(x) - A}{\max(t(x), t_0)} + A \quad (3.6)$$

Where:

- t_0 : Minimum threshold value to avoid division by zero.

In the case of surgical vapor, this process restores scene visibility, highlighting anatomical structures previously obscured by haze generated during electrocautery, resulting in a clearer and higher-contrast image.

Algorithm 1 presents a condensed pseudocode for the haze removal process using the Dark Channel Prior (DCP), designed to enhance clarity and readability.

Additionally, through research into traditional computer vision approaches, another work of He et al. was identified, which introduces the **Guided Filter** as a replacement for the Soft Matting process in refining the transmission map. The Guided Filter improves computational efficiency by operating in $O(N)$ time, whereas Soft Matting requires solving high-dimensional linear systems with a complexity greater than $O(N^2)$. It is worth noting that while the Guided Filter is not as precise as Soft Matting in handling highly complex edge transitions, it provides sufficient quality for most haze removal applications.

The Guided Filter assumes a local linear model, where the refined transmission value $t(x)$ is modeled as a linear function of the guide image $I(x)$ within a local window ω_k (He, Sun, and Tang 2013):

Algorithm 1 Haze Removal using Dark Channel Prior (DCP)

Require: Hazy input image I

Ensure: Dehazed image J

Dark Channel Prior (DCP) Calculation

- 1: **for each** window $\Omega(x)$ **in** I **do**
- 2: Compute the minimum value in each RGB channel
- 3: **end for**

Atmospheric Light A Estimation

- 4: Select the top 0.1% brightest pixels in $J_{\text{dark}}(x)$
- 5: Obtain the atmospheric light A

Transmission Map $t(x)$ Estimation

- 6: **for each** window $\Omega(x)$ **in** I **do**
- 7: Normalize the image using A
- 8: Compute the transmission map $t(x)$
- 9: **end for**

Transmission Map Refinement Using Soft Matting

- 10: Apply refinement to smooth and preserve edges

Haze-Free Image Recovery

- 11: **for each** pixel x **in** I **do**
- 12: Compute the dehazed image $J(x)$
- 13: **end for**
- 14: **return** J

$$t_i = a_k I_i + b_k, \quad \forall i \in \omega_k \quad (3.7)$$

Where:

- t_i : Refined transmission value at pixel i .
- I_i : Value of the guide image at pixel i .
- a_k and b_k : Linear coefficients constant within the window ω_k .

To estimate the coefficients a_k and b_k , the following quadratic error function is minimized within each window:

$$E(a_k, b_k) = \sum_{i \in \omega_k} (a_k I_i + b_k - \tilde{t}_i)^2 + \varepsilon a_k^2 \quad (3.8)$$

Where:

- \tilde{t}_i : Initial transmission value obtained through DCP.
- ε : Regularization parameter to prevent overfitting.

The optimal coefficients are given by:

$$a_k = \frac{\frac{1}{|\omega|} \sum_{i \in \omega_k} I_i \tilde{t}_i - \mu_k \bar{t}_k}{\sigma_k^2 + \varepsilon} \quad (3.9)$$

$$b_k = \bar{t}_k - a_k \mu_k \quad (3.10)$$

Where:

- μ_k : Mean of the guide image within the window ω_k .
- σ_k^2 : Variance of the guide image within the window ω_k .
- \bar{t}_k : Mean of the initial transmission map within the window.

The refined transmission map is obtained by averaging the coefficients a_k and b_k across all overlapping windows containing pixel x :

$$t(x) = \frac{1}{|\omega|} \sum_{k: x \in \omega_k} (a_k I_x + b_k) \quad (3.11)$$

Figure 3.4 illustrates the results of the dehazing process using the Dark Channel Prior (DCP) combined with the Guided Filter. In Figure 3.4a, the effect of electrocautery is shown, where haze begins to obscure the field of view of the monocular endoscopic sensor. In Figure 3.4b, the result of the dehazing process is displayed, where most of the haze has been removed, revealing a clearer image with identifiable organ details and structures.

(a) Original monocular endoscopic image with haze.

(b) Monocular endoscopic image after haze removal using the proposed method.

Figure 3.4 Comparison of a monocular endoscopic image before and after haze removal.

Having verified that the method works effectively in a surgical environment, it was chosen for the final pipeline. It is worth reiterating that, by not relying on a deep learning-based approach, which requires a training dataset currently unavailable, the selected method offers simplicity of implementation while delivering satisfactory results within a highly acceptable standard of speed and computational efficiency, with an approximate processing time of 4.50 seconds per image.

Feature Detection

The next component to analyze is feature detection, specifically the task of **identifying surgical tools** that occlude the monocular endoscopic video, with the goal of subsequent segmentation and removal in the Deformable 3DGS output. To select the method for this component, an initial analysis of published papers was conducted, revealing a significant volume of research—over 337,000 works on object detection—with a growing interest, as illustrated in the bar chart in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5 Bar chart illustrating the number of publications on object detection from the year 2000 onwards.

Although among these works there are detection methods that employ **traditional computer vision techniques**, this option must be discarded due to their inherent limitations. These include low adaptability and insufficient precision for the scope of this work, where accurately detecting surgical tools to remove them from the Deformable 3DGS pipeline is crucial for achieving a complete view of the organ. Additionally, these techniques operate in stages, increasing complexity and reducing real-time efficiency.

For this reason, **deep learning-based feature detection methods** are proposed. Within this approach, there are two types of architectures to consider: **single-stage detectors**, where object localization and classification are performed in a single pass through the network, and **two-stage detectors**, where the first stage generates regions of interest (ROIs) and the second stage classifies and refines these ROIs to produce the final bounding boxes. The latter is discarded because single-stage detectors are characterized by their high speed and efficiency compared to two-stage detectors. Furthermore, although two-stage detectors are known for their high precision and robustness, current single-stage options are closing this performance gap (Yun 2021).

Within the single-stage architecture, one model stands out for its real-time speed while maintaining an optimal balance between precision and efficiency: the **YOLO (You Only Look Once) model**, a revolutionary approach proposed by Redmon et al. in 2016 (Redmon et al. 2015). In addition to the competitive advantages mentioned, YOLO is also notable for its ease of use, thanks to the efforts of Ultralytics, an organization that has simplified the implementation, training, and deployment of the model.

In terms of its operation, YOLO begins by dividing the input image into a grid of cells. For each cell, the network predicts the coordinates of bounding boxes, confidence scores for those boxes, and the class probabilities for the objects within the boxes. After filtering the boxes using confidence thresholds and applying Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) to eliminate redundant overlapping boxes, retaining only those with the highest confidence scores, the final output of the network is obtained (fig. 3.6 (Redmon et al. 2015)).

Figure 3.6 Object detection process using YOLO.

The precision of YOLO is demonstrated in the work "Quantitative Analysis of Deep Learning-Based Object Detection Models", which presents a comparative study evaluating the accuracy and speed of a wide range of object detection methods. This study concludes that the best-performing model is **YOLOv8-640**, achieving an average bounding box precision (APP_{bbox}) of **59.3%** and an inference speed of **0.007 ms** using the COCO 2017 dataset (Elgazzar et al. 2024).

Among the YOLO versions, **YOLOv11** was chosen because it outperforms its predecessors in terms of both precision and latency. Specifically, **YOLOv11x** achieves approximately **54.5% mAP⁵⁰⁻⁹⁵** at **13ms** latency, surpassing all previous YOLO iterations (Khanam and Hussain 2024). Figure 3.7 clearly illustrates how YOLOv11 establishes a new efficiency frontier, outperforming its predecessors in the precision-speed trade-off.

Furthermore, the approach of integrating detection and segmentation into a single

Figure 3.7 Performance comparison between different YOLO versions: Precision (COCO mAP⁵⁰⁻⁹⁵) vs Latency on T4 TensorRT10 FP16. YOLOv11 sets a new state-of-the-art, surpassing its predecessors in the precision-speed trade-off (Khanam and Hussain 2024).

model was considered but dismissed due to the issues illustrated in the figures 3.8. Through a training process of 200 epochs with data augmentation, utilizing a labeled laparoscopic scene dataset available through Roboflow (Roboflow 2024), several limitations were observed. These include incomplete surgical tool detection, leading to partial segmentation (fig. 3.8a), instances of fragmented segmentation outputs (fig. 3.8b), and inconsistencies in the continuity of detection and segmentation across frames (figs. 3.8c and 3.8d). Despite these challenges, the training revealed a persistent tendency of the model to detect tools, albeit with intermittent frame-level detection losses followed by recovery. Consequently, a two-stage framework was adopted, decoupling detection and segmentation to develop a robust composite algorithm. This strategy leverages the relatively reliable detection capability to guide the subsequent segmentation process, generating precise tool masks that are utilized for the construction of the Deformable 3DGS.

Figure 3.8 Issues in the trained YOLOv11 model for surgical tool detection and segmentation in monocular endoscopic images: (a) partial segmentation, (b) detection without full segmentation, (c-d) intermittent detection loss across frames.

Image Segmentation

Given the requirement for image segmentation to generate masks for surgical tools detected by the YOLOv11 model, a comparative analysis of potential methodologies was conducted. Similar to the components discussed earlier, image segmentation encompasses **traditional approaches** such as thresholding-based or edge detection-based methods. However, these approaches were dismissed due to their inherent limitations in dynamic surgical environments. Such limitations include poor performance under high lighting variability caused by direct artificial light sources, which induce specular reflections on the metallic and reflective surfaces of surgical tools. Additional challenges include the high heterogeneity in tool appearance, continuous tool motion during interactions with organs and tissues, and other complexities inherent to laparoscopic scenes.

Therefore, **deep learning-based image segmentation methodologies** were selected, specifically the **SAM (Segment Anything Model) version 2**, an enhanced iteration of the original SAM framework introduced by Meta AI in 2023 for object segmentation. This decision was driven by SAM 2’s superior performance in the $\mathcal{J}\&\mathcal{F}$ Score—a metric quantifying the overlap accuracy between predicted and ground-truth segmentations while evaluating boundary contour quality—and the \mathcal{G} metric (Generalization on YTVOS), which assesses a model’s robustness in generalizing to complex video segmentation scenarios using the YTVOS 2019 dataset (YouTube Video Object Segmentation), which contains diverse objects in challenging environments. As illustrated in Fig. 3.9, SAM 2 outperforms competing video object segmentation methods, demonstrating precision and consistency suitable for the scope of this work (Ravi et al. 2024).

Method	$\mathcal{J}\&\mathcal{F}$				\mathcal{G}	
	MOSE val	DAVIS 2017 val	LVOS val	SA-V val	SA-V test	YTVOS 2019 val
STCN (Cheng et al., 2021a)	52.5	85.4	-	61.0	62.5	82.7
SwinB-AOT (Yang et al., 2021b)	59.4	85.4	-	51.1	50.3	84.5
SwinB-DeAOT (Yang & Yang, 2022)	59.9	86.2	-	61.4	61.8	86.1
RDE (Li et al., 2022a)	46.8	84.2	-	51.8	53.9	81.9
XMem (Cheng & Schwing, 2022)	59.6	86.0	-	60.1	62.3	85.6
SimVOS-B (Wu et al., 2023b)	-	88.0	-	44.2	44.1	84.2
JointFormer (Zhang et al., 2023b)	-	90.1	-	-	-	87.4
ISVOS (Wang et al., 2022)	-	88.2	-	-	-	86.3
DEVA (Cheng et al., 2023b)	66.0	87.0	55.9	55.4	56.2	85.4
Cutie-base (Cheng et al., 2023a)	69.9	87.9	66.0	60.7	62.7	87.0
Cutie-base+ (Cheng et al., 2023a)	71.7	88.1	-	61.3	62.8	87.5
SAM 2 (Hiera-B+)	<u>76.6</u>	<u>90.2</u>	78.0	<u>76.8</u>	<u>77.0</u>	<u>88.6</u>
SAM 2 (Hiera-L)	77.9	90.7	78.0	77.9	78.4	89.3

Figure 3.9 Comparative performance of video object segmentation methods across benchmark datasets: MOSE, DAVIS 2017, LVOS, SA-V, and YTVOS 2019. Reported metrics include the $\mathcal{J}\&\mathcal{F}$ Score and \mathcal{G} metric. SAM 2 variants (Hiera-B+ and Hiera-L) achieve state-of-the-art performance on most datasets, showcasing excellence in segmentation accuracy and generalization capabilities (Ravi et al. 2024).

Regarding its architecture, SAM2 is based on a continuous flow memory framework,

enabling sequential processing of video frames while maintaining spatiotemporal coherence of segmented objects. Its workflow is outlined below (Fig. 3.10) (Ravi et al. 2024):

1. **Prompting:** The input is provided by the YOLOv11 model's bounding boxes for each video frame.
2. **Image Encoding (Feature Extraction):** Upon receiving the prompt, SAM2 processes the selected frame using its *Hiera* image encoder, which transforms the image into a compact numerical representation capturing key visual features (e.g., edges, textures, and object-specific patterns). The encoding process involves:
 - (a) **Spatial Partitioning:** The input image is subdivided into fixed-size patches.
 - (b) **Hierarchical Feature Extraction:** Multi-scale representations are generated to capture details at varying abstraction levels.
 - (c) **Embedding Generation:** High-dimensional feature descriptors are produced for subsequent segmentation steps.
3. **Memory Attention:** Unlike the original SAM, which performed static image segmentation without temporal context, SAM2 incorporates a memory bank to enhance temporal consistency in video sequences. This bank stores features from previously processed frames, enabling retrieval of object-specific historical data. The memory attention mechanism operates as follows:
 - (a) **Previous Frame Querying:** Recent frames stored in the memory bank are accessed to analyze the segmented object's evolution. A similarity metric compares the object's current position and appearance with historical data.
 - (b) **Information Fusion:** Current features are fused with historical data to refine predictions, ensuring temporally coherent segmentation.
4. **Mask Prediction:** Using the current frame's features and historical memory, SAM2 generates segmentation masks via a specialized decoder that predicts the object's spatial extent. The mask prediction process includes:
 - (a) **Multi-Hypothesis Generation:** Multiple segmentation hypotheses are created to address prediction uncertainty.
 - (b) **IoU-Based Optimal Selection:** The final mask is selected using the Intersection over Union (IoU) metric to ensure maximal accuracy.
 - (c) **Memory-Driven Correction:** Segmentation is refined using the object's temporal evolution, recovering details lost to occlusions or rapid motion.

5. **Memory Update:** After generating the segmentation mask for the current frame, SAM2 updates its memory bank by storing the processed frame’s visual features, segmentation mask, and object spatial coordinates for future inference.
6. **Refinement through Feedback:** SAM2 incorporates a continuous user feedback mechanism, allowing additional prompts to refine segmentation in frames with inaccuracies.

Figure 3.10 Overview of the SAM2 architecture. The model processes video frames over time, starting with the image encoder, which extracts hierarchical visual features. The memory attention module retrieves relevant information from previous frames to ensure temporal consistency. The mask decoder generates segmentation masks based on encoded image features and user prompts such as masks, points, or bounding boxes. The memory encoder updates the memory bank, storing temporal information for subsequent frames, enhancing the model’s ability to track objects throughout the video.(Ravi et al. 2024).

As shown in Fig. 3.11, the segmented frame generated by SAM2 using bounding boxes from the YOLOv11 surgical tool detection and segmentation model (employed in Fig. 3.8b) demonstrates accurate segmentation of both tools. This result validates the selection of SAM2, as it resolves the partial segmentation issues observed earlier.

(a) Original endoscopic video frame. (b) YOLOv11 trained model with segmentation errors. (c) SAM2 segmentation using bounding boxes from the YOLOv11 trained model.

Figure 3.11 Comparison of segmentation between the YOLOv11 trained model and SAM2 model.

Video Inpainting

With the surgical tools masked, video inpainting can be performed to reconstruct occluded areas in monocular endoscopic videos by filling missing regions with visually plausible content. This process aims to generate a coherent video sequence in which surgical tools are effectively removed, thereby providing an unobstructed view of anatomical structures.

Video inpainting methodologies can be broadly categorized into traditional or deep learning-based approaches. Traditional methods were dismissed due to inherent limitations, including temporal incoherence (as these methods process individual frames independently, ignoring inter-frame relationships) and poor performance in handling large occluded regions. This last challenge is particularly critical in endoscopic scenes, where surgical tools often occupy significant portions of the frame. In Figures 3.12, the inpainting results can be observed when attempting to remove the surgical tools, yielding outcomes that do not meet acceptable minimum standards. The presented results are based on the following methods (Chatterjee, Jana, and Ghosh 2021):

- **Fast Marching Method Inpainting - OpenCV `INPAINT_TELEA`:** Based on the rapid propagation of information from the edges of the missing region inward, using an anisotropic diffusion algorithm. This technique propagates neighboring pixel values along contour directions, preserving local structures and details to achieve a visually coherent transition (Fig. 3.12b).
- **Fluid Dynamics Inpainting - OpenCV `INPAINT_NS`:** Inspired by the Navier-Stokes fluid dynamics equations, this method extends isophotes (lines of equal intensity) from known regions into missing areas, ensuring smooth propagation of textures and edges. It prioritizes geometric continuity by propagating structural features rather than directly interpolating pixel values (Fig. 3.12c).
- **Fast Structure Reconstruction - OpenCV `INPAINT_FSR_FAST`:** Employs a rapid structural reconstruction technique based on information extrapolation from visible regions, using accelerated interpolation to estimate missing pixel values. Computationally efficient and suitable for real-time applications, though it may yield suboptimal visual results in high-complexity areas (Fig. 3.12d).
- **Best Structure Reconstruction - OpenCV `INPAINT_FSR_BEST`:** An optimized variant of the FAST method, utilizing advanced interpolation and refinement techniques for higher-quality reconstruction. Improves texture and contour propagation accuracy, delivering more realistic and visually consistent results at the cost of increased processing time compared to FAST (Fig. 3.12e).

As shown in Figures 3.12, all traditional methods produce unacceptable inpainting results due to the loss of anatomical details. Additionally, the Fast Marching and Fluid

(a) Original monocular endoscopic video frame containing surgical tools before in-painting.

(b) Result of in-painting using Fast Marching Method In-painting. Notice the linear artifacts and the over-smoothing effect, leading to a loss of fine texture details.

(c) Result of in-painting using the Navier-Stokes method. Artifacts of linear propagation are noticeable, and the texture continuity is not fully preserved.

(d) Result of in-painting using the FAST method. The generated colors do not blend well with the surroundings, and fine anatomical details are lost.

(e) Result of in-painting using the BEST method. Although it provides the most visually consistent result, texture artifacts and detail loss are still present.

Figure 3.12 Comparison of traditional in-painting methods for the removal of surgical tools in monocular endoscopic video.

Dynamics methods exhibit linear smearing, leaving visible linear artifacts in the output. The Fast Structure Reconstruction method minimizes these linear marks but introduces chromatic artifacts, where interpolated colors mismatch the surrounding tissue. Finally, the Best Structure Reconstruction method over-smooths the inpainted regions, erasing critical details and generating filling patterns inconsistent with the original anatomical structure.

Given the limitations of traditional video inpainting methods, deep learning-based approaches were explored. Among these, the **Spatial-Temporal Transformer Network (STTN)** achieved accurate inpainting while preserving anatomical details. In contrast, DeepFillv2 (Yu et al. 2019), though outperforming traditional methods, produced inferior results compared to STTN, as evidenced by unrealistic textures in reconstructed areas, whereas STTN maintained smoother and anatomically consistent reconstructions.

Figure 3.13 Comparison of inpainting methods applied to surgical tool removal in monocular endoscopic videos. DeepFill introduces texture inconsistencies, whereas STTN achieves superior visual consistency and structural preservation.

The STTN model, proposed by Zeng et al., features an architecture comprising the following components (Fig. 3.14) (Zeng, Fu, and Chao 2020):

1. **Frame Encoder:** Responsible for extracting spatial features from each input video frame. A series of 2D convolutional layers is employed to capture low- and high-level visual information, such as edges, textures, and color patterns. The encoder incorporates multiple convolutional layers with varying filter sizes and strides, alongside non-linear activation functions (e.g., Leaky ReLU) to mitigate gradient vanishing. Feature normalization techniques, such as Instance Normalization, are applied to enhance training stability and model generalization. The output is a set of low-

dimensional latent representations preserving essential visual information, facilitating subsequent processing in the spatial-temporal transformer module.

2. **Spatial-Temporal Transformer:** The core component of STTN, designed to propagate information across the temporal dimension of the video. Its objective is to fill missing regions by identifying coherent information in neighboring and distant video frames. This is achieved through a multi-head patch-based attention mechanism, which analyzes relationships between video segments at multiple scales.
3. **Frame Decoder:** Converts the transformer-generated representations back into complete video frames. Its primary role is to restore the original spatial resolution and enhance the visual quality of reconstructed frames. The decoder combines transposed convolutions and upsampling techniques (e.g., bilinear interpolation) to progressively increase spatial resolution while preserving visual coherence. The process concludes with a *tanh* activation function to normalize pixel values within the appropriate range, ensuring generated frames are visually consistent with the original sequence.

Figure 3.14 Architecture of the Spatial-Temporal Transformer Network (STTN) for video inpainting. The input consists of a sequence of frames with missing regions, which are processed by a frame-level encoder to extract feature representations. These features are then fed into the spatial-temporal transformer, which employs a multi-head attention mechanism with multiple patch scales to capture dependencies across frames. The extracted patches are projected into query (Q), key (K), and value (V) representations, where an attention mechanism computes similarities to fill the missing regions. Finally, the processed features are reconstructed through a frame-level decoder to produce the inpainted output sequence (Zeng, Fu, and Chao 2020).

Another key factor in selecting the STTN model is its demonstrated superiority over state-of-the-art models such as *VINet*, *DFVI*, *LGTSM*, and *CAP* in video inpainting tasks. Quantitative evaluations on the benchmark datasets **Youtube-VOS** and **DAVIS** confirm that STTN consistently outperforms existing methods across key metrics, including **PSNR** (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio), **SSIM** (Structural Similarity Index), **Flow Warp**

Error (Ewarp), and **VFID** (Video-based Fréchet Inception Distance). Notably, STTN achieves relative improvements of **2.4%** (PSNR), **1.3%** (SSIM), and **19.7%** (Ewarp) on Youtube-VOS, with particularly significant advancements in reducing flow warp errors and enhancing the perceptual quality of reconstructed videos (Zeng, Fu, and Chao 2020).

Depth Estimation

As outlined in the "Most Relevant 3D Reconstruction Techniques" section, **traditional depth estimation methods** such as Structure-from-Motion (SfM) and Multi-View Stereo (MVS) can theoretically derive depth from monocular endoscopic images. However, these methods were dismissed due to inherent limitations in endoscopic video environments. First, they require multiview captures from diverse angles to reconstruct 3D scene geometry—a condition rarely met in endoscopic procedures, where the camera is typically constrained to a single frontal viewpoint. Second, challenges such as highly deformable soft tissues, dynamic illumination changes, specular reflections, and the absence of distinctive textural features degrade keypoint matching accuracy between consecutive frames, further undermining geometric correspondence-based approaches. Consequently, deep learning-based methods were adopted for their robustness to these constraints.

The selected approach is the **Depth Anything V2 model**, proposed by Yang et al., which significantly improves upon its predecessor in detail preservation and robustness. Key advancements include the use of an advanced teacher model trained on highly precise synthetic data to generate high-quality depth pseudo-labels. These pseudo-labels enable the training of a student model on large volumes of unlabeled real-world images, ensuring accurate and generalizable depth estimation (fig. 3.15). The model operates via a transformer-based deep learning pipeline (ViT) for monocular depth estimation, structured into four stages (Yang et al. 2024a):

1. **Input Image Preprocessing:** The monocular input image undergoes normalization (pixel value scaling to a standardized range) and resizing to a fixed resolution.
2. **Feature Extraction with DINOv2 Encoder:** The preprocessed image is fed into the DINOv2-based encoder, a pre-trained vision transformer (ViT) for extracting rich visual representations. The DINOv2 architecture comprises:
 - (a) **Image Patch Partitioning:** The image is divided into small patches, linearly projected into high-dimensional embeddings.
 - (b) **Self-Attention Mechanisms:** Global intra-image relationships are modeled through self-attention, enabling cross-regional influence on depth estimation.
 - (c) **Visual Embedding Generation:** A set of representative embeddings encoding texture, edges, and relative depth cues is produced.

3. **Depth Decoding with Depth Prediction Transformer (DPT):** The DINOv2-derived features are processed by a depth decoder (DPT variant) to generate detailed depth maps. The DPT operates as follows:
 - (a) **Multi-Scale Feature Fusion:** Integrates features across abstraction levels to capture fine details and global scene structures.
 - (b) **Depth Regression Mechanism:** Correlates visual features with relative depth via attention layers, producing affine-invariant depth maps.
 - (c) **Specialized Loss Optimization:** Employs *Scale- and Shift-Invariant Loss (SSI Loss)* for scale consistency and *Gradient Matching Loss* to enhance edge sharpness and structural fidelity.

4. **Depth Map Postprocessing:** The raw depth map is normalized to ensure scene-consistent scale, low-confidence regions (below a predefined threshold) are suppressed, and spatial interpolation is applied to smooth depth transitions.

Figure 3.15 Illustration of the Depth Anything V2 training pipeline based on a teacher-student learning paradigm. The process consists of three key steps: (1) training a teacher network on multiple synthetic datasets to learn high-quality depth representations, (2) generating pseudo-labeled datasets from real-world unlabeled data using the trained teacher network, and (3) training a student network on the pseudo-labeled dataset to achieve an optimal balance between accuracy and computational efficiency (Biswas 2024).

Depth Anything V2 was chosen for this study as it was the most advanced model available during this Deformable 3DGS project’s development (last quarter of 2024), coinciding with Depth Anything V2’s official release on October 20, 2024, making it an ideal fit for integration into this work. Its superiority over state-of-the-art depth estimation models—including *AdaBins*, *DPT*, *P3Depth*, *SwinV2*, *AiT*, *VPD*, *IEBins*, and *ZoeDepth*—was demonstrated across benchmark datasets such as **NYU-D** and **KITTI**.

Quantitative evaluations confirm that Depth Anything V2, particularly the ViT-L variant, consistently outperforms these existing methods across key metrics.

In the NYU-D dataset, it achieves the highest values in accuracy metrics, such as δ_1 (0.984), δ_2 (0.998), and δ_3 (1.000), which measure the proportion of predicted depth values that fall within a certain factor of the ground truth depth, providing an indicator of the model's precision in estimating varying depth ranges. Furthermore, Depth Anything V2 achieves the lowest error values, including **Absolute Relative Error (AbsRel)** (0.056), which quantifies the average relative deviation of predicted depths from ground truth depths, **Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)** (0.206), which evaluates the quadratic mean of prediction errors and penalizes larger deviations, and **log10** (0.024), which measures the logarithmic error between predicted and actual depth values, offering insights into scale consistency.

Similarly, on the KITTI dataset, Depth Anything V2 (ViT-L) surpasses competing models with a δ_1 of 0.983 and the lowest error metrics, including **AbsRel** (0.045), **RMSE** (1.861), and **RMSE log** (0.067) (Yang et al. 2024a). These results indicate significant improvements in both accuracy and robustness over existing solutions, making Depth Anything V2 the optimal choice for monocular depth estimation tasks, particularly in scenarios requiring high precision and reliability across diverse environments.

In Figure 4.13, the depth estimation obtained using the Depth Anything V2 model is presented, demonstrating a preservation of the overall structure with a clear differentiation between the surgical instruments and the background. Additionally, the depth map exhibits a smooth and coherent transition between different parts of the scene, with progressive depth values from the surgical instruments in the foreground to the tissues in the background. It is also worth highlighting the accurate capture of details, such as the edges of the surgical instruments and the effective handling of homogeneous tissue surfaces.

(a) Monocular endoscopic image capturing a surgical scene with surgical tools.

(b) Estimated depth map from the monocular endoscopic image.

Figure 3.16 Comparison between the original monocular endoscopic image and the corresponding depth estimation obtained using Deep Anything V2 model.

Camera Pose Estimation

The next essential component for Deformable 3DGS is camera pose estimation, which involves determining the 3D position and orientation of the camera relative to a global or scene-specific coordinate system.

It must be emphasized again that traditional camera pose estimation methods, such as Structure from Motion (SfM) or algorithms like COLMAP (Schönberger and Frahm 2016), are dismissed due to inherent limitations in dynamic surgical scenes. These methods assume that the scene is predominantly rigid—a condition not met in surgical environments where organs and tissues constantly change shape. Additionally, traditional algorithms rely on triangulation between multiple viewpoints to calculate depth and camera pose, whereas laparoscopic surgery provides only a single frontal viewpoint, introducing scale and depth ambiguities.

Given the limitations and challenges in this camera pose estimation phase, an initial literature review confirmed that the works presented in the "3D Gaussian Splatting in Surgical Scenes" section rely exclusively on pre-existing datasets, and none have considered using a custom dataset requiring preprocessing to prepare data for creating a Deformable 3DGS. This is evidenced, for example, in the review of MICCAI 2024, the 27th International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention, which shows that the SurgicalGaussian work did not consider using a custom dataset and only utilized the EndoNeRF and StereoMIS datasets (2024 2024). Furthermore, an issue published by the author in the EndoGaussian work confirms that its authors also did not consider preprocessing their own data (Group 2024), even recommending the use of COLMAP or GLOMAP—an enhanced version of COLMAP that simultaneously estimates the positions and orientations of all cameras (Pan et al. 2024). However, as previously presented, these tools were deemed unsuitable and were attempted in this work, resulting in errors in both cases.

Given this fact and the absence of prior research on the case, an exhaustive study of tools capable of pose estimation under these challenging conditions was conducted, which also confirmed that the approach to follow was deep learning-based methods. The selected method is **MonST3R (Monocular Spatio-Temporal 3D Reconstruction)**, an evolution of DUS_t3R (Dense Unsupervised Structure from Motion with Transformers), which creates an opportunity window for this Deformable 3DGS project by removing DUS_t3R's inherent limitation of being designed for static scenes, where it assumes the scene structure remains constant over time. Similar to the Depth Anything V2 model, the MonST3R method emerged during the development of this work, specifically on October 4, 2024, making it the most novel work in camera pose estimation for dynamic scenes. MonST3R's architecture consists of three main stages: **feature extraction**, **scene geometry prediction**, and **global optimization** for pose and structure refinement. These are detailed

below (Fig. 3.17) (Zhang et al. 2024):

1. Feature Extraction:

- (a) **Model Input:** A sequence of monocular images $I^t, I^{t+1}, I^{t+2}, \dots$, from which it extracts essential features for subsequent processing.
- (b) **Transformer-Based Encoder:** The model employs a *transformer-based encoder*, inspired by Vision Transformers (ViT), to capture spatial and temporal information from the scene. The components of the encoder are:
 - **Patch Embeddings:** Each image is divided into fixed-size patches that are projected into a latent feature space using a linear layer.
 - **Self-Attention Mechanisms:** These model long-range dependencies between patches within each image and across video frames.
 - **Positional Encoding:** Positional encodings are added to preserve spatial structure after the patch division.
- (c) **Encoder Output:** A feature-rich representation encoding the geometric structure of the scene.

2. Scene Geometry Prediction:

- **Generation of 3D Point Clouds per Frame:** Based on the extracted features, depth maps and 3D coordinates of the scene are predicted. The inverse projection is applied to convert 2D image points into 3D coordinates:

$$P_{3D} = K^{-1} \cdot \hat{D}(u, v) \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.12)$$

where $\hat{D}(u, v)$ represents the estimated depth.

- 3. **Camera Pose Estimation:** Performed in two phases: an **initial relative pose estimation** using traditional methods and a **global optimization** to refine accuracy.

- (a) **Initial Estimation of Relative Camera Pose:** First estimates the relative pose between consecutive frames t and t' using the **Perspective-n-Point (PnP)** method, which determines the rotation R and translation T of the camera. The process is shown below:
 - i. **2D-3D Correspondence Generation:** A set of correspondences between estimated 3D points $X^{t;t'}$ and their respective 2D projections x in the image is obtained.

ii. **PnP Solution:** The pose estimation is formulated as follows:

$$R^*, T^* = \arg \min_{R, T} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left\| x_i - \pi(RX_i^{t;t'} + T) \right\|^2 \quad (3.13)$$

where:

- x_i are 2D pixel coordinates.
- $\pi(\cdot)$ is the projection function from 3D to 2D.
- $X_i^{t;t'}$ represents the estimated 3D point cloud.

iii. **Outlier Rejection with RANSAC:** RANSAC is applied to remove incorrect correspondences and improve robustness.

iv. **Initial Output:** The estimated relative pose is represented as:

$$P^{t \rightarrow t'} = [R^* \mid T^*] \quad (3.14)$$

(b) **Global Optimization of Camera Pose:** To refine the initial pose and correct accumulated errors, MonST3R applies a **global optimization**, adjusting poses and point clouds simultaneously.

Objectives of global optimization:

- Minimize accumulated pose estimation errors.
- Ensure smooth trajectories by avoiding abrupt changes in rotation and translation.
- Enforce consistency with optical flow to validate motion estimation.

Global Optimization Cost Function:

$$\hat{X} = \arg \min \mathcal{L}_{\text{align}}(X, \sigma, P_W) + w_{\text{smooth}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{smooth}}(X) + w_{\text{flow}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{flow}}(X) \quad (3.15)$$

where:

- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{align}}$ minimizes alignment errors between accumulated and local estimates.
- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{smooth}}$ penalizes abrupt variations in rotation and translation.
- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{flow}}$ ensures that the estimated motion aligns with the optical flow.

Optimization Process:

- i. Reparametrize poses and point clouds in a global coordinate frame.
- ii. Optimize camera trajectory by minimizing the loss terms.
- iii. Obtain a final refined representation of the scene.

4. **4D Global Scene Reconstruction:** After global optimization, MonST3R produces a consistent 4D reconstruction of the scene using smoothed camera trajectories and aligned global point cloud.

Figure 3.17 Overview of the MonST3R pipeline for dynamic scene reconstruction. The model processes an input video using a sliding window approach, extracting per-frame pointmaps and optical flow estimates. These intermediate representations are accumulated over time and optimized using three key loss functions: alignment loss ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{align}}$) to ensure geometric consistency, flow loss ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{flow}}$) to enforce agreement with optical flow estimations, and smoothness loss ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{smooth}}$) to regularize the camera trajectory. The optimization yields a globally consistent point cloud representation and refined camera pose parameters ($\hat{X}, \hat{P}, \hat{K}$) (Zhang et al. 2024).

In Figure 3.18, it is confirmed that MonST3R is valid for camera pose estimation in surgical scenes derived from monocular endoscopic video.

Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting

After establishing the preprocessing pipeline for monocular endoscopic videos, the choice of 3DGS method to apply was analyzed. As discussed in the section "3D Gaussian Splatting in Surgical Scenes," two methods stand out among the limited current options: **SurgicalGaussian** and **Deform3DGS**. Their key differences are as follows:

1. Deformation Modeling Approach:

- **SurgicalGaussian** employs a **Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)** to capture tissue deformations. This network learns an implicit deformation representation through nonlinear functions, enabling modeling of complex geometric changes. However, this comes at the cost of increased training time and computational overhead (Xie et al. 2024).
- **Deform3DGS** introduces a more efficient framework called **Flexible Deformation Modeling (FDM)**, which uses linear combinations of Gaussian

Figure 3.18 Visualization of the estimated camera pose within a surgical scene from monocular endoscopic video.

basis functions. This explicit deformation modeling approach achieves computational efficiency and significantly reduces training time (Yang et al. 2024b).

2. Initialization and Reconstruction Precision:

- **SurgicalGaussian** relies on depth maps and surgical masks for point cloud initialization, depending on the MLP to refine details during training (Xie et al. 2024).
- **Deform3DGS** incorporates **Motion-Aware Point Fusion (MAPF)**, enhancing reconstruction accuracy by densely distributing Gaussian points in regions of high tissue deformation. This strategy prioritizes critical areas from the outset, minimizing the need for extended iterative refinement (Yang et al. 2024b).

Although initial descriptions might suggest Deform3DGS as the optimal choice for developing a Deformable 3DGS from monocular endoscopic videos, a numerical comparison between both methods was conducted using the same subset of the EndoNeRF dataset, as previously mentioned in the literature review.

Table 3.1 displays the results of a 3000-iteration training process for both SurgicalGaussian and Deform3DGS on the EndoNeRF subset (Wang et al. 2022). It is worth noting that PSNR values representing the mean PSNR across a 62-image sequence for the "Pulling" scenario and a 135-image sequence for the "Cutting" scenario. Additionally, occlusion zone rendering results were excluded from the comparison, as this limitation is explicitly targeted for improvement in this work.

Based on Table 3.1, Deform3DGS substantially outperforms SurgicalGaussian in processing time while achieving higher PSNR in the "Pulling" scenario. Specifically, De-

form3DGS achieves a 62.93% reduction in total time for the "Pulling" task alongside a 35.88% improvement in PSNR. For the "Cutting" task, Deform3DGS maintains a 46.83% time reduction, while its PSNR remains practically identical, with only a 0.097% decrease compared to SurgicalGaussian.

The minor PSNR discrepancy in the "Cutting" scenario arises from Deform3DGS's inability to reconstruct the left lateral region (Fig. 3.19c). However, it is observed that other regions are accurately reconstructed with only 3000 iterations. It is worth noting that, without this discrepancy, the PSNR in Deform3DGS would be significantly higher.

A critical drawback of SurgicalGaussian further justifies its rejection: when trained and rendered for 40,000 iterations, it achieves a PSNR of 39.6336 in 1 hour and 47 minutes—failing to surpass Deform3DGS's "Pulling" scenario PSNR of 40.3025, which is attained in just 1 minute and 51 seconds. For 40,000 iterations, Deform3DGS achieves a PSNR of 42.8937 in 20 minutes and 17 seconds, representing an 8.23% quality improvement with 81.2% less computational time, unequivocally demonstrating its superiority in both reconstruction quality and processing speed.

Tabla 3.1 Comparisons of SurgicalGaussian and Deform3DGS on the same subset of the EndoNeRF dataset.

Scenario	Total Time (Train + Render) (s)	PSNR
Pulling EndoNeRF (SurgicalGaussian)	299.04	29.6593
Cutting EndoNeRF (SurgicalGaussian)	286.59	28.9080
Pulling EndoNeRF (Deform3DGS)	110.84	40.3025
Cutting EndoNeRF (Deform3DGS)	152.44	28.8801

On the other hand, a qualitative analysis of the "Cutting" scenario reveals that SurgicalGaussian fails to achieve sharp reconstructions, producing significantly blurred outputs where fine anatomical details—particularly on the left image region—are lost (Fig. 3.19b). In contrast, Deform3DGS delivers sharper reconstructions with preserved structural details (Fig. 3.19c). However, partial reconstruction on the left side suggests that additional iterations may be required for full completion. This incomplete region directly impacts the PSNR metric, despite the overall superior visual fidelity.

In the "Pulling" scenario, SurgicalGaussian similarly exhibits pronounced blurring, with substantial loss of anatomical details in high-texture regions such as blood vessels and tissue boundaries (Fig. 3.20b). Deform3DGS, however, achieves a markedly higher PSNR (43.4136), reflecting its enhanced capacity to retain details and improve sharpness (Fig. 3.20c). The reconstructed output demonstrates clearer anatomical structures and enhanced texture definition. However, some challenges remain, such as slight blurriness in the area previously occluded by the left-side surgical instrument, leading to visible discontinuities in the white line that was initially covered. Additionally, a prominent black region appears where the right-side surgical tool was previously located.

- (a) Original endoscopic image of the "Cutting" EndoN-eRF scenario.
- (b) Reconstruction using SurgicalGaussian (image PSNR: 28.5501). The result appears very blurry, especially on the left side of the reconstruction, leading to a significant loss of anatomical details.
- (c) Reconstruction using Deform3DGS (image PSNR: 27.2331). The image presents higher sharpness and improved precision in reconstruction. However, the left side reveals an incomplete region that negatively impacts the PSNR.

Figure 3.19 Qualitative comparison of original and reconstructed endoscopic images using SurgicalGaussian and Deform3DGS. SurgicalGaussian produces a blurry reconstruction, while Deform3DGS achieves sharper results with some remaining incomplete areas.

- (a) Original endoscopic image of the "Pulling" EndoN-eRF scenario.
- (b) Reconstruction using SurgicalGaussian (PSNR: 34.1603). The result appears blurry, losing anatomical details across the image, particularly in areas of high texture.
- (c) Reconstruction using Deform3DGS (PSNR: 43.4136). The visual quality is significantly improved; however, slight blurriness is observed in the region previously occluded by the left instrument, with discontinuities in the white line and a large black region due to the left-side tool occlusion.

Figure 3.20 Qualitative comparison of original and reconstructed endoscopic images for the "Pulling" scenario using SurgicalGaussian and Deform3DGS. While Deform3DGS shows superior visual quality, some areas affected by occlusions require further refinement.

For the quantitative and qualitative reasons outlined above, the Deform3DGS reconstruction method was selected for implementing Deformable 3DGS from monocular endoscopic videos. Regarding its operation, the workflow of Deform3DGS is structured into the following stages (fig. 3.21) (Yang et al. 2024b):

1. **Input processing:** The input to the Deform3DGS pipeline is a monocular endoscopic video, which consists of a sequence of images I_i , depth maps D_i obtained via stereo estimation, and binary masks M_i to segment surgical tools from the scene. Additionally, the initial camera pose parameters, provided in the form of a pose bounds file, are required to establish a consistent global reference frame and ensure accurate 3D point cloud initialization.
2. **Motion-Aware Point Fusion (MAPF):** The initial 3D point cloud is generated by projecting the depth maps onto the 3D space using the camera intrinsic matrix K . The process is defined as:

$$P^i = K^{-1}D_i(I_i \odot M_i) \quad (3.16)$$

where:

- I_i is the input image
- D_i is the depth map
- M_i is the tissue mask

A motion-aware strategy is then applied to distribute the Gaussian points more densely in high-deformation areas. A motion mask F is computed using frame-to-frame differences and the mean image approach:

$$F = I(\|C_0 - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=0}^N C_j\| > \tau) \cup (1 - M_0) \quad (3.17)$$

where:

- F is the resulting motion mask, highlighting regions with significant deformation or tool occlusions.
- C_0 is the initial reference frame in the sequence.
- C_j represents the j -th frame in the sequence.
- $\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=0}^N C_j$ is the mean image across the sequence, used to compute global changes in pixel intensity over time.

- $\| \cdot \|$ denotes the pixel-wise difference between the initial frame and the mean image.
- τ is a predefined threshold to identify significant pixel intensity differences indicative of motion.
- M_0 is the tool mask for the initial frame, where $1 - M_0$ highlights tissue regions by excluding tools.
- $I(\cdot)$ is an indicator function that outputs 1 for pixels exceeding the threshold τ and 0 otherwise.

3. **Flexible Deformation Modeling (FDM):** The FDM module allows efficient representation of tissue deformations over time without relying on computationally expensive neural networks such as MLPs. Instead, it models deformations using a weighted sum of Gaussian basis functions:

$$b(t; \theta, \sigma) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}(t - \theta)^2\right) \quad (3.18)$$

where:

- $b(t; \theta, \sigma)$ represents the Gaussian basis function used to model temporal deformations.
- t represents the current time step.
- θ is the mean of the Gaussian basis function, which defines the temporal center of influence for the deformation.
- σ represents the standard deviation, controlling the spread of the deformation effect over time.

Each 3D Gaussian G in the point cloud is represented by:

$$G = \{(\mu, r, s, \alpha, c)\} \quad (3.19)$$

where:

- μ represents the 3D position.
- r represents the rotation.
- s represents the scale.
- α represents opacity.
- c represents the spherical harmonics-based color encoding.

The temporal evolution of deformations is modeled using:

$$\psi(t; \Theta) = \sum_{j=1}^B \omega_j b_j(t) \quad (3.20)$$

where ω_j are learnable weights, and $b_j(t)$ are Gaussian basis functions.

4. **Model Optimization:** Deform3DGS optimizes the reconstruction by minimizing a combination of color and depth loss functions. The color loss function \mathcal{L}_C ensures consistency between the rendered and reference images:

$$\mathcal{L}_C = \|M \odot (\hat{C} - C)\| \quad (3.21)$$

where:

- \mathcal{L}_C is the color loss function that measures the difference between the rendered and real images.
- M is the tissue mask.
- \odot represents the element-wise multiplication, ensuring only unoccluded pixels contribute to the loss.
- \hat{C} is the rendered color image generated by the Gaussian splatting model.
- C is the reference ground-truth image from the endoscopic video.

The depth loss function \mathcal{L}_D ensures accurate depth reconstruction:

$$\mathcal{L}_D = \|M \odot (\hat{D}^{-1} - D^{-1})\| \quad (3.22)$$

where:

- \mathcal{L}_D is the depth loss function, which measures the inverse depth error.
- \hat{D} is the predicted depth map obtained from the model.
- D is the ground-truth depth map estimated from stereo vision.
- M is the tissue mask.
- The inverse depth formulation D^{-1} is used to provide better numerical stability during optimization.

The total optimization objective is given by:

$$L = \mathcal{L}_C + \mathcal{L}_D \quad (3.23)$$

where L represents the final loss function combining both color and depth terms, ensuring that the reconstructed scene maintains visual consistency and geometric accuracy.

Figure 3.21 Illustration of our fast deformable tissue reconstruction framework, Deform3DGS, composed of (a) Point cloud initialization, (b) Flexible Deformation Modeling, and (c) 3D Gaussian Splatting (Yang et al. 2024b).

As demonstrated in its workflow, Deform3DGS addresses the challenge of surgical tools occluding the scene by leveraging information from frames where the tool does not occlude the same region. To achieve this, the Motion-Aware Point Fusion (MAPF) mechanism merges points from different temporal instances, ensuring higher point density in dynamically deforming areas. Thus, even if a region is occluded in certain frames, historical data from previous frames is retained and adjusted according to tissue motion. Additionally, the Flexible Deformation Modeling (FDM) enables realistic movement of Gaussian points through Gaussian basis functions, interpolating the appearance of occluded regions based on visible surrounding tissue data. Finally, model optimization—incorporating color and depth loss functions—smooths transitions between visible and estimated regions, ensuring coherent reconstructions free of artifacts.

However, Deform3DGS faces limitations when a surgical tool continuously occludes a scene region throughout the entire video sequence. Since the model relies on aggregating information from multiple frames over time to inpaint occluded areas, regions never visible in any captured frame lack prior data for inferring structure and appearance. This is illustrated in Figs. 3.19c and 3.20c, where black artifacts persist in regions perpetually occluded by tools. This issue is addressed in the "System Development" section.

System Development

This chapter presents the system development framework for implementing Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting for Monocular Endoscopic Video Reconstruction, detailing the **modular architecture**, **execution workflow**, and **software integration**. The chapter begins by describing the system architecture, which is structured into **two main stages**: the **dataset preparation pipeline** and the **model optimization stage**. The dataset preparation involves multiple preprocessing steps, including video dehazing, surgical tool segmentation, video inpainting, depth estimation, and camera pose estimation. The second stage focuses on the implementation of InDeform3DGS, which incorporates inpainting-based enhancements to improve reconstruction quality in occluded surgical regions.

A detailed execution workflow is then outlined, specifying the required system configuration, dependencies, and execution methodology.

The chapter proceeds with a comprehensive discussion of each core module, elaborating on the feature detection, video dehazing, segmentation, inpainting, depth estimation, and camera pose estimation stages. The feature detection module employs YOLOv11, with hyperparameter optimization conducted using Optuna, ensuring optimal detection accuracy. The video dehazing module integrates the Dark Channel Prior (DCP) with Guided Filtering, improving visibility in endoscopic footage through an interactive parameter-tuning approach. The segmentation module utilizes Segment Anything Model 2 (SAM2), incorporating a temporal consistency mechanism to refine bounding box selection over consecutive frames. The inpainting module is based on Spatial-Temporal Transformer Networks (STTN), integrating batch processing and tunable parameters to enhance inpainting quality and efficiency. The depth estimation module employs Depth Anything V2, leveraging batch processing to optimize computational performance while ensuring accurate depth reconstruction. Finally, MonST3R is implemented for camera pose estimation, with batch processing optimizations reducing memory overhead while maintaining

pose estimation accuracy.

The chapter also introduces InDeform3DGS, an improvement over Deform3DGS, which integrates **inpainting-based reconstruction refinements**. This method combines multiple loss functions designed to enhance the reconstruction of regions occluded by surgical instruments. These include similarity loss, depth inpaint loss, illumination loss, diversity loss, edge-smoothing loss, temporal consistency loss, and noise loss, ensuring that occluded regions are reconstructed with minimal artifacts while maintaining anatomical consistency.

Finally, software integration is discussed, detailing the project’s structured directory organization, modular design, and implementation best practices. The main pipeline script (`main.py`) is introduced, allowing the execution of individual or combined processing stages while ensuring efficient data handling and GPU resource management. Key utility scripts for bounding box extraction, model training, pose visualization, and evaluation automation are also described. The chapter concludes by presenting the complete software architecture, ensuring that the developed system is **scalable**, **reproducible**, and **optimized** for the high-fidelity reconstruction of monocular endoscopic surgical scenes.

4.1 System Architecture

To address the problem of deformable 3D reconstruction from monocular endoscopic videos, this work adopts a modular architecture that transforms surgical data into optimized 3D representations. This approach is divided into two main stages: the first stage involves processing the monocular endoscopic video to generate a suitable dataset, while the second stage implements InDeform3DGS to obtain the Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting.

The first stage, illustrated in Figure 3.3, details the dataset preparation workflow. The second stage, presented in Figure 4.1, outlines the process for generating the Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting, utilizing the following inputs:

- Dehazed monocular endoscopic video
- Depth estimation of the dehazed video
- Segmentation masks of surgical tools
- Inpainted monocular endoscopic video
- Depth estimation of the inpainted video
- Camera pose estimation of the monocular endoscopic video

This chapter provides a detailed overview of the methodology for obtaining these inputs, along with the integration of InDeform3DGS and its role in the reconstruction of surgical scenes.

It is important to highlight that the primary contribution of InDeform3DGS lies within the Model Optimization stage (fig. 4.1). Nevertheless, the dataset preparation pipeline, initiated from the monocular endoscopic video, remains a fundamental aspect of this work.

Figure 4.1 System architecture of InDeform3DGS.

4.2 System Setup and Execution Workflow

The system is developed and tested on **Ubuntu 22.04.05 LTS**. All core libraries and frameworks required for this project are documented in the *Core Libraries and Frameworks* section. Detailed installation instructions are available in the official GitHub repository’s `README.md` file. Installing these libraries and dependencies enables the execution of all core modules, which are described in detail in the following subsections.

In the final part of the *System Development* section, the integration of all modules is presented, along with Figure 4.17, which illustrates the complete directory structure and key files required for project execution. Among these files, the primary script `main.py` is located in the `src/` directory. This script supports modular execution through the `--stages` argument, allowing users to run individual modules separately as described in the following sections. To run specific pipeline stages using the `--stages` argument:

```
python src/main.py --stages dehazing,segmentation,inpainting,...
```

While the pipeline supports fully automated execution (omitting `--stages`), modular execution is recommended for initial validation. This allows inspection of intermediate results in `data/intermediate/` after each stage, ensuring proper dataset preparation

before initiating the 3D reconstruction phase. To initiate the **Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting for Monocular Endoscopic Video Reconstruction of Surgical Scenes**, the user only needs to place the monocular endoscopic video in the `data/input/` directory and execute the `main.py` script to sequentially process each stage.

With the system setup ready, the implementation details of each **core module** and their respective improvements are described in the following sections. As an introduction to the subsequent exposition, Figure 4.2 provides a visual overview of the enhancements integrated into each module.

Figure 4.2 Overview of the implemented improvements in the core modules.

4.2.1 Dehazed Module

The first component to describe in terms of its development and optimization corresponds to the video dehazing process, which was previously selected to employ the *Dark Channel Prior (DCP)* combined with the *Guided Filter*. For this purpose, a GitHub repository was utilized to obtain the Guided Filter implementation (Babu 2023), and custom code was developed to integrate DCP with Transmission Map Refinement using the Guided Filter.

The implemented code is available on the official GitHub repository for this work in the script `dehaze_video.py`. This script includes the DCP dehazing algorithm integrated with interactive controls via `tkinter`, enabling real-time adjustment of the following parameters:

1. **Dehaze Intensity (ω)**: Controls the haze removal intensity. Higher values result in stronger haze reduction but may degrade fine image details.
2. **Detail Preservation Threshold (T_0)**: Defines the minimum transmission threshold to preserve details in low-visibility regions. Larger values retain more details, while smaller values may introduce blurring.
3. **Dark Channel Radius**: Specifies the window radius for dark channel computation. Larger values improve haze estimation accuracy at the cost of increased computational time.

4. **Kernel Size (r):** Determines the Gaussian filter size for smoothing the transmission map. Larger kernels reduce visual artifacts but may compromise sharpness.
5. **Contrast (α):** Adjusts the output image contrast. Higher values enhance anatomical structure visibility.
6. **Brightness (β):** Modifies the output image brightness. Elevated values compensate for luminance loss in processed frames.

Figure 4.3 displays the interactive interface for parameter tuning, enabling real-time comparison between original and dehazed images. After parameter optimization, the dehazing process can be reapplied with user-tuned settings to generate the full dehazed video sequence.

Figure 4.3 Interactive user interface for parameter tuning in the *dehazing* process. The interface allows real-time adjustment of parameters including haze removal intensity (Ω), detail preservation threshold (T_0), dark channel radius, kernel size, contrast (α), and brightness (β). The left panel displays the original frame, while the right panel shows the processed output with adjusted parameters.

As outlined in the *Methodology* section, the absence of a dedicated dataset necessitated the use of the following metrics to evaluate dehazing quality:

1. **Entropy:** Measures the information content of an image based on pixel intensity distribution. Higher entropy values indicate greater visible details and improved image recovery (Patel 2016).

Formula:

$$H(I) = - \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} p(i) \log_2 p(i) \quad (4.1)$$

where:

- L : Number of intensity levels (e.g., 256 for 8-bit images)
- $p(i)$: Probability of a pixel having intensity i

2. **Laplacian Variance:** Quantifies image sharpness by evaluating edge and fine-detail presence. Higher variance corresponds to better focus (Koley, Roy, and Dhar 2021).

Formula:

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{x=1}^M \sum_{y=1}^N (L(x, y) - \mu)^2 \quad (4.2)$$

where:

- $L(x, y)$: Laplacian-filtered image
- μ : Mean value of the Laplacian output
- M, N : Image dimensions

3. **Dark Channel Score (DCS):** Estimates residual haze using the observation that haze-free natural images contain regions with near-zero values in at least one RGB channel. Lower DCS indicates better haze removal (He, Sun, and Tang 2009).

Formula:

$$D(x, y) = \min_{c \in \{R, G, B\}} I_c(x, y) \quad (4.3)$$

The average dark channel score is computed as:

$$\text{DCS} = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{x=1}^M \sum_{y=1}^N D(x, y) \quad (4.4)$$

where:

- $D(x, y)$: Dark channel value (minimum across RGB channels)
- M, N : Image dimensions

The selection of frames was based on choosing the haziest moment from the monocular endoscopic video and a random haze-free moment to evaluate whether the same parameter values improved the proposed metrics. The dehazing parameters were set to (100, 62, 5, 31, 140, 20), ordered according to the previously introduced parameter sequence. Results are visualized in Fig. 4.4.

Qualitatively, the processed images exhibit significant improvements in the visibility and clarity of anatomical structures within the surgical scene. In Figs. 4.4b and 4.4d, a marked increase in sharpness is observed, enhancing the definition of surgical tool edges

and surrounding anatomical features. The contrast improvement facilitates tissue differentiation, highlighting regions previously obscured by haze.

It is important to highlight the issue of changes in color tone, which results in a more contrasted and saturated appearance. This alteration could potentially impact the visual perception of healthcare professionals, as an excessively contrasted coloration may not accurately represent the actual characteristics of the tissues.

(a) Frame 81: Original monocular endoscopic image capturing a surgical scene with surgical tools.

(b) Frame 81 (Dehazed): Enhanced version of the original endoscopic image after applying the dehazing algorithm, improving contrast and clarity.

(c) Frame 143: Original endoscopic image affected by haze, causing reduced visibility of surgical tools and anatomical structures.

(d) Frame 143 (Dehazed): Processed image after dehazing, revealing previously occluded details and enhancing the differentiation of surgical instruments.

Figure 4.4 Comparison of original and dehazed monocular endoscopic images. The dehazing process enhances contrast, sharpness, and visibility, improving the identification of surgical tools and anatomical structures.

On the other hand, Table 4.1 summarizes the numerical results of the three proposed metrics. The analysis confirms visual quality improvements:

- Entropy increased by 3.19% (Frame 81) and 7.74% (Frame 143), indicating enhanced detail recovery.
- Laplacian Variance rose by 113.76% (Frame 81) and 113.57% (Frame 143), reflecting sharper edges.
- Dark Channel Score (DCS) decreased by 32.06% and 38.07%, demonstrating effective haze reduction.

These quantitative results, alongside qualitative observations, validate the algorithm’s success in improving image visibility and fidelity.

Tabla 4.1 Evaluation of quality metrics for images before and after dehazing.

Frame ID	Entropy	Laplacian Variance	Dark Channel Score
81 (dehazed)	7.1495	895.5128	35.2127
81 (original)	6.9283	418.8667	51.8334
143 (dehazed)	6.8889	982.1366	41.4988
143 (original)	6.3946	459.9276	67.0459

4.2.2 Feature Detection Module

The next component to be described is the surgical tool detection module for monocular endoscopic videos. As outlined in the previous section, the YOLOv11 model is utilized for this task. The primary goal is to achieve the highest possible detection accuracy, which will subsequently enable the creation of tool masks for inpainting in the monocular endoscopic video and for training the Deformable 3DGS.

To accomplish this, a script named `yolov11_train_optimized.py` is employed, leveraging the `optuna` library for hyperparameter optimization before conducting the final training to obtain the optimal YOLOv11 model. Optuna employs a Bayesian Optimization approach, which efficiently explores the hyperparameter space through an iterative, model-guided search process. This method relies on an acquisition function that balances the exploration of new configurations with the exploitation of those that have demonstrated promising results. By doing so, Optuna adaptively adjusts hyperparameters, prioritizing high-potential configurations and significantly reducing search time compared to traditional methods like *Grid Search* or *Random Search*.

In practice, Optuna implements the Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) method, a Bayesian optimization variant that models hyperparameter distributions using density estimates. Unlike traditional global distribution methods, TPE divides the search space into two probabilistic distributions:

- $l(x)$: Represents hyperparameter values that have shown superior performance, i.e., with a loss below a specified threshold.
- $g(x)$: Represents hyperparameter values with inferior performance, i.e., with a loss above the threshold.

The next set of hyperparameters to evaluate is selected by maximizing the probability ratio between both distributions, according to the following expression:

$$x^* = \arg \max \frac{l(x)}{g(x)}$$

This strategy accelerates the identification of optimal configurations by focusing on promising regions of the hyperparameter space and avoiding unnecessary exploration.

Additionally, Optuna incorporates a pruning mechanism, which allows for early stopping of less promising trials based on the intermediate performance obtained in each iteration. This pruning mechanism contributes to a significant reduction in computation time by avoiding the complete execution of suboptimal configurations, focusing on those hyperparameter combinations that maximize the objective metric. Optuna provides several pruning methods, with the most commonly used being the **Median Pruner**, which compares the performance of the current trial with the median of previous trials and stops those whose improvement is below the median, thus optimizing computational resources. The implementation of this pruning mechanism can be visualized in the training script.

The hyperparameters optimized during training include:

- **Number of epochs (epochs):** Defines the number of iterations over the training dataset. A range between 50 and 200 epochs is established, allowing for the exploration of configurations that balance model convergence and the risk of overfitting.
- **Batch size (batch size):** Specifies the number of samples processed simultaneously in each iteration. A range of 2 to 8 is defined to avoid GPU memory exhaustion and maintain a stable learning rate.
- **Image size (imgsz):** Determines the resolution of the input images, affecting both accuracy and computational performance. The selected values (480 and 640 pixels) allow for a balance between prediction quality and processing efficiency.
- **Data augmentation parameters:** Techniques that improve model generalization by applying transformations to the training images. The ranges for each parameter have been selected to provide sufficient variability without altering the semantics of the original images:
 - **Rotation (degrees):** A range between 0 and 45 degrees is established to allow for small angular variations without excessively distorting the appearance of surgical tools.
 - **Translation (translate):** A range between 0.0 and 0.5 is defined, allowing for controlled displacements that simulate variations in camera position.
 - **Scaling (scale):** With a range of 0.1 to 1.0, it allows for modifying the image size while preserving the aspect ratio, improving robustness to different camera distances.
 - **Shearing (shear):** A range between 0 and 10 degrees is allowed, introducing image deformations that can help improve the model's ability to detect tools from unconventional angles.

- **Perspective (perspective)**: A range between 0.0 and 0.001 is established to simulate small perspective variations without compromising visual coherence.
- **Vertical and horizontal flipping (flipud, fliplr)**: With values in the range of 0.0 to 1.0, complete image inversion is allowed, helping the model to be invariant to common symmetries in surgical scenes.
- **Mosaicing (mosaic)**: A range of 0.0 to 1.0 is established, combining multiple images into one to improve dataset diversity.
- **Image mixing (mixup)**: With a range of 0.0 to 1.0, it allows for overlapping images, increasing scene complexity to improve model generalization.

Optuna optimizes the aforementioned hyperparameters based on the mean average precision metric (mAP@[0.50:0.95]), which measures the model’s performance in object detection at different overlap thresholds between predictions and ground truth, with Intersection over Union (IoU) values ranging from 0.50 to 0.95 in increments of 0.05.

Once the optimization process is completed, the best hyperparameters obtained are used to perform a final training of the model to obtain the final model to be used.

The training process was conducted using the parameter ranges outlined earlier, with a total of 20 trials. The dataset, sourced from Roboflow, consists of surgical scenes from laparoscopic procedures. It includes 1,169 images, divided into three subsets: 948 images for training, 133 for validation, and 88 for testing. In percentage terms, the training set accounts for approximately 81.1% of the total images, the validation set for 11.4%, and the test set for 7.5%.

While the data split follows a standard deep learning approach, the dataset’s relatively small size may limit the model’s ability to generalize to new scenarios. Additionally, the effective number of images used in training may be even smaller because the original dataset contains seven distinct classes: Allis, Bag, Cautery, Forceps, Gallbladder, Liver, and Suction. However, this study focuses solely on detecting the surgical tools of interest—Cautery, Forceps, and Suction—which further diminishes the amount of relevant data. This limitation in data quantity reinforces the need to apply data augmentation techniques to mitigate overfitting and improve the model’s ability to correctly detect surgical instruments in different scenarios.

The evolution of the mean average precision metric (mAP@[0.50:0.95]) across the 20 trials is illustrated in Figure 4.5. The graph shows a general upward trend, indicating steady improvement in the target metric as different hyperparameter configurations are explored. Early trials exhibit rapid progress, suggesting that the initial configurations were far from optimal. From trial 10 onward, the metric stabilizes with minor fluctuations, indicating that the optimization algorithm has identified promising configurations. The highest value of 0.752 is achieved in trial 11, representing the best combination of parameters found at that stage. However, temporary declines in the metric, such as those

observed in trials 2 and 8, highlight the exploration of suboptimal configurations. Overall, the optimization process successfully balances exploration and exploitation, identifying a set of hyperparameters that maximizes model performance.

Figure 4.5 Evolution of model performance (mAP@[0.50:0.95]) during hyperparameter optimization with Optuna over 20 trials. The graph illustrates the trend of improvement in model accuracy as different hyperparameter combinations are explored.

Additionally, the relative importance of the hyperparameters is depicted in Figure 4.6. The results reveal that translation (translate) and shearing (shear) are the most influential factors, representing 25% and 23% of the total importance, respectively. This suggests that the model's ability to adapt to positional variations of objects within the frame is critical for improving detection accuracy.

Next, in third place, the image size (imgsz) with 20% importance indicates that the input resolution has a significant impact on the model's ability to capture essential details of surgical tools, balancing precision and computational efficiency.

The hsv_v parameter, which controls brightness variation in the data augmentation transformation, has a moderate impact (12%), indicating that variability in lighting influences the model's robustness. Other parameters such as scale and vertical flipping (flipud) have a lesser impact, suggesting that the network is less sensitive to these changes.

Finally, parameters such as the number of epochs (epochs) and batch size (batch_size) have minimal influence, implying that the model converges efficiently with the selected values and that optimizing these parameters does not have a critical impact on the performance metric.

Figure 4.6 Relative importance of hyperparameters on the performance of the YOLOv11 model during optimization. The hyperparameters *translate*, *shear*, and *imgsiz* have the greatest impact on the mean average precision metric ($\mathbf{mAP@[0.50:0.95]}$), while other parameters such as *batch size* and *fliplr* show minimal influence.

The best hyperparameters, corresponding to trial 11 of the optimization process, are summarized in Table 4.2.

Tabla 4.2 Best hyperparameters obtained after 20 trials of optimization. Corresponding to trial 11.

Hyperparameter	Value
Epochs	148
Image Size (imgsiz)	640
Batch Size	2
HSV Hue (hsv_h)	0.0998
HSV Saturation (hsv_s)	0.5794
HSV Value (hsv_v)	0.6414
Rotation (degrees)	30
Translation (translate)	0.4958
Scale	0.1018
Shear	10
Perspective	0.00019
Flip Up-Down (flipud)	0.3899
Flip Left-Right (fliplr)	0.9775
Mosaic	0.0044
Mixup	0.3954

Using the optimized hyperparameters, the model is integrated into the pipeline. The

training performance of this model is evaluated through the graphs shown in Figure 4.7, which provide insights into the following aspects:

1. **F1-Confidence Curve:** Demonstrates how the F1-score, which represents the balance between precision and recall, varies depending on different confidence thresholds of the model (the confidence threshold with which the model classifies an instance as belonging to a specific class). This allows evaluating the overall classification performance at different levels of certainty in the predictions. Key observations from Figure 4.7a include:
 - The maximum F1-score for all classes is reached at a confidence threshold of 0.601, with a value of 0.84, indicating that this is the optimal operating point for the model.
 - The *Cautery* class outperforms others with consistently higher F1-scores, indicating superior detection reliability.
 - The *Forceps* class shows reduced performance, with a steeper curve decline, reflecting detection challenges.
 - As the confidence threshold increases, the F1-score initially rises, reaching a maximum before decreasing sharply, highlighting the need for a balanced threshold.
 - The combined curve for all classes reflects a general trend of the model, suggesting that excessively high confidence thresholds may reduce detection recall.
2. **Precision-Confidence Curve:** Shows the relationship between the model's precision and the confidence level of the predictions. It is worth noting that precision (*precision*) is defined as the proportion of true positives relative to the total positive predictions made by the model. This curve allows evaluating the balance between precision and confidence, providing key information for selecting an optimal threshold that maximizes precision. In Figure 4.7b, the following conclusions are drawn:
 - The overall model precision (thick blue line) reaches a maximum value of 1.00 at a confidence level of 0.94, indicating excellent performance in terms of precision when high confidence thresholds are adopted.
 - The *Suction* class exhibits significantly higher precision compared to the other classes across almost all confidence levels, suggesting that the model performs better in detecting this particular surgical tool.
 - The *Cautery* and *Forceps* classes, with *Forceps* slightly inferior, show a similar trend, with a progressive increase in precision as confidence increases, but with slightly lower precision values compared to the *Suction* class.

- At low confidence levels, precision is lower due to the presence of false positives, indicating that the model generates more incorrect predictions in these cases.
- As the confidence threshold increases, precision improves notably, demonstrating that the model can make more secure and precise predictions when higher confidence in classification is required.
- The choice of the optimal confidence threshold depends on the required balance between precision and coverage, where higher values ensure fewer false positives at the cost of potentially missing some relevant objects.

3. **Precision-Recall Curve:** Shows the relationship between precision and recall (the proportion of true positives detected relative to the total actual positives in the data). In Figure 4.7c, the following conclusions are drawn:

- The mAP@0.5 metric for all combined classes is **0.886**, indicating high overall model performance in detecting surgical tools.
- The *Cautery* class shows the best performance with a maximum precision of **0.965**, displaying a more stable curve and maintaining high precision levels even at high recall values. This suggests that the model detects this tool with great accuracy and few false positives.
- The precision of the *Suction* class shows an abrupt decline at a recall of 0.7, followed by stabilization at 0.5 precision, suggesting a limitation in the model's ability to correctly differentiate this tool as the number of detections increases. This behavior may be attributed to an imbalance in the data distribution, as the number of Suction instances in the dataset is lower compared to other classes, creating a bias in training.
- The *Forceps* class shows the lowest precision among the analyzed classes, reaching a value of **0.838**. Its curve exhibits a more pronounced drop in precision as recall increases, indicating a higher presence of false positives or lower confidence in detections.
- Precision decreases drastically at high recall values, which is expected due to the inclusion of more true positives but also more false positives, negatively affecting the model's overall precision.
- The thick blue curve represents the general behavior of the model considering all classes, showing a favorable trend in the mid-range of recall but a sharp decline at high values, which is related to the issue of having a small dataset.

4. **Recall-Confidence Curve:** Shows how recall varies depending on the confidence threshold applied to the model. In Figure 4.7d, the following conclusions are drawn:

- The **recall** metric for all combined classes is **0.96** at a low confidence threshold, indicating that the model can detect most surgical tools present in the images.
- The *Cautery* class shows outstanding performance, maintaining a recall value close to 1.0 for most of the confidence range. However, a notable decline is observed starting at a confidence threshold of 0.9, suggesting that as the decision threshold increases, detections with lower confidence scores are discarded, reducing the number of true positives detected.
- The *Forceps* class performs worse compared to the Cautery class, with a more pronounced downward trend as the confidence threshold increases. This indicates that the model may be losing detections of this tool under stricter threshold configurations.
- The *Suction* class exhibits a distinctive behavior compared to the other classes. From a confidence threshold of **0.0** to approximately **0.6**, recall remains stable at **0.7**, indicating that the model detects this tool consistently in this confidence range. However, starting at a threshold of **0.6**, a sharp decline in recall is observed, suggesting that many detections with lower confidence are being eliminated. This phenomenon may be attributed to an uneven distribution of confidence scores assigned to the Suction class. It is possible that most detections of this class have relatively low confidence scores, causing a stricter threshold to discard a large number of true positives. Additionally, this trend may be related to the lower representation of Suction in the dataset, preventing the model from learning robust distinctive features for this category and, consequently, assigning lower confidence scores to its predictions.
- The overall curve shows that a low confidence threshold allows for high recall, but this may introduce false positives. As the confidence threshold increases, recall gradually decreases, indicating a trade-off between sensitivity and precision.

Additionally, two confusion matrices are analyzed:

1. **Confusion Matrix:** Shows the absolute number of correct and incorrect predictions made by the model for each class, comparing true labels with predicted labels. In Figure 4.8a, the following conclusions are drawn:

- The **Cautery** class shows high performance, with **73 correct predictions** and only **2 instances misclassified** as Forceps and 2 as Suction. However, there are **28 cases classified as Background**, suggesting that some surgical tools may be confused with the background under certain conditions.

Figure 4.7 Evaluation curves of the YOLOv11 model trained for surgical tool detection. The F1, precision, and recall metrics are analyzed as a function of the confidence threshold, providing a detailed view of the model’s performance in classifying detected objects.

- The **Forceps** class shows solid detection with **75 correct predictions**, but it has a significant issue of confusion with the background (**56 instances classified as Background**). This indicates that, in some cases, the tool may not be detected correctly, possibly due to its color, shape, or lighting in the images.
- The **Suction** class has a very low number of instances in the dataset, with only **5 correct detections**. This suggests that the model has not been sufficiently exposed to representative examples of this tool, which may affect its ability to generalize and detect reliably.
- The **Background** category has been misclassified in **8 instances as Forceps**, which could indicate that certain background elements have visual characteristics similar to this tool, leading the model to make errors in its predictions.

2. **Normalized Confusion Matrix:** Shows the confusion matrix where the values have been scaled between 0 and 1 by dividing each cell by the total number of actual instances of the corresponding class. In Figure 4.8b, the following conclusions are drawn:

- The **Cautery** class has **100% precision** in its correct predictions, although it shows a small **2% confusion with Forceps**. Additionally, **29% of Suction tools** have been incorrectly classified as Cautery, indicating a possible visual similarity between these classes.
- The **Forceps** class maintains **88% precision**, but it suffers from **67% confusion with the Background**, reinforcing the hypothesis that the model may have difficulties differentiating certain surgical objects from the image background.
- The **Suction** class achieves **71% precision**, but its low representation in the dataset may be the main cause of its lower performance, as the model has been trained with a limited number of examples.
- The **Background** class has **9% confusion with Forceps**, suggesting that in some images, surgical instruments may not be clearly segmented from the background, affecting detection quality.

Through the evaluation curves, the optimal confidence threshold has been determined to be 0.6, ensuring an appropriate balance between precision and recall. It has been observed that the Cautery class shows superior performance, with high F1-score values and consistent precision across different confidence thresholds. On the other hand, the Forceps class exhibits a progressive decline in precision and recall as the confidence threshold increases, suggesting difficulties in consistent detection. The Suction class demonstrates a

(a) Confusion matrix of the YOLOv11 model in surgical tool detection, showing the absolute number of correct and incorrect predictions for each class. (b) Normalized confusion matrix of the YOLOv11 model, representing the proportions of correct and incorrect predictions per class, allowing evaluation of the model's performance regardless of the number of instances per class.

Figure 4.8 Comparison between the absolute confusion matrix and the normalized confusion matrix of the YOLOv11 model in detecting surgical tools in endoscopic images.

limitation in the number of representative examples in the dataset, leading to an abrupt drop in precision and recall at certain thresholds. Finally, the confusion matrix confirms these findings, showing that most prediction errors are due to confusion with the background or the scarcity of instances of certain classes in the training set.

In Figure 4.9, two validation examples are shown. Each image displays the validation labels on the left and the predicted labels on the right. In Figure 4.9a, the model has correctly detected the Cautery surgical tool with a high confidence of 0.9, indicating that the model has adequately learned the distinctive visual features of this tool. However, in Figure 4.9b, prediction errors are evident, reflecting some of the issues discussed in the confusion matrix and evaluation curve analysis.

One of the main problems observed is the confusion between the background and the Forceps class, with an incorrect prediction of Forceps with a confidence of 0.7. This error is attributed to the similarity in texture and color between the background and the surgical tool, suggesting that the model has not sufficiently learned to differentiate these elements under varying lighting conditions.

Additionally, a phenomenon of prediction accumulation for the Cautery class is observed, where the model generates four overlapping predictions for the same tool with different confidence levels. This behavior may be due to how the model handles bounding box generation, specifically deficiencies in the Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) process. When NMS is not well-tuned, the model may generate multiple detections for the same object at slightly different positions, rather than merging them into a single prediction with the highest confidence. This may be related to a suboptimal configuration of IoU

(Intersection over Union) thresholds in post-processing, causing multiple bounding boxes to be retained instead of being eliminated.

(a) Comparison between validation labels (left) and YOLOv11 model predictions (right). A correct detection of the Cautery tool with a high confidence of 0.9 is observed.

(b) Comparison between validation labels (left) and YOLOv11 model predictions (right). Errors in detection are evident, including confusion of the background with Forceps and accumulation of multiple predictions for Cautery.

Figure 4.9 Examples of YOLOv11 model detection in endoscopic images. The left side shows images with validation labels, and the right side shows images with model predictions. Cases of correct detection, classification errors, and prediction accumulation are highlighted.

With the trained model and its presented issues, the script `detection_stage.py` is used in the pipeline. In this script, an initial approach to the redundancy problem is implemented using a Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) function. First, predictions are sorted in descending order of confidence. Then, the detection with the highest confidence is selected and compared with the remaining ones using the Intersection over Union (IoU) metric. IoU is calculated as the ratio of the overlapping area of two boxes to the total combined area of both. If the IoU between two boxes exceeds a predefined threshold (0.5 by default), the prediction with lower confidence is discarded. This process is repeated until no more predictions remain to be evaluated, ensuring that only the most significant detections are retained, reducing false positives and improving model precision.

In addition to NMS, this code also applies a **dilation factor** to expand the detection boxes. This strategy is implemented because, in some cases, the bounding boxes generated by the model may be too small compared to the detected surgical tool, which could affect the quality of subsequent segmentation. To address this, the size of each bbox is recalculated by proportionally increasing its dimensions around its center, ensuring that the region of interest better captures the actual extent of the object.

This adjustment does not pose a problem for integration with SAM2, as this model can **correctly interpret the intention of the bbox**, even if it is larger than the tool

itself. SAM2 is not limited to the exact edges of the detection box but uses the bounded region as an indication of where to center its segmentation.

Furthermore, to improve system robustness and minimize false positives, a detailed approach is implemented in the segmentation module. The combination of these strategies allows for the generation of precise masks of surgical tools, optimizing the detection and segmentation of objects of interest.

4.2.3 Image Segmentation Module

For surgical tool segmentation in monocular endoscopic videos, the SAM2 (Segment Anything Model v2) is utilized. As outlined in the *Methodology* section, this approach **reduces dependency on the YOLOv11 detection model**, which occasionally produces intermittent failures such as object omissions in certain frames. This implementation is available in the official GitHub repository for this work in the script `segmentation_stage.py`.

To address the YOLOv11 model’s intermittent bounding box predictions, Algorithm 2 is implemented. This algorithm analyzes detection continuity across a temporal window of four consecutive frames, ensuring an object is considered valid only if it appears in at least three frames with sufficient area overlap via the *Intersection over Union (IoU)* metric. The IoU quantifies the relationship between the intersection and union of predicted and ground-truth pixel sets, calculated as:

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} \quad (4.5)$$

where:

- A : Area of the object in the *ground truth* image (reference truth).
- B : Area predicted by the model.
- $A \cap B$: Intersection of both areas (correctly segmented pixels).
- $A \cup B$: Total union of both areas (all pixels belonging to the object in either area).

This validation mechanism filters out false or inconsistent detections, minimizing reliance on individual unreliable predictions. Furthermore, segmentation is performed in batches of 50 frames—a strategy that optimizes computational performance and enables bounding box validation at the start of each batch rather than only at the video’s beginning. This mitigates over-reliance on SAM2’s tracking, which is critical in surgical scenarios where tools may exit the frame for several consecutive frames or re-enter with altered geometry (e.g., new tools). **Batch processing** allows SAM2 to periodically re-define valid bounding boxes, improving detection accuracy for new or re-entered tools.

A potential limitation is acknowledged: if a new tool appears mid-batch, SAM2 may fail to segment it correctly due to the absence of valid bounding box updates during

batch processing. However, this error is probabilistic and can be mitigated by adjusting the batch size, thereby balancing bounding box update frequency.

Algorithm 2 Temporal Consistency-Based Bounding Box Segmentation Process

```
1: Process Initialization
2: 1. Bounding Box Extraction
3: Read bounding box file line-by-line and store boxes in a dictionary.
4: 2. Temporal Consistency Evaluation
5: for each current frame in the video do
6:   Extract bounding boxes from the current frame and the next 3 frames.
7:   for each bounding box pair in consecutive frames do
8:     Compute overlap using IoU.
9:     if  $\text{IoU} > 0.7$  then
10:      Mark the box as consistent.
11:    end if
12:  end for
13:  if box appears in at least 3 of 4 frames then
14:    Accept the box as valid.
15:  else
16:    Discard the box due to inconsistency.
17:  end if
18: end for
19: 3. Inconsistent Bounding Box Handling
20: if no consistent bounding boxes are found then
21:   Skip the current frame.
22:   Log a warning and proceed to the next frame.
23:   No segmentation is performed for this frame.
24: end if
25: 4. Batch Segmentation Processing
26: Split the video into batches of 50 frames.
27: for each batch of frames do
28:   Step 2: Temporal Consistency Evaluation
29:   if valid bounding boxes are detected then
30:     Propagate segmentation to all batch frames.
31:   else
32:     Step 3: Inconsistent Bounding Box Handling
33:   end if
34: end for
35: Process Termination
36: Save the segmented video and generated masks.
```

To validate the proposed algorithm using SAM2, the segmentation process was applied

to seven distinct surgical scenes provided by Keio University, demonstrating accurate tool segmentation. Specifically, Fig. 4.10 illustrates a sequence of frames spaced 10 frames apart, showcasing SAM2's ability to consistently track and segment objects. This effectively resolves the issue highlighted in Fig. 3.8. Additionally, a functionality was implemented in the code to indicate the watermark's location and segment it for subsequent inpainting, and to ensure the Deformable 3DGS is not trained with watermark artifacts.

Figure 4.10 Sequence of the first surgical scene demonstrating effective tracking and segmentation of surgical tools by the SAM2 model. The images showcase consistent segmentation performance across frames, with the model also identifying the watermark present in the scene.

The remaining six surgical scenes are shown in Fig. 4.11, where tools are accurately segmented. However, it is noted that a surgical gauze of Fig. 4.11 remains unsegmented. This limitation arises due to the lack of training data for this specific tool type and the surgical gauze in the YOLOv11 model.

4.2.4 Video Inpainting Module

As outlined in the *Methodology* section, the STTN model is employed for inpainting segmented surgical tools and watermarks, where applicable. The corresponding implementation is available in the official GitHub repository under the script `inpainting_stage.py`.

The code incorporates several enhancements beyond a basic STTN implementation, which would typically involve inputting a video and corresponding masks for inpainting, performing inference with the STTN model, and denormalizing the output to produce the final inpainted video. These enhancements significantly improve the model's performance and adaptability.

A key feature is the introduction of tunable parameters to optimize inpainting results. In addition to selecting the processing device (CPU or a specific GPU), the following parameters can be configured:

1. **width and height:** Used to resize frames before processing by the model. Defaulting to 432 x 240, this parameter aligns with the STTN model's training resolution.

(a) Frame from the second surgical scene with correctly segmented surgical tools.

(b) Frame from the third surgical scene with correctly segmented surgical tools.

(c) Frame from the fourth surgical scene with correctly segmented surgical tools.

(d) Frame from the fifth surgical scene with correctly segmented surgical tools. The surgical gauze remains unsegmented.

(e) Frame from the sixth surgical scene with correctly segmented surgical tools.

(f) Frame from the seventh surgical scene with correctly segmented surgical tools.

Figure 4.11 Examples of surgical tool segmentation in different surgical scenes. The images demonstrate successful segmentation of instruments across multiple surgical scenes, highlighting the performance of the segmentation model.

It is worth noting that a subsequent rescaling is also applied to restore the original dimensions.

2. **neighbor_stride**: Specifies the number of neighboring frames to consider for providing context to complete the current image. Since surgical scenes can have abrupt changes due to tool-tissue interactions such as cutting, pulling, and others, this is set to 5 frames.
3. **ref_length**: Defines the spacing between reference frames selected to improve global video coherence. It is used in the reference function to obtain distant frames from the current one. This parameter is set to 10 frames by default, for the same reason mentioned for **neighbor_stride**.
4. **anchor_stride**: Defines the frequency at which anchor frames are selected as fixed reference points in the inpainting process, ensuring that these specific frames are always considered, even if they are not within the immediate neighbors or distant temporal references. This parameter is useful in scenarios where the scene remains relatively constant but has recurring occlusions or intermittent object movements, ensuring a stable visual reference over time.
5. **enable_blending**: Enables blending of inpainted frames to smooth transitions.

These parameters can be adjusted based on the specific surgical scene. For Scene 1 (Figure 4.10), tuning `anchor_stride` yields measurable differences in the following metrics, applied exclusively to inpainted regions:

1. **CX Loss (Contextual Loss):** Measures the perceptual similarity between the reconstructed image and its surrounding context.
 - **Interpretation:** Lower values indicate that the generated image is perceptually similar to the context.
2. **LPIPS (Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity):** Measures perceptual similarity using features extracted from pre-trained neural networks.
 - **Interpretation:** Lower values indicate greater perceptual similarity.
3. **Patch Coherence:** Evaluates the coherence of generated textures in the reconstructed regions.
 - **Interpretation:** Higher values indicate better texture coherence.

Table 4.3 illustrates the impact of varying `anchor_stride` on these metrics. While differences are minimal, an `anchor_stride` of 5 achieves the optimal balance across all metrics.

Table 4.3 Evaluation of quality metrics for different values of anchor stride.

Anchor Stride	CX Loss	LPIPS	Patch Coherence
5	5.291	0.043	99.460
10	5.292	0.044	99.455
15	5.291	0.044	99.450
20	5.292	0.044	99.455
25	5.292	0.044	99.458

Another significant improvement is the integration of batch processing, which maximizes GPU parallelism to reduce processing time and minimize overhead from repeated model calls. By preprocessing frames collectively into a single tensor, the implementation leverages cache memory and computational resources more effectively, ensuring smoother and more efficient execution.

Table 4.4 compares batch and individual processing, highlighting substantial gains in computational efficiency. Batch processing reduces total processing time by 22.46%, from 0.236 seconds (individual) to 0.183 seconds. RAM usage is also optimized by 82.42%, with batch processing consuming only 8.97 MB compared to 51.00 MB for individual processing. Similarly, GPU memory usage peaks at 144.91 MB for batch processing—a 35.57% reduction from the 224.82 MB peak in individual processing. These optimizations are

achieved without sacrificing inpainting quality, as CX Loss, LPIPS, and Patch Coherence remain constant, confirming that the enhanced efficiency does not compromise the final output.

Tabla 4.4 Evaluation of quality metrics for batch and individual processing.

Processing Type	Time (s)	RAM (MB)	GPU Peak (MB)	CX Loss	LPIPS	Patch Coh.
Batch Processing	0.183	8.97	144.91	5.292	0.044	99.475
Individual Processing	0.236	51.00	224.82	5.292	0.044	99.475

Figure 4.12 displays the segmentations derived from Figures 4.11, alongside their inpainted results. The inpainted frames exhibit varying levels of accuracy and visual consistency. For instance, in Figure 4.12a, the inpainting algorithm performs well in the region where the surgical tool pulls the tissue, though the upper right area loses some anatomical details, slightly affecting the scene’s realism. Figure 4.12b shows successful inpainting, with the forceps naturally disappearing; however, the reddish area appears darker than its surroundings, making the inpainted region slightly noticeable. Figure 4.12c demonstrates effective reconstruction, with the pulling and cutting actions handled well, revealing previously occluded details clearly. In Figure 4.12d, the inpainting is satisfactory, though the shape of the removed tool remains faintly visible. Figure 4.12e presents a generally well-executed inpainting, but the lower part of the tissue appears darker than expected, suggesting minor blending inconsistencies. Finally, Figure 4.12f shows well-executed inpainting, though the lower part of the forceps retains a darker tone compared to the surrounding tissue.

4.2.5 Depth Estimation Module

The Depth Anything V2 model was selected due to its superiority over alternative approaches as discussed in *Methodology* section. Initially, a version was developed to process frames sequentially, one at a time. However, to optimize the `depth_stage.py` script (available in the official GitHub repository for this work), the batch processing strategy previously employed was adopted. As shown in Table 4.5, significant differences are observed in processing time, RAM usage, and peak GPU memory consumption.

First and foremost, batch processing reduces total execution time by 41.3%, decreasing from 139.90 seconds (individual processing) to 82.06 seconds (batch processing). In terms of RAM usage, the difference is less pronounced, with batch processing consuming 2.2% less memory compared to individual processing (116.81 MB vs. 119.44 MB). On the other hand, peak GPU memory usage exhibits an inverse trend, as batch processing requires 164.8% more memory (5.19 GB vs. 1.96 GB). This increase is primarily due to the

(a) Frame from the second surgical scene with inpainted surgical tools. The inpainting is well-executed in the region where the forceps are pulling the tissue; however, anatomical details are lost in the upper right area.

(b) Frame from the third surgical scene with inpainted surgical tools. The forceps clamping the tissue are naturally removed, but the red region appears darker than its surroundings.

(c) Frame from the fourth surgical scene with inpainted surgical tools. Both the pulling and cutting actions are successfully inpainted, revealing clear anatomical details.

(d) Frame from the fifth surgical scene with inpainted surgical tools. The inpainting is well-executed; however, the outline of the removed tool remains slightly visible.

(e) Frame from the sixth surgical scene with inpainted surgical tools. The result is generally satisfactory, but the lower part of the inpainted tissue remains slightly darker than the surrounding area.

(f) Frame from the seventh surgical scene with inpainted surgical tools. The inpainting is successful, though the lower part of the forceps appears darker compared to the adjacent tissues.

Figure 4.12 Examples of surgical tool inpainting in different surgical scenes. The images demonstrate the effectiveness of the inpainting model in removing surgical instruments.

simultaneous loading of multiple images into the GPU, which enables faster processing at the cost of higher GPU memory demand.

Thus, batch processing offers a notable improvement in temporal efficiency and slight RAM savings, albeit at the expense of significantly higher GPU memory usage. This trade-off must be carefully considered when selecting the processing strategy based on available computational resources.

Tabla 4.5 Comparison of Depth Estimation Performance Using Depth Anything V2 with and without Batch Processing.

Processing Type	Total Time (s)	RAM Usage (MB)	GPU Peak Memory (GB)
Batch Processing	82.06	116.81	5.19
Individual Processing	139.90	119.44	1.96

On the other hand, upon examining the resulting figures (fig. 4.13), it is qualitatively observed that the depth estimation obtained through individual processing demonstrates a better representation of the right region of the image. In this area, a tissue with a distinct texture is more clearly discernible, emerging from the right side, indicating its closer proximity to the camera (fig. 4.13b). This perception of depth is significantly more accurate in the individual processing, providing a more faithful interpretation of the surgical scene.

In contrast, the depth estimation generated through batch processing fails to capture this level of detail with the same precision (fig. 4.13c). The differentiation of depth planes is less evident, suggesting a slight loss of critical spatial information necessary for surgical interpretation.

Therefore, although batch processing offers significant advantages in terms of computational efficiency, reducing execution time by 41.3%, the individual processing approach is preferred due to its superior fidelity in depth estimation.

(a) Original endoscopic frame with inpainted surgical tools. **(b)** Depth estimation using individual processing. **(c)** Depth estimation using batch processing.

Figure 4.13 Comparison of depth estimation results obtained from individual and batch processing methods.

Additionally, when performing depth estimation using individual processing for the other scenes, a correct depth estimation is generally observed for each image (fig. 4.14),

allowing the visualization of anatomical features with high accuracy. However, some inconsistencies can be noted. Specifically, in Figure 4.14h, the central tissue is perceived as the closest object in the depth estimation, while visually it is not, resulting in an inaccurate depth representation. Similarly, in Figure 4.14l, the depth estimation visibly reflects the imperfections introduced by the inpainting process. The inpainting artifacts propagate into the depth estimation, leading to discrepancies in the reconstructed depth map.

Overall, the depth estimation approach works effectively in most cases, accurately capturing the spatial arrangement of surgical elements. However, occasional failures occur, either due to the limitations of the depth estimation model itself or the presence of minor inaccuracies in the inpainted frames, which can mislead the depth estimation network.

Figure 4.14 Comparison of inpainted endoscopic frames and their corresponding depth estimation results across different surgical scenes.

4.2.6 Camera Pose Estimation Module

For this module, camera pose estimation was implemented using the previously presented MonST3R method. Similar to the Depth module, the feasibility of individual processing and batch processing was evaluated.

To enable batch processing, an efficient method was developed to utilize the MonST3R architecture without compromising the final output. Each batch of frames is processed independently, generating a local estimation of the camera pose and intrinsic parameters. Once a batch is processed, the generated information—including the camera trajectory and reconstructed structure—is transferred to the next batch, enabling a smooth and coherent transition between segments. This iterative feedback minimizes error accumulation and ensures global pose estimation consistency throughout the entire video. At the end of the process, results from each batch are combined into a single consolidated file, guaranteeing an output equivalent to individual processing while offering efficient memory management and a significant reduction in computational load.

Table 4.6 provides a comparison between the batch processing approach and individual processing. It is worth noting that a 3-second surgical scene was used for testing due to GPU memory limitations, as the laptop employed had only 8GB of VRAM and operated at a reduced image size of 224x224. According to the author of the official repository, processing their 3-second demo sequence at a 512x512 resolution requires approximately 33GB of VRAM, which would trigger a CUDA Out of Memory (OOM) error if hardware requirements are unmet (Junyi42 2024).

Therefore, the development of the batch processing-based implementation is essential to overcome the CUDA OOM issue, enabling efficient processing of the surgical sequence within the available hardware constraints.

Tabla 4.6 Comparison of Camera Pose Estimation Performance Using MonST3R with and without Batch Processing.

Processing Type	Total Time (s)	RAM Usage (MB)	GPU Peak Memory (MB)
Batch Processing	53.63	2371.20	3466.31
Individual Processing	90.37	4366.32	7120.31

The comparison of camera pose estimation performance using MonST3R between batch and individual processing reveals significant differences in efficiency and resource consumption. In terms of total processing time, batch processing completes the task in 53.63 seconds, whereas individual processing requires 90.37 seconds, representing a 40.64% reduction in execution time when using the batch approach. Regarding memory usage, batch processing consumes 2371.20 MB of RAM compared to 4366.32 MB in individual processing, demonstrating a 45.68% decrease in RAM consumption. This indicates that the batch approach effectively manages memory allocation by processing smaller chunks of data, thereby preventing memory overload and optimizing computational resources.

In contrast, GPU peak memory usage is notably higher in individual processing, reaching 7120.31 MB, compared to 3466.31 MB in individual processing. This represents a

51.34% reduction in GPU memory utilization, showcasing the benefits of distributing the workload over multiple iterations rather than processing the entire sequence at once.

On the other hand, Figure 4.15 presents visualizations of the 3D reconstruction alongside the camera trajectory using the `viser` library. A custom script, available in the official GitHub repository of this work under `pose_visualizer.py`, has been developed to load the trained and visualize the data obtained through the MonST3R method.

It is worth mentioning that the interactive interface exhibits a stable, smooth, and continuous camera movement, indicating an accurate camera pose estimation suitable for the implementation of Deformable 3DGS. Furthermore, it should be noted that a black point cloud can be observed surrounding the three-dimensional scene (fig. 4.15). This phenomenon arises from the presence of black areas in the monocular endoscopic video, which correspond to the endoscopic tube. However, this artifact does not compromise the accuracy of the camera pose estimation, as the reconstruction process effectively focuses on the relevant anatomical structures while disregarding non-informative regions.

(a) Visualization of the 3D point cloud and camera trajectory for the first surgical scene. (b) Visualization of the 3D point cloud and camera trajectory for the third surgical scene. (c) Visualization of the 3D point cloud and camera trajectory for the fourth surgical scene.

Figure 4.15 Visualization of the camera trajectory and 3D point cloud for different surgical scenes using the `viser` library.

4.2.7 Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting Module

Having preprocessed the monocular endoscopic video to comply with the format required by the Deform3DGS algorithm, the selected method is implemented, as detailed in the *Methodology* section. However, within the same *Methodology* section, it is observed that the original method exhibits significant limitations in surgical environments, particularly concerning **prolonged occlusions**, which persist over multiple consecutive frames in the same location. These occlusions degrade the 3D reconstruction quality, as the model cannot accurately infer the geometry of obscured regions.

To address this issue, an extension of the original method, termed **InDeform3DGS**, is developed (fig. 4.1). This extension incorporates *video inpainting* techniques to enhance reconstruction quality. In this approach, an inpainting model is applied to the raw

monocular endoscopic video, visually removing surgical tools present in the scene. The information obtained from this processed video is used to improve the 3D reconstruction, providing a better estimation of areas that remain hidden for prolonged periods in the original video.

For the implementation of this solution, the possibility of directly using the inpainted video as input for the original Deform3DGS code is initially considered (see Fig. 4.16). This requires modifications to the Deform3DGS source code to allow processing of videos without additional masks, as surgical tools have already been removed by the inpainting process. The results obtained with this strategy demonstrate **high fidelity** in scene reconstruction relative to the inpainted video, theoretically enabling the generation of an optimal Deform3DGS model if a perfect inpainting process were available. However, due to the limitations previously discussed in the *Video Inpainting Module* section, the inpainting quality is not entirely accurate, leading to information loss in certain areas of the scene.

To mitigate the shortcomings of the initial approach and maximize the use of available information, **InDeform3DGS** is developed as a hybrid methodology that combines the original video with the inpainted version. This approach leverages the information provided by the inpainted video to complete regions where the original Deform3DGS fails to reconstruct accurately due to prolonged occlusions. Unlike the initial approach, this method utilizes multiple inputs, including the dehazed video, its depth estimation, and the binary masks from the segmentation module discussed earlier (see Fig. 4.16).

InDeform3DGS involves modifications to the Model Optimization component of the original Deform3DGS, as presented in the *Methodology* section within the discussion of its architecture. These modifications include the incorporation of multiple loss functions previously unavailable and unfeasible due to the lack of consideration for the useful information that inpainting of the monocular endoscopic video could provide. These loss functions are outlined below:

1. **Similarity Loss** ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{similarity}}$): The similarity loss measures the difference between the reconstructed region and the corresponding inpainted region, focusing exclusively on surgical tool areas:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{similarity}} = \|(1 - M) \odot \hat{C} - (1 - M) \odot C_{\text{inpainted}}\| \quad (4.6)$$

Where:

- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{similarity}}$: Similarity loss for the tool regions.
- M : Tissue masks. Therefore, $1 - M$ corresponds to the regions where surgical tools are present.
- \hat{C} : Rendered color image generated by the Gaussian Splatting model.

Figure 4.16 Comparison of the modified Deform3DGS approach and the proposed InDeform3DGS method. On the left, the modified Deform3DGS pipeline directly incorporates the inpainted video as input, bypassing the need for segmentation masks. While this approach provides high fidelity to the inpainted video, its performance is constrained by the imperfections inherent to the inpainting process. On the right, the InDeform3DGS approach is visualized, where additional inputs are required, including the dehazed RGB video, its corresponding depth estimation, and segmentation masks of the surgical tools. This method selectively integrates information from the inpainted video to refine regions where Deform3DGS struggles due to persistent occlusions, resulting in a more complete and coherent 3D reconstruction.

- $C_{\text{inpainted}}$: Reference inpainted image from the monocular endoscopic video.

Purpose: Ensures that the reconstructed appearance of tool regions matches the inpainted reference, helping the model handle occluded regions by leveraging the inpainting.

2. **Depth Inpaint Loss ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$):** This loss compares depth maps of tool regions between the reconstructed and inpainted frames:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{depth-inpaint}} = \|(1 - M) \odot \hat{D} - (1 - M) \odot D_{\text{inpainted}}\| \quad (4.7)$$

Where:

- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$: Depth loss for tool regions.
- \hat{D} : Predicted depth map from the model.
- $D_{\text{inpainted}}$: Reference depth map from the inpainted video.

Purpose: Promotes accurate depth reconstruction in occluded regions by aligning the predicted depth with the inpainted reference.

3. **Illumination Loss ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{illumination}}$):** The illumination loss evaluates luminance consistency in the tool regions:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{illumination}} = \|(1 - M) \odot \hat{L} - (1 - M) \odot L_{\text{inpainted}}\| \quad (4.8)$$

Where:

- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{illumination}}$: Illumination loss for tool regions.
- \hat{L} : Luminance of the rendered image, computed as $\hat{L} = 0.299\hat{R} + 0.587\hat{G} + 0.114\hat{B}$.
- $L_{\text{inpainted}}$: Luminance of the inpainted reference image.

Purpose: Ensures consistent lighting in the reconstructed and inpainted tool regions, reducing unrealistic brightness or shadow artifacts in occluded areas. This loss serves as a complement to the Similarity Loss, ensuring that the final reconstruction is not overly constrained by the inpainted image. As discussed in the first approach of the Modified Deform3DGS, certain inpainted images may not perfectly replicate the real scene due to imperfections in the inpainting process. The Illumination Loss compensates for this limitation by providing additional information about realistic brightness and lighting conditions from the inpainted image, which can guide the reconstruction of occluded areas more effectively.

4. **Diversity Loss** ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{diversity}}$): Diversity loss prevents trivial solutions by encouraging variability in reconstructed regions:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{diversity}} = \frac{1}{\text{Var}(\Phi((1 - M) \odot \hat{C}))} \quad (4.9)$$

Where:

- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{diversity}}$: Diversity loss in tool regions.
- Φ : Features extracted by the VGG network from the tool regions. Specifically, the pre-trained **VGG16 model** trained on the **ImageNet dataset** is utilized. The first 23 convolutional layers are selected to capture relevant visual features such as textures, shapes, and patterns that are essential for describing the surgical tool regions. Fully connected layers are excluded as they are used for classification tasks (Simonyan and Zisserman 2015).
- Var : Variance of extracted features; higher variance implies greater diversity.

Purpose: Avoids oversimplification in regions occluded by tools by encouraging diversity in texture and color in reconstructed areas.

5. **Edge-Smoothing Loss** ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$): The edge-smoothing loss ensures smooth transitions between inpainted and non-inpainted regions:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{edge-smoothing}} = \|R_{\text{edge}} \odot \hat{C} - R_{\text{edge}} \odot C_{\text{inpainted}}\| \quad (4.10)$$

Where:

- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$: Loss to smooth transitions at tool edges.
- R_{edge} : Smoothed edge region calculated using Gaussian kernels applied to $1 - M$.

Purpose: Reduces harsh transitions at the boundaries of occluded areas, improving the visual consistency of reconstructed frames.

6. **Temporal Consistency Loss** ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{time-consistency}}$): This loss ensures temporal coherence of reconstructed regions between consecutive frames:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{time-consistency}} = \|(1 - M) \odot \hat{C}_{\text{current}} - (1 - M) \odot \hat{C}_{\text{prev}}\| \quad (4.11)$$

Where:

- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{time-consistency}}$: Temporal consistency loss.
- \hat{C}_{current} : Rendered image of the current frame.

- \hat{C}_{prev} : Rendered image of the previous frame.

Purpose: Prevents flickering or inconsistencies in the reconstructed tool regions over time, particularly in areas that remain occluded across multiple frames.

7. **Noise Loss ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{noise}}$):** Noise loss minimizes unwanted noise by focusing on the variance in tool regions:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{noise}} = \text{Mean}((1 - M) \odot \sigma^2(\hat{C})) \quad (4.12)$$

Where:

- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{noise}}$: Noise loss in tool regions.
- $\sigma^2(\hat{C})$: Local variance of pixel intensities in the reconstructed tool regions.

Purpose: Suppresses noise in occluded regions, ensuring smoother reconstructions and preventing the accumulation of artifacts.

8. **Total Loss ($\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}}$):** The total loss combines all the components with specific weights:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = & \lambda_{\text{similarity}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{similarity}} + \lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{depth-inpaint}} + \lambda_{\text{illumination}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{illumination}} + \\ & \lambda_{\text{diversity}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{diversity}} + \lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{edge-smoothing}} + \\ & \lambda_{\text{time-consistency}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{time-consistency}} + \lambda_{\text{noise}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{noise}} \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

Where:

- λ_x : Weight controlling the relative importance of each loss term.

It should be reiterated once again that, for the implementation of the InDeform3DGS method, the various modules presented must be utilized to obtain a dataset composed of the following list, as also illustrated in Figures 3.3 and 4.1:

- Dehazed monocular endoscopic video
- Depth estimation of the dehazed video
- Segmentation masks of surgical tools
- Inpainted monocular endoscopic video
- Depth estimation of the inpainted video
- Camera pose estimation of the monocular endoscopic video

The *Results and Discussion* section presents the outcomes of both approaches, Modified Deform3DGS and InDeform3DGS, including a numerical comparison using defined metrics and a qualitative analysis to determine the optimal method and its applicable conditions.

4.3 Software Integration

Having presented all components of the project Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting for Monocular Endoscopic Video Reconstruction of Surgical Scenes, the software integration is carried out. For this purpose, the integration follows a modular and scalable architecture, ensuring maintainability and ease of expansion. In Figure 4.17, the Project Structure Diagram (available on the project’s official GitHub repository) illustrates the division of files into key directories, each serving a specific role within the pipeline. It is noted that less relevant files are omitted from visualization but are represented with ellipses. Thus, the visible files are relevant and organized into the following main directories:

- **src/**: Contains the core source code of the project. It includes the `main.py` script, which serves as the entry point for pipeline execution. Key features of `main.py` are highlighted below:
 1. A modular and scalable architecture is implemented, separating pipeline stages into independent modules for monocular endoscopic video processing.
 2. Object-oriented programming (OOP) is employed to instantiate and execute each stage/module located in the `stages/` folder, which contains the optimized implementations discussed in the System Development section. For **InDeform3DGS** (located in the `third_party/` folder), `subprocess` calls are used for training and rendering, along with metric evaluation for the full reconstruction process.
 3. A command-line interface via `argparse` is provided, enabling customization of execution (e.g., activating/deactivating specific stages with `--stages`). Hyperparameter configuration is supported (e.g., `threshold_detection`).
 4. Best programming practices are followed, including scalable model and file management (e.g., pretrained models in `models/pretrained/`, intermediate data in `data/intermediate/`), input validation, error handling, and GPU memory cleanup after each stage.
- **data/**: Manages input datasets, intermediate results (outputs from each module), final outputs (Deformable 3DGS reconstructions), tool outputs, process logs, and training data for the YOLOv11 model.

- **tools/**: Contains utility scripts and helper functions. Key scripts include:
 1. **pose_visualizer.py**: Visualizes outputs of the pose estimation module.
 2. **yolov11_train_optimized.py**: Trains the YOLOv11 model used in the main pipeline.
 3. **get_bbox_from_video.py**: Extracts bounding boxes for watermarks in input videos, allowing InDeform3DGS to treat these regions as occlusions and remove them during inpainting.
 4. **iterate.py**: Automates tests proposed in the *Results and Discussion* section. It performs training, rendering, and metric evaluation while varying the weights of the total loss (Equation 4.13). Three modes are supported: fixed lambda values, lambda ranges with defined increments (e.g., `lambda_similarity` from 0 to 1 in 0.01 steps), or Bayesian optimization to maximize an objective metric.
 5. **compare.py**: Computes metrics discussed in *Results and Discussion*.
- **third_party/**: This directory contains external dependencies and third-party libraries required by the project. It includes various external projects utilized in this work, as well as InDeform3DGS. Note that the files displayed in the Project Structure Diagram (fig. 4.17) within the InDeform3DGS folder correspond to those modified in this study to implement the proposed improvements over the original Deform3DGS framework.
- **config/**: Stores configuration files for InDeform3DGS, organized into four sections:
 1. **ModelParams**: Specifies the camera scale and the inpainting integration, allowing the selection between InDeform3DGS and the original *Deform3DGS.
 2. **DatasetParams**: Configures input resolution, evaluation frequency, and dataset paths.
 3. **OptimizationParams**: Adjusts learning rates, iteration counts, and loss weights (Equation 4.13).
 4. **ModelHiddenParams**: Specifies internal attributes (e.g., number of curves and model channels).

Having integrated all components into a unified, modular software architecture, the system is now prepared for rigorous testing to validate the outputs generated by this framework. The structured design ensures efficient interaction between modules while maintaining scalability and reproducibility. The subsequent sections present the evaluation results, assessing the system’s ability to handle prolonged occlusions through quantitative metrics and qualitative comparisons, demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed pipeline.

Figure 4.17 Project Structure Diagram illustrating the organization of directories, Python scripts, model files, and data files, among other components. The structure follows a modular and scalable design, where each main directory has a clearly defined function, ensuring efficient management of the project’s workflow and dependencies.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the experimental results and discussions related to the proposed approach for Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting in monocular endoscopic video reconstruction. The evaluation is carefully structured to assess the performance of the developed methodologies through both **quantitative metrics** and **qualitative visual comparisons**. To ensure a thorough analysis, a comprehensive experimental design is outlined, detailing the datasets, evaluation metrics, and validation strategies employed to rigorously evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed modifications.

The evaluation begins with the definition of numerical metrics, including the Natural Image Quality Evaluator (NIQE), Blind/Referenceless Image Spatial Quality Evaluator (BRISQUE), Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), and Multi-scale Image Quality Transformer (MUSIQ). These metrics are selected to provide a balanced assessment of both perceptual and structural qualities of the reconstructed images. Additionally, a **weighted final score** is introduced to integrate all metrics into a single comprehensive measure of reconstruction performance.

The impact of the proposed modifications is then examined through a series of comparative tests. Initially, a baseline assessment using the original Deform3DGS approach is conducted on **multiple datasets**, including those from EndoNeRF and Keio University. These baseline results establish a reference point for evaluating subsequent modifications. The first modification incorporates inpainted video **directly into the reconstruction process**, resulting in perceptual quality improvements but introducing minor artifacts due to **oversimplified texture** reconstructions.

A per-loss analysis follows, investigating the contribution of **each loss function** introduced in the InDeform3DGS framework. Penalizations such as depth inpainting, edge smoothing, illumination consistency, and temporal coherence are systematically analyzed. Results indicate that certain penalizations, particularly edge smoothing and depth inpainting, contribute positively to image quality, while others, such as temporal consistency

constraints, negatively affect performance by introducing visual artifacts.

To further optimize performance, a **Bayesian optimization process** is employed to determine the optimal weight configuration for the loss functions. Initial tests incorporating all loss functions fail to surpass baseline performance, suggesting that specific constraints degrade reconstruction quality. Consequently, illumination and temporal consistency losses are excluded from further optimization. A refined Bayesian tuning process is then conducted, leading to significant improvements in the final score. This demonstrates that the adjusted loss configuration effectively balances perceptual and structural fidelity.

The optimized InDeform3DGS model is validated on additional datasets, including surgical scenes captured under **varying conditions**. The evaluation reveals that the optimized model consistently outperforms the baseline in terms of perceptual quality, with notable improvements in reconstructing occluded regions. However, these advancements come at the cost of increased computational time due to the added complexity introduced by model optimization components.

Finally, qualitative visual comparisons further support the quantitative findings, highlighting improvements in anatomical consistency and the removal of reconstruction discontinuities. These results confirm that the modifications introduced in this work significantly enhance the robustness of Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting for surgical scene reconstruction. The proposed approach effectively addresses key limitations of previous methods while maintaining acceptable computational efficiency. The chapter concludes by summarizing these key findings.

5.1 Experimental Design and Procedures

To rigorously evaluate the performance of the proposed methodology, a structured experimental design is established. This section outlines the experimental setup, detailing the datasets, evaluation metrics, and validation strategies employed to assess the effectiveness of the Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting Module. The objective is to ensure that the proposed modifications, effectively address the limitations identified in the original Deform3DGS approach, particularly in handling prolonged occlusions in monocular endoscopic video reconstruction.

The experimental design follows a systematic approach, evaluating both the Modified Deformable 3DGS and InDeform3DGS approaches, as well as each component introduced in this work, to determine their impact on the final results.

To validate the improvements, comparative numerical metrics are defined. These metrics are used to compare the results with the original Deform3DGS and to analyze the outcomes under different conditions. The metrics include:

1. **Natural Image Quality Evaluator (NIQE):** Measures the naturalness of an image based on Natural Scene Statistics (NSS). It assumes that high-quality images exhibit specific statistical properties, which are modeled using Gaussian distributions (Niu, Yuandong et al. 2024).

• **Procedure:**

- Divide the image $I(x, y)$ into small blocks (e.g., 8×8 pixels).
- Compute local statistics for each block. These include:
 - (a) Mean and Variance: Describe the overall luminance and contrast in the image.
 - (b) Skewness: Captures asymmetry in the luminance distribution.
 - (c) Kurtosis: Measures the "peakedness" of the luminance distribution.
- Fit the statistics to a Generalized Gaussian Distribution (GGD):

$$f(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\beta}{2\alpha\Gamma(1/\beta)} \exp\left(-\left|\frac{x}{\alpha}\right|^\beta\right) \quad (5.1)$$

- Measure the distance between the image's statistics and the NSS model using the Mahalanobis distance:

$$\text{NIQE} = \sqrt{(\mu - \mu_r)^T \Sigma_r^{-1} (\mu - \mu_r)} \quad (5.2)$$

- Normalize the final score for comparison with other images.

• **Interpretation:** Lower NIQE values indicate higher image quality.

• **Evaluation Metric Justification:**

- Evaluated in the region corresponding to the surgical tool, where no reference is available.
- Specifically used to assess the naturalness of the reconstructed region that previously contained the tool.

2. **Blind/Referenceless Image Spatial Quality Evaluator (BRISQUE):** Evaluates image quality by analyzing distortions without requiring a reference image (Niu, Yuandong et al. 2024).

• **Steps:**

- (a) **Normalize the Image:** The image is normalized using Mean Subtracted Contrast Normalization (MSCN), which enhances the local statistics of luminance. The MSCN coefficients are computed as:

$$I'(x, y) = \frac{I(x, y) - \mu(x, y)}{\sigma(x, y) + \epsilon} \quad (5.3)$$

where:

- $I(x, y)$: Pixel intensity at position (x, y) .
- $\mu(x, y)$: Local mean computed within a sliding window centered at (x, y) .
- $\sigma(x, y)$: Local standard deviation computed within the same window.
- ϵ : A small constant to prevent division by zero.

(b) **Extract Natural Scene Statistics (NSS)**: The MSCN coefficients are analyzed to compute local statistical features, including mean, variance, skewness, kurtosis, and products of MSCN coefficients across different directions (horizontal, vertical, diagonal).

(c) **Train and Apply a Regression Model**: These NSS features are used as input to a regression model trained on a dataset of reference images with known Mean Opinion Scores (MOS). In PyIQA (the library used in this work), a Support Vector Regressor (SVR) is employed for this purpose, enabling the prediction of the perceptual quality score (BRISQUE value) for the input image.

- **Interpretation**: Lower BRISQUE values indicate better perceptual quality.
- **Evaluation Metric Justification**:
 - Similar to NIQE, it evaluates the region corresponding to the surgical tool in the absence of a reference image.
 - Designed to detect perceptual distortions and spatial artifacts in the reconstructed regions, ensuring visually consistent quality.

3. **Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR)**: Already introduced in the *Literature Review of 3D Gaussian Splatting in Surgical Scenes* section. Measures the similarity between two images, typically used to assess reconstruction quality (Niu, Yuandong et al. 2024).

- **Formula**:

$$\text{PSNR} = 20 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{MAX}}{\sqrt{\text{MSE}}} \right) \quad (5.4)$$

- **Where**:

- MAX: Maximum pixel value (e.g., 255 for 8-bit images).
- MSE: Mean Squared Error between the original image I_{original} and the reconstructed image $I_{\text{reconstructed}}$:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (I_{\text{original},i} - I_{\text{reconstructed},i})^2 \quad (5.5)$$

- **Interpretation:** Higher PSNR values indicate better reconstruction quality.
- **Evaluation Metric Justification:**
 - Applied to regions containing tissue, excluding areas with the surgical tool.
 - Measures the accuracy of the reconstruction by comparing it against the reference image, focusing on areas unaffected by occlusions.

4. **Multi-scale Image Quality Transformer (MUSIQ):** A Transformer-based model designed for accurate image quality assessment (IQA), leveraging multi-scale representations and advanced positional embeddings (Ke et al. 2021).

- **Steps (fig. 5.1):**
 - (a) **Input Preparation:**
 - Use the full-resolution image as input.
 - Generate resized versions of the image, preserving aspect ratio (*ARP resizing*).
 - Divide all images (original and resized) into fixed-size patches (e.g., 32×32).
 - (b) **Patch Encoding:**
 - Encode each patch using a lightweight ResNet-5 to extract features.
 - (c) **Positional Embedding:**
 - Apply **Hash-based 2D Spatial Embedding (HSE)** to encode patch positions.
 - Introduce spatial awareness for each patch within the image by applying **Hash-based 2D Spatial Embedding (HSE)** to encode their positions on a fixed grid.
 - Add **Scale Embedding (SCE)** to differentiate patches from different scales.
 - (d) **Transformer Encoding:**
 - Concatenate patch embeddings into a sequence, adding a **[CLS]** token to create a unified representation that aggregates information from all patches.
 - Process the sequence using a multi-head self-attention Transformer encoder to capture relationships between patches across the entire image and integrate both local and global information effectively.
 - (e) **Prediction:**
 - Use the output of the **[CLS]** token, passing it through a simple fully connected layer (MLP) to predict the image quality score.

- **Key Features:**
 - **Multi-scale Representation:** Combines global and local information from multiple image scales.
 - **Aspect Ratio Preservation:** Prevents distortions caused by resizing, crucial for IQA tasks.
 - **Compatibility:** Can process images of arbitrary resolutions and aspect ratios.
- **Interpretation:** MUSIQ achieves state-of-the-art performance by integrating positional information and multi-scale features, making it ideal for evaluating image quality in diverse contexts.
- **Evaluation Metric Justification:**
 - Evaluates the entire image without requiring reference information, making it more comprehensive and reliable than NIQE and BRISQUE.
 - Unlike NIQE and BRISQUE, which focus only on local statistical features, MUSIQ utilizes a Transformer-based architecture that captures both local details and global structures, leading to a more perceptually aligned quality assessment.
 - MUSIQ significantly outperforms NIQE and BRISQUE in benchmark datasets, demonstrating a higher correlation with human judgments of image quality. On the PaQ-2-PiQ dataset, MUSIQ achieves an SRCC of 0.566 and a PLCC of 0.661, whereas NIQE and BRISQUE only reach SRCC scores of 0.094 and 0.303, respectively, and PLCC scores of 0.131 and 0.341 (fig. 5.2a). Similarly, on the KonIQ-10k dataset, MUSIQ attains an SRCC of 0.916 and a PLCC of 0.928, significantly surpassing NIQE (SRCC = 0.507, PLCC = 0.523) and BRISQUE (SRCC = 0.665, PLCC = 0.681) (fig. 5.2b).

Having presented the four metrics to be used, a combined approach is employed to leverage their complementary strengths and provide a more comprehensive evaluation of the reconstructed images. Although each metric serves distinct purposes—NIQE and BRISQUE assess the naturalness and perceptual quality of tool regions without requiring a reference image, while PSNR evaluates the fidelity of tissue regions against a reference and MUSIQ captures both global and local quality in a perceptually aligned manner—their integration ensures that the evaluation is not overly reliant on a single metric. This holistic approach is particularly important, as it addresses the limitations of individual metrics and aligns the evaluation with both human perception and ground-truth accuracy. Moreover, PSNR, widely used in prior studies on 3D Gaussian Splatting in surgical scenes, is specifically employed to compare tissue regions unaffected by tools. By incorporating

Figure 5.1 MUSIQ Model Architecture. The model processes an input image at multiple scales, preserving the full-resolution image and generating resized variants while maintaining the aspect ratio. Each image is divided into patches and encoded using a patch encoding module. To capture spatial structure and hierarchical scales, **Hash-based 2D Spatial Embedding (HSE)** and **Scale Embedding (SCE)** are incorporated. The encoded patches are then transformed into a sequence and processed by a **Transformer Encoder**, where self-attention captures global and local relationships. Finally, the special token **[CLS]** serves as an aggregated representation of the image and is passed through a fully connected layer (MLP) to predict the image quality score.

method	Validation Set		Test Set	
	SRCC	PLCC	SRCC	PLCC
BRISQUE [26]	0.303	0.341	0.288	0.373
NIQE [27]	0.094	0.131	0.211	0.288
CNNIQA [18]	0.259	0.242	0.266	0.223
NIMA [36]	0.521	0.609	0.583	0.639
Ying <i>et al.</i> [43]	0.562	0.649	0.601	0.685
MUSIQ-single	0.563	0.651	0.640	0.721
MUSIQ (Ours)	0.566	0.661	0.646	0.739
std	± 0.002	± 0.003	± 0.005	± 0.006

(a) Results on the PaQ-2-PiQ dataset comparing MUSIQ with existing IQA models.

method	SRCC	PLCC
BRISQUE [26]	0.665	0.681
ILNIQE [47]	0.507	0.523
HOSA [39]	0.671	0.694
BIECON [19]	0.618	0.651
WaDIQaM [3]	0.797	0.805
PQR [44]	0.880	0.884
SFA [21]	0.856	0.872
DBCNN [49]	0.875	0.884
MetaIQA [50]	0.850	0.887
BIQA [34] (25 crops)	0.906	0.917
MUSIQ-single	0.905	0.919
MUSIQ (Ours)	0.916	0.928
std	± 0.002	± 0.003

(b) Results on the KonIQ-10k dataset comparing MUSIQ with state-of-the-art IQA models.

Figure 5.2 Performance comparison of MUSIQ on PaQ-2-PiQ and KonIQ-10k datasets against existing IQA (Image Quality Assessment) models. The results demonstrate that MUSIQ outperforms both traditional and deep learning-based methods in terms of Spearman’s Rank Correlation Coefficient (SRCC) and Pearson Linear Correlation Coefficient (PLCC).

PSNR, the evaluation ensures that the tissue regions remain undeteriorated despite the enhancements introduced in this work. The combined evaluation metric is defined as:

$$\text{Final Score} = 0.8 \cdot (0.5 \cdot \text{MUSIQ} - 0.25 \cdot \text{NIQE} - 0.25 \cdot \text{BRISQUE}) + 0.2 \cdot \text{PSNR} \quad (5.6)$$

The choice of this weighting scheme is intended to ensure a balanced emphasis on both perceptual and geometric accuracy. The first part, which includes MUSIQ, NIQE, and BRISQUE, assigns more weight to MUSIQ due to its advanced Transformer-based architecture and superior correlation with human judgments. On the other hand, the inclusion of PSNR ensures that regions unaffected by tools are preserved in quality. The implementation of the measurement of these metrics is presented in `compare.py` in the official GitHub repository of the project.

Finally, another metric to evaluate is the total processing time, as computational efficiency remains crucial for achieving a real-time system. For this reason, the dataset preparation time for each test is also detailed in the following section.

5.1.1 Test Definition

Knowing the final metric to be compared, the different tests to be evaluated are defined. For this purpose, five different datasets will be used, two of which belong to EndoNeRF

(Wang et al. 2022) and the other three datasets belong to Keio University. It is worth noting that a more exhaustive study will be conducted with the "Pulling" dataset from EndoNeRF, as this is the one used in most of the papers presented in the *Literature Review*.

The specifics of the datasets are outlined below:

- **Pulling Dataset (EndoNeRF):**

- **Number of Frames:** 62 frames.
- **Resolution:** 640×512 .
- **Description:** This dataset consists of two surgical tools. One tool remains stationary on the right side throughout all frames, while the other tool on the left grabs a tissue and pulls it upwards. The pulling action introduces significant deformations in the tissue.

- **Cutting Dataset (EndoNeRF):**

- **Number of Frames:** 155 frames.
- **Resolution:** 640×512 .
- **Description:** This dataset involves a single surgical tool performing a cutting action on tissue. The tool remains fixed in position throughout all frames while consistently cutting.

- **Scene 1 (Keio University Dataset):**

- **Number of Frames:** 125 frames.
- **Resolution:** 854×480 , resized to 512×512 to ensure compatibility with Monst3r's camera pose estimation and its neural network architecture.
- **Description:** This scene captures a surgical procedure where surgical forceps are pinching tissue, while an electrocautery tool performs a cutting action on the tissue.

- **Scene 3 (Keio University Dataset):**

- **Number of Frames:** 155 frames.
- **Resolution:** 960×540 , , resized to 512×512 to ensure compatibility with Monst3r's camera pose estimation and its neural network architecture.
- **Description:** This scene includes a fixed set of surgical forceps positioned in the upper left corner. Additionally, two forceps are used to pinch and pull an organ upward, exposing structures located behind the organ.

- **Scene 4 (Keio University Dataset):**

- **Number of Frames:** 139 frames.
- **Resolution:** 960×540 , resized to 224×224 to visualize the behavior of InDeform3DGS, contrasting it with the standard 512×512 resizing used in other scenes.
- **Description:** In this scene, surgical forceps are holding a piece of tissue while additional tools cut the tissue to remove it.

The dataset preparation times for conducting the tests are detailed in Table 5.1, which shows the following:

- The Pulling Dataset requires 159.87 seconds, corresponding to an average processing time of 2.58 seconds per frame. This value is comparable to the Cutting Dataset, which has an average processing time of 2.65 seconds per frame, as both datasets share the same resolution.
- Scene 1 from the Keio University Dataset, with a higher resolution of 854×480 , has a total processing time of 354.29 seconds, resulting in 2.83 seconds per frame. This increase in per-frame processing time compared to the EndoNeRF datasets is attributed to the higher resolution.
- Lastly, Scenes 3 and 4 from the Keio University Dataset, which have the highest resolution of 960×540 , require 3.19 seconds and 3.08 seconds per frame, respectively, reflecting the increased computational cost associated with higher resolution.

Tabla 5.1 Processing times (in seconds) for dataset preparation across different datasets and processing steps, including total time in seconds.

Dataset	Deh.	Det.	Seg.	Inp.	Inp. Depth	Deh. Depth	Pose Est.	Total Time
Pulling	7.03	0.94	23.75	7.43	23.03	20.46	77.23	159.87
Cutting	17.74	1.87	78.70	26.46	54.50	53.28	178.93	411.48
Scene 1	15.27	1.81	60.82	17.07	61.43	62.78	135.11	354.29
Scene 3	24.40	2.32	81.30	27.60	96.63	84.67	178.18	495.10
Scene 4	22.02	2.13	54.61	21.97	77.53	84.76	164.99	428.01

The following tests will be conducted using the aforementioned datasets:

1. **Baseline with Deform3DGS (Pulling - EndoNeRF):** Employ the standard Deform3DGS reconstruction using the *Pulling* dataset from EndoNeRF as a baseline.

Figure 5.3 Sequence from the Cutting dataset of EndoNeRF across frames 0, 45, 90, and 135, showing the tissue cutting process.

Figure 5.4 Sequence from the Pulling dataset of EndoNeRF across frames 0, 20, 40, and 60, showcasing the tissue pulling process.

Figure 5.5 Sequence from Scene 1 of the Keio University dataset across frames 0, 35, 70, and 110.

Figure 5.6 Sequence from Scene 3 of the Keio University dataset, illustrating the process of organ manipulation and tissue exposure across frames 0, 45, 90, and 130.

Figure 5.7 Sequence from Scene 4 of the Keio University dataset, showing key stages of tissue manipulation and removal across frames 0, 45, 90, and 130.

2. **Modified Deform3DGS (Pulling - EndoNeRF):** Use the Modified Deform3DGS approach, where the input consists of an inpainted video from the *Pulling* dataset of EndoNeRF.
3. **Per-Loss Analysis (Pulling - EndoNeRF):** Evaluate the impact of each loss introduced in InDeform3DGS by individually varying their weights from 0.1 to 1.0 (with a step of 0.1). This allows understanding the isolated effect of each loss on the final reconstruction quality.
4. **Bayesian Tuning (Pulling - EndoNeRF):** Perform a Bayesian optimization to find the best weights for each loss term in InDeform3DGS to maximize the Final Score. The *Pulling* dataset from EndoNeRF is used for this evaluation.
5. **Baseline with Deform3DGS (Cutting - EndoNeRF):** Apply the standard Deform3DGS reconstruction on the *Cutting* dataset from EndoNeRF as a baseline.
6. **InDeform3DGS with Optimized Weights (Cutting - EndoNeRF):** Use the optimized loss weights found in Test 4 for the InDeform3DGS approach and apply them to the *Cutting* dataset of EndoNeRF.
7. **Baseline with Deform3DGS (Scene 1 - Keio University):** Employ the standard Deform3DGS reconstruction using *Scene 1* from the Keio University dataset as a baseline.
8. **InDeform3DGS with Optimized Weights (Scene 1 - Keio University):** Use the optimized loss weights found in Test 4 and apply them to the InDeform3DGS approach for *Scene 1* of the Keio University dataset.
9. **Baseline with Deform3DGS (Scene 3 - Keio University):** Perform the standard Deform3DGS reconstruction on *Scene 3* of the Keio University dataset as a baseline.
10. **InDeform3DGS with Optimized Weights (Scene 3 - Keio University):** Apply the optimized loss weights found in Test 4 to the InDeform3DGS approach for *Scene 3* of the Keio University dataset.

11. **Baseline with Deform3DGS (Scene 4 - Keio University):** Use the standard Deform3DGS reconstruction on *Scene 4* of the Keio University dataset as a baseline.
12. **InDeform3DGS with Optimized Weights (Scene 4 - Keio University):** Employ the optimized loss weights found in Test 4 and apply them to the InDeform3DGS approach for *Scene 4* of the Keio University dataset.

It is worth noting that only the final tests are presented here. However, during the development of this work, the code underwent numerous iterations during the project, with errors being addressed as they emerged. Much of this work is not included in the document due to its limited relevance or to maintain a reasonable length. For example, the approach of improving the Optimization Model in the SurgicalGaussian work was implemented, where several tests were conducted to determine if the results were better than those of Deform3DGS. Among these tests was a Bayesian Tuning process involving 200 training runs on SurgicalGaussian, each with 40,000 iterations. This process took approximately 5 days, with the work laptop running continuously. Therefore, although only the relevant final tests are presented, there is a substantial amount of work not documented here.

Furthermore, regarding the final tests presented, it is worth noting that for each training session, only 3,000 iterations are defined. This constraint ensures that satisfactory results are achieved in less time, bringing the system closer to the real-time processing required in surgical applications.

5.2 Results Analysis

5.2.1 Test 1: Baseline with Deform3DGS (Pulling - EndoNeRF)

The process begins with Test 1, where the *Pulling* dataset from EndoNeRF is employed as a baseline. It should be noted that the metrics presented are derived from the average of the metrics discussed in the previous section. Specifically, the values for each frame across all tests are averaged to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the system's performance over the entire sequence, avoiding reliance on individual values that may be prone to sporadic fluctuations.

Table 5.2 presents the baseline results for comparative analysis.

5.2.2 Test 2: Modified Deform3DGS (Pulling - EndoNeRF)

The second test involves the application of the Modified Deform3DGS, where the inpainted video is directly integrated into the Deform3DGS pipeline without the need for a mask, as the input video is free of occlusions. The results obtained using this approach are summarized in Table 5.3:

Tabla 5.2 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 1.

Metric	Value
Total Time (s)	122.10
avg_niqe	9.3270
avg_brisque	87.8461
avg_musiq	68.6921
avg_psnr	40.3025
avg_final_score	16.1027

Tabla 5.3 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 2.

Metric	Value
Total Time (s)	94.67
avg_niqe	9.8879
avg_brisque	94.4398
avg_musiq	70.9964
avg_psnr	39.2585
avg_final_score	15.3847

The second test reveals the following insights when the inpainted video is directly applied in the Modified Deform3DGS:

- Total Time: Test 2 demonstrates a 22.45% improvement in speed, reducing processing time from 122.10s to 94.67s.
- avg_niqe: A 6.01% increase is observed in Test 2 (from 9.3270 to 9.8879), indicating a slight decline in perceived naturalness in the tool region.
- avg_brisque: Test 2 shows a 7.51% increase (from 87.8461 to 94.4398), suggesting a higher presence of artifacts or noise in the tool area.
- avg_musiq: Test 2 exhibits a 3.35% increase (from 68.6921 to 70.9964), reflecting improved perceptual quality and more natural, visually coherent images.
- avg_psnr: A 2.59% reduction is noted, from 40.3025 in Test 1 to 39.2585 in Test 2, indicating lower fidelity in terms of signal-to-noise ratio in the tissue region.
- avg_final_score: A 4.46% decrease is observed, from 16.1027 to 15.3847, suggesting a slight reduction in overall quality.
- Conclusion: While the direct use of the inpainted video yields a more visually appealing result according to MUSIQ, the NIQE and BRISQUE values indicate the presence of noticeable artifacts. Additionally, PSNR and Final Score suggest a loss of structural fidelity.

Regarding the qualitative comparison, Figure 5.8 shows a visual comparison between frames 0 and 27 for both experiments, allowing an evaluation of how each method handles the reconstruction of occluded areas. In Test 1, corresponding to the original Deform3DGS, it is observed that regions affected by prolonged occlusion (highlighted with circles) present significant reconstruction errors. The region where the surgical tool was located throughout the sequence is not adequately reconstructed, resulting in an area with artifacts, visible discontinuities, and completely black regions. This indicates that the method fails to correctly infer depth information in these areas, leaving gaps without valid data that affect the spatial coherence of the reconstructed model.

Conversely, Test 2 introduces an excessive simplification of previously occluded regions. Specifically, the texture and structural details in the affected area are overly smoothed, leading to a less detailed reconstruction with reduced geometric fidelity.

Figure 5.8 Comparison between **Test 1** (original Deform3DGS) and **Test 2** (Modified Deform3DGS). Frames 0 and 27 of both experiments are displayed to assess the reconstruction of regions occluded by surgical tools. In **Test 1**, the original Deform3DGS model fails to accurately reconstruct areas that remain occluded for extended periods, generating artifacts in the affected region. In contrast, **Test 2**, which uses the inpainted video directly without a mask, produces a visually more homogeneous reconstruction but **over-simplifies the occluded region**, eliminating critical structural details.

5.2.3 Test 3: Per-Loss Analysis (Pulling - EndoNeRF)

For Test 3, a detailed analysis of the impact of each loss function on the reconstruction quality is conducted. The following graphs and tables summarize the findings. Numerical data can be found in Tables C.1 and C.2 in the Appendix.

NIQE Analysis

The first graph (Fig. 5.9) illustrates how varying the weight (λ) of each loss affects the average NIQE metric. Key observations include:

- $\lambda_{\text{depth_inpaint}}$: A slight reduction in NIQE is observed, with the best improvement at $\lambda = 0.6$ and $\lambda = 0.8$, indicating that depth inpainting enhances perceptual quality up to a threshold.
- $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$: A fluctuating trend is observed. Intermediate values such as 0.5 yield the lowest NIQE (best quality), while higher values (0.7 and 1) degrade the metric. This suggests that excessive diversity can introduce noise and affect the structural coherence of the image.
- $\lambda_{\text{edge_smoothing}}$: Consistently reduces NIQE, achieving its best performance at 1.0. This indicates that edge smoothing positively contributes to perceived quality by reducing discontinuities in the reconstruction.
- $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$: A sustained increase in NIQE is observed as the weight of the illumination loss increases. This increase significantly exceeds the baseline value, suggesting that excessive control over illumination introduces artifacts or unnatural variations in the image, affecting perceptual quality.
- λ_{noise} : Remains relatively stable with minor variations. Although the values are generally close to the baseline, low values of λ_{noise} seem to improve visual perception.
- $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$: Exhibits behavior similar to $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$, showing an increase in NIQE as its weight increases. This result indicates that excessive control over similarity can introduce distortions that affect the naturalness of the reconstructed image.
- $\lambda_{\text{time_consistency}}$: A deterioration in NIQE is observed as the weight of temporal regularization increases, implying that greater emphasis on temporal consistency negatively affects the visual perception of the video. Additionally, the NIQE values for this regularization are consistently higher than the baseline, suggesting that its inclusion does not improve perceptual quality.

General Conclusion for NIQE: The analysis suggests that the depth inpainting loss, edge smoothing loss, and noise loss improve perceptual quality, while the illumination loss, similarity loss, and time consistency loss tend to degrade it. On the other hand, the diversity loss fluctuates around the baseline NIQE value, but there may be values of $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$ where the NIQE metric improves.

BRISQUE Analysis

Next, the analysis of the BRISQUE metric as a function of the different λ values reveals the following (Fig. 5.10):

Figure 5.9 Relationship between λ values and the average NIQE metric. The plot illustrates how NIQE varies as λ increases from 0.1 to 1, distinguishing the impact of different types of λ on perceptual quality.

- $\lambda_{\text{depth_inpaint}}$: A slight reduction in BRISQUE is observed compared to the baseline, achieving its best performance at $\lambda = 0.6$. This suggests that incorporating depth inpainting contributes to a more natural image, although with variations depending on the assigned weight.
- $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$: A fluctuating behavior is observed, with intermediate values ($\lambda = 0.8$) showing the least distortion. However, for high values ($\lambda = 1$), BRISQUE worsens, indicating that excessive diversity in reconstruction can affect visual coherence.
- $\lambda_{\text{edge_smoothing}}$: Significantly reduces BRISQUE, reaching its lowest value at $\lambda = 0.6$ and $\lambda = 0.8$. This suggests that edge smoothing helps eliminate high-frequency artifacts, resulting in a visually more coherent image.
- $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$: A sustained increase in BRISQUE is observed as the weight of the illumination regularization increases. This increase significantly exceeds the baseline, indicating that excessive regularization of illumination introduces unnatural variations, negatively affecting perceived quality.
- λ_{noise} : Remains relatively stable with minor variations. In general, intermediate values ($\lambda = 0.6$) show the least distortion, suggesting that adequate noise regularization can improve visual appearance without affecting image coherence.
- $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$: Exhibits behavior similar to $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$, with a constant increase in BRISQUE as its weight increases. This indicates that excessive control over similarity between frames can generate a perception of greater distortion in the reconstructed image.

- $\lambda_{\text{time_consistency}}$: A progressive deterioration in BRISQUE is observed as its weight increases, consistently exceeding the baseline. This suggests that temporal regularization introduces unwanted variations in the reconstructed image, affecting the perception of naturalness.

General Conclusion for BRISQUE: The analysis suggests that the depth inpainting loss, noise loss, and edge smoothing loss tend to improve perceived quality according to BRISQUE, while the illumination loss, similarity loss, and time consistency loss increase image distortion. Similar to the NIQE metric, the diversity loss, despite being below the baseline BRISQUE, should be chosen carefully to avoid negatively affecting perceived quality.

Figure 5.10 Relationship between λ values and the average BRISQUE metric. The plot illustrates how BRISQUE varies as λ increases from 0.1 to 1, highlighting the impact of different λ values on perceptual quality degradation due to distortions.

MUSIQ Analysis

On the other hand, the analysis of the MUSIQ metric as a function of the different λ values provides the following key insights (Fig. 5.11):

- $\lambda_{\text{depth_inpaint}}$: A general increasing trend in MUSIQ is observed as the weight of this regularization increases, reaching its best value at $\lambda = 1$. This suggests that depth inpainting positively contributes to the visual perception of the reconstruction, possibly reducing artifacts that affect structural continuity. It is worth noting an outlier at $\lambda = 0.8$, where a sharp drop in the metric is observed. Qualitatively, it is observed that at this point, the depth inpainting loss with this weight introduces artifacts that affect visual perception.

- $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$: Shows variable behavior, with lower values at $\lambda = 0.5$, indicating that excessive diversity in reconstruction can affect visual coherence. However, for $\lambda = 0.8$, an increase in MUSIQ is recorded, suggesting that a certain degree of diversity can improve global perception.
- $\lambda_{\text{edge_smoothing}}$: Tends to improve visual perception as its weight increases, with its best performance at $\lambda = 0.6$. This suggests that edge smoothing helps eliminate abrupt transitions, contributing to greater perceptual coherence.
- $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$: Remains relatively stable, with values above the baseline. However, starting from $\lambda = 0.6$, a slight increase is observed, indicating that adequate regularization of illumination can improve visual perception without introducing severe artifacts.
- λ_{noise} : Exhibits stable behavior for most values, but at $\lambda = 0.8$, a sharp decrease in MUSIQ is detected, a phenomenon similar to the depth inpainting loss. However, for the remaining values, it shows a higher MUSIQ value. compared to the baseline
- $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$: Shows a stable trend and achieves the highest MUSIQ values. This suggests that increasing the weight of similarity with the inpainted video improves the visual perception of the reconstruction. Since the inpainted video removes surgical tools, the model optimized with a higher $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$ better adapts to these modifications, which may result in a more homogeneous and visually coherent appearance. However, excessively high values may lead to a dependence on the inpainted video, which could amplify artifacts introduced by the inpainting process rather than improving the quality of the final reconstruction.
- $\lambda_{\text{time_consistency}}$: A progressive decrease in MUSIQ is observed as its weight increases, indicating that excessive temporal regularization can negatively affect the perception of visual quality. It is the only loss that remains below the baseline.

General Conclusion for MUSIQ: The analysis suggests that almost all losses have a positive impact on visual perception according to MUSIQ, excluding the two outliers observed at $\lambda = 0.8$ for the noise loss and depth inpainting loss. It is worth noting that the diversity loss should be carefully weighted, as intermediate values generate a lower MUSIQ value. Finally, the time consistency loss strongly penalizes visual perception according to MUSIQ.

PSNR Analysis

To evaluate the tissue regions and ensure that the implementation provided by InDeform3DGS is not negatively affected, PSNR is employed in the tissue areas. Each new component affects the results as follows:

Figure 5.11 Relationship between λ values and the average MUSIQ metric. The plot illustrates how MUSIQ varies as λ increases from 0.1 to 1, providing insights into the perceptual quality of the reconstructed images based on a deep-learning-based aesthetic assessment model.

- $\lambda_{\text{depth inpaint}}$: PSNR values remain stable relative to the baseline, with minimal variations. However, a slight decrease is observed at $\lambda = 0.9$, which could indicate that while inpainting contributes to improving reconstruction in occluded regions, its impact on non-occluded areas is neutral or slightly detrimental if too much weight is assigned to this loss function.
- $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$: A stable behavior is generally observed, with small fluctuations around the baseline. However, at $\lambda = 0.5$, PSNR reaches its maximum value, suggesting that moderate diversity in reconstruction can contribute to improving coherence in visible regions without affecting structural quality.
- $\lambda_{\text{edge smoothing}}$: Shows stable and slightly higher values than the baseline, indicating that greater penalization of edge discontinuities does not compromise quality in non-occluded regions.
- $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$: A slight decreasing trend in PSNR is detected as the weight of illumination penalization increases, reaching its lowest value at $\lambda = 1.0$. This indicates that while illumination correction may improve visual perception, its impact on the structural consistency of the video is negative if applied too intensely.
- λ_{noise} : Remains stable until $\lambda = 0.7$, where a moderate drop is recorded, followed by a recovery at $\lambda = 0.8$.
- $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$: A slight decrease in PSNR is observed as λ increases.
- $\lambda_{\text{time consistency}}$: A downward trend in PSNR is evident as the weight of this penalization increases. It is the loss that most penalizes PSNR.

General Conclusion for PSNR: Overall, PSNR remains close to the baseline, indicating that the implementation of the different λ penalizations does not significantly affect non-occluded regions. However, extreme values in the similarity loss, illumination loss, and time consistency loss tend to reduce structural fidelity, suggesting the need for an optimal balance. Additionally, moderate use of $\lambda_{\text{edge smoothing}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$ may contribute to improving reconstruction without compromising quality in visible regions.

Figure 5.12 Relationship between λ values and the average PSNR metric. The plot illustrates how PSNR varies as λ increases from 0.1 to 1, specifically measured in the tissue regions rather than the inpainted tool areas. This ensures that the structural fidelity of the reconstructed medical content is evaluated independently of the inpainting artifacts.

Final Score Analysis

Having discussed the impact of each component on the PSNR, MUSIQ, NIQE, and BRISQUE metrics separately, the analysis proceeds to examine the impact on the metric that combines all of the above, referred to as the **Final Score** in this work. The obtained values show the following (Fig. 5.13):

- $\lambda_{\text{depth inpaint}}$: Shows a stable trend with a slight increase up to $\lambda = 0.5$; however, at $\lambda = 0.8$, a sharp drop in the *final score* is observed. This is due to the behavior observed in the MUSIQ metric, which carries the most weight in the formula shown in Equation 5.6.
- $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$: Remains stable until $\lambda = 0.5$ but shows an increase at $\lambda = 0.8$, indicating that promoting diversity in model optimization can improve perceived quality. However, extreme values ($\lambda = 1.0$) result in a decrease in the score, falling below the baseline.

- $\lambda_{\text{edge smoothing}}$: Generally maintains a stable trend, with values above the baseline. Its peak occurs at $\lambda = 0.6$, suggesting that a moderate amount of edge smoothing can be beneficial without compromising structural quality.
- $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$: A decreasing pattern is observed, indicating that as the weight of this penalization increases, the *final score* decreases. Additionally, all different weight values applied to this loss result in a lower final score compared to baseline, implying that illumination adjustment may be generating visual inconsistencies or unwanted changes in the image.
- λ_{noise} : Similar to $\lambda_{\text{depth inpaint}}$, it suffers a significant drop at $\lambda = 0.8$, a drop also attributed to the MUSIQ metric. However, the final score remains above the baseline.
- $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$: Maintains a descending behavior. This confirms that excessive reliance on the inpainted video can amplify existing artifacts or overly simplify occluded regions, affecting perceived quality.
- $\lambda_{\text{time consistency}}$: Shows a clear downward trend, indicating that strong penalization of temporal consistency negatively impacts global visual quality. This suggests that excessively prioritizing coherence between frames can generate distortions in non-occluded regions.

General Conclusion for Final Score: Overall, the *final score* suggests that the implementation of λ should be done with an appropriate balance. While moderate values of $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{edge smoothing}}$ can improve visual perception, high values in $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$, $\lambda_{\text{time consistency}}$, and $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$ tend to degrade final quality. Additionally, the sharp drops in $\lambda_{\text{depth inpaint}}$ and λ_{noise} at $\lambda = 0.8$ indicate that over-weighting these loss functions can negatively impact model optimization.

Additionally, a heatmap is generated to visually and clearly illustrate the impact of different λ weights on the performance of Deformable 3DGS in terms of Final Score. The following conclusions are drawn:

- Penalizations such as $\lambda_{\text{edge smoothing}}$, $\lambda_{\text{depth inpaint}}$, λ_{noise} and $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$ show more beneficial trends in model optimization, with optimal values in intermediate ranges.
- Penalizations such as $\lambda_{\text{time consistency}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$ tend to degrade the score when increased too much, suggesting that their constraints may be too strict.
- Similarity with the inpainted image should be handled carefully, as excessive reliance can amplify artifacts and reduce reconstruction quality.
- It is recommended to find a balance in each penalization, avoiding extreme values that may negatively affect the visual and structural quality of the reconstruction.

Figure 5.13 Relationship between λ values and the average Final Score. This metric integrates PSNR, MUSIQ, NIQE, and BRISQUE to provide a comprehensive evaluation of perceptual quality and structural fidelity. The plot illustrates how different λ values impact the overall reconstruction quality, determining whether specific implementations improve or deteriorate relative to the baseline.

Figure 5.14 Heatmap illustrating the relationship between λ types (x-axis), λ values (y-axis), and the average Final Score. The color intensity indicates the Final Score, where higher values represent improved perceptual quality and structural fidelity. This visualization helps to identify the optimal λ configurations that maximize reconstruction quality.

Total Time Analysis

Regarding the total time for each complete process (training and rendering) performed for each λ value for each type of loss, the following insights are presented:

- $\lambda_{\text{depth_inpaint}}$ (**Average time: 148.66 seconds**)
The depth loss in the inpainted region requires calculating the difference between the rendered depth map and the inpainted one. This involves loading depth images, converting them to GPU tensors, and performing loss operations. However, its computational cost is not high compared to other more complex losses, maintaining a relatively low time.
- $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$ (**Average time: 222.23 seconds**)
This is the most time-consuming penalization. The diversity loss is based on feature extraction using a VGG network to avoid trivial solutions in reconstruction. This process introduces deep convolutions and variance calculations in selected regions, significantly increasing computation time.
- $\lambda_{\text{edge_smoothing}}$ (**Average time: 161.15 seconds**)
The edge smoothing penalization is implemented by applying two-dimensional Gaussian filters to calculate the difference between the smoothed mask and the inpainted image in tool regions. Although it introduces additional operations, it is less costly than the diversity loss.
- $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$ (**Average time: 153.49 seconds**)
It is based on convolution with a luminance kernel to calculate the luminance loss. This method involves additional GPU processing but does not introduce operations as heavy as feature extraction or variance calculation. Its impact on computation time is moderate.
- λ_{noise} (**Average time: 178.6 seconds**)
Noise detection is based on local mean and variance calculations on the rendered image, which involves multiple convolutions in regions of interest. This increases computation time, especially in regions with significant intensity variations.
- $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$ (**Average time: 150.64 seconds**)
The similarity penalization aims to minimize the difference between the rendered image and the inpainted image. Being a simple $L1$ loss, the computation time is not very high. However, it still requires calculating the difference in all tool regions, introducing a slight increase in time.
- $\lambda_{\text{time_consistency}}$ (**Average time: 159.78 seconds**)
The temporal consistency loss requires comparing the tool region of the current

frame with that of the previous frame. This involves keeping the features of previous frames in memory and calculating the difference, introducing additional operations in each iteration, although without drastically affecting computation time.

General Conclusion for Total Time: The diversity penalization ($\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$) is the most time-consuming due to the use of a deep convolutional network for feature extraction and variance calculation. In contrast, the similarity and edge smoothing losses are relatively efficient, as they only involve basic tensor operations. However, all penalizations exceed the baseline time by introducing additional calculations in the training process.

Figure 5.15 Relationship between λ values and the total processing time. The plot illustrates how increasing λ values influence computational efficiency.

Overall Analysis

In Table 5.4, a summary of the effect of λ discussed earlier is presented, where penalizations that show results superior to the baseline for any λ value between $[0.1, 1]$ are colored in green, those that have at least one λ value below the baseline but oscillate around the upper part of the baseline are colored in yellow, and those that mostly show λ values resulting in metric degradation are colored in red. From the table, the following can be extracted:

- $\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$ is the penalization that offers the best global results, showing improvements in all metrics and achieving a *Final Score* above the baseline.
- $\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$ shows notable improvements in NIQE, BRISQUE, and MUSIQ, with stable performance in PSNR and a drop in *Final Score* at $\lambda = 0.8$.
- λ_{noise} maintains positive performance, with a minor impact on the MUSIQ metric and a sharp drop at $\lambda = 0.8$, but without significantly affecting the global *Final Score*.

- $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$ exhibits more unstable behavior. Although it improves certain metrics such as BRISQUE and PSNR, its impact on MUSIQ and *Final Score* is more variable, with a significant drop at $\lambda = 1.0$.
- Penalizations such as $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$, $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$, and $\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$ show clearly negative trends:
 - $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$ tend to deteriorate NIQE and BRISQUE, with decreasing *Final Score* values.
 - $\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$ is the worst penalization evaluated, with a negative impact on all metrics and a *Final Score* that remains below the baseline for all λ values, indicating that its application in InDeform3DGS is not recommended.
- In conclusion, the results suggest that the final implementation of InDeform3DGS should prioritize penalizations such as:
 - $\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$, $\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$ and λ_{noise} , given their positive impact on the analyzed metrics.
 - In contrast, penalizations such as $\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$ should be avoided, as they negatively impact the visual perception and structural quality of the reconstructed model.

Lambda	NIQE	BRISQUE	MUSIQ	PSNR	Final Score
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	Opt. 0.6-0.8	Improv. 0.6	Increasing trend	Stable, drop at 0.9	Drop at 0.8
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	Fluctuates	Opt. 0.8	Low at 0.5	Stable, improv. at 0.5	Drop at 1.0
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	Improv. 1.0	Opt. 0.6-0.8	Improv. 0.6	Stable, slight improv.	Best at 0.6
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	Deteriorates	Worsens	Stable	Decreases	Decreases
λ_{noise}	Stable	Opt. 0.6	Drop at 0.8	Drop at 0.7, improv. at 0.8	Drop at 0.8
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	Affects quality	Distortion	Higher MUSIQ	Slight progressive reduction	Decreases
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	Worsens	Deterioration	Below baseline	Worst impact on PSNR	Lowest

Tabla 5.4 Summary of the impact of each λ on NIQE, BRISQUE, MUSIQ, PSNR, and Final Score. Green cells indicate that, for any λ value, the metric is superior to the baseline. Yellow cells represent values where at least one point is below the baseline, but the trend oscillates around it. Red cells correspond to λ configurations where all obtained values are inferior to the baseline, indicating metric deterioration.

5.2.4 Test 4: Bayesian Tuning (Pulling - EndoNeRF)

Test 4: Initial Bayesian Tuning Incorporating All Losses in InDeform3DGS Model Optimization (Pulling - EndoNeRF)

Despite the insights gained from the previous test, a Bayesian optimization is conducted to explore the impact of all λ weights, including those that negatively affect the metrics. The goal is to identify the optimal combination of λ values that can potentially enhance the Final Score beyond the baseline.

This Bayesian optimization spans λ values in the range $[0, 1]$, with increments of two decimal places. The process begins with 10 initial random evaluations to explore the search space before proceeding with the optimization. The Expected Improvement (EI) acquisition function is employed to balance exploration and exploitation when selecting the next evaluation point. Although 300 iterations are planned, the optimization is terminated after 224 iterations due to stagnation and a lack of improvement in the Final Score, as illustrated in Figure 5.16.

The optimization progress exhibits significant variability in the Final Score values during the initial phase, a typical characteristic of Bayesian optimization's exploration stage. However, despite fluctuations throughout the process, most values remain between 14.5 and 15.5, consistently below the baseline. Consequently, the optimization terminates, and conclusions are drawn to refine the search strategy based on the new insights.

Figure 5.16 Optimization progress of Bayesian Optimization for finding the optimal combination of λ values. The plot shows the evolution of the Final Score across 224 iterations. The red dashed line represents the baseline performance (16.1027), serving as a reference to evaluate the improvements obtained through the optimization process. Despite some fluctuations, the optimization does not consistently surpass the baseline, indicating that further exploration or refinements in the search space may be needed.

Additionally, a heatmap is generated to analyze the correlation between λ values and

the *Final Score*, providing insights into the relative influence of each hyperparameter on reconstruction quality. Key observations include:

- $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$ exhibits a strong negative correlation with the Final Score (-0.5327), suggesting that increasing the weight of the illumination loss diminishes final quality.
- $\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$ also demonstrates a significant negative impact (-0.4184), indicating that strict temporal consistency constraints reduce visual fidelity.
- $\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$ shows a low positive correlation with the Final Score (0.0093), making it a candidate for improving reconstruction quality.
- $\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$ has a slight positive impact (0.0077), implying that edge smoothing can marginally enhance reconstruction.
- $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$ displays a mild negative correlation (-0.0872), though its impact is less detrimental compared to $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$.
- $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$ shows a weak but positive relationship with the Final Score (0.0050).

Figure 5.17 Correlation heatmap between λ values and the *Final Score*. The matrix highlights the influence of each hyperparameter on the global reconstruction metric. $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$ exhibit significant negative correlations with the *Final Score*, suggesting that high values of these hyperparameters degrade reconstruction quality. In contrast, $\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$, $\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$ show a slightly positive impact.

Based on the analysis, the illumination and time consistency losses are excluded from subsequent optimizations due to their strong negative correlation with the *Final Score*. These findings align with the conclusions from the initial Bayesian Tuning and Test 3, reinforcing the decision to disregard these losses.

For the similarity loss, which has a small negative correlation but is essential for providing color information in 3D reconstruction, a separate study is conducted. A fixed weight is applied to this loss, with values ranging from [0.01, 0.1] in increments of 0.01, to determine the optimal $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$.

Figure 5.18 illustrates the relationship between $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$ and the Average Final Score. The results indicate that the maximum performance is achieved within the $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$ range of 0.01 to 0.02, suggesting that a slight penalization for deviations from the inpainted image benefits reconstruction. Beyond $\lambda_{\text{similarity}} = 0.02$, the Final Score exhibits a declining trend, indicating that higher values of this loss restrict reconstruction undesirably. Notably, all tested values exceed the baseline, confirming the utility of this loss when carefully regulated. Consequently, $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$ is fixed at 0.02 for the subsequent Bayesian tuning.

Figure 5.18 Relationship between $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$ and the average *Final Score*. The plot reveals a non-monotonic relationship, with low $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$ values (around 0.02) yielding the highest Final Score. However, higher values lead to a progressive decline, suggesting that excessive penalization of deviations from the inpainted image negatively impacts model optimization. The dotted line represents the baseline performance when all λ values are 0.

Test 4: Final Bayesian Tuning (Pulling - EndoNeRF)

Based on the conclusions drawn from previous tests, the final Bayesian optimization is conducted for 150 iterations using the search space defined in Table 5.5.

Figure 5.19 illustrates the evolution of the Final Score, showing that it consistently

Tabla 5.5 Hyperparameter search space for Bayesian optimization in InDeform3DGS.

Hyperparameter	Search Space
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	[0, 1] (two decimal places)
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	[0, 1] (two decimal places)
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	[0, 1] (two decimal places)
λ_{noise}	[0, 1] (two decimal places)
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	0.02 (fixed value)
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	0.0 (disabled)
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	0.0 (disabled)

outperforms the baseline across all iterations. The maximum performance is achieved at iteration 118, with a Final Score of 17.0626, representing a significant improvement over the initial configuration. The corresponding loss weights at this iteration are detailed in Table 5.6.

The optimization process suggests that disabling the illumination and time-consistency losses, while keeping $\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$ fixed at 0.02, positively impacts performance by avoiding penalties that previously reduced model effectiveness. Most iterations now exceed the baseline, as shown in Figure 5.16. Overall, the optimization stabilizes around 16.8 to 17.0.

Tabla 5.6 Optimized hyperparameter values obtained at iteration 118 of the second Bayesian optimization in InDeform3DGS. The best final score achieved was 17.0626.

Hyperparameter	Optimized Value
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	0.02
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	0.91
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	0.00
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	0.22
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	0.26
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	0.00
λ_{noise}	1.00

Additionally, a correlation heatmap between the λ values and the Final Score is presented in Figure 5.20.

- **Negative impact of $\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$ (-0.1628 correlation with Final Score):** Increasing the weight of the depth inpainting loss slightly deteriorates reconstruction quality, suggesting that this term may not significantly enhance the final output.
- **Moderate positive effect of $\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$ (0.1391 correlation with Final Score):** Edge smoothing exhibits a weak yet positive relationship with the Final Score, indicating that smoother transitions at tool boundaries can improve reconstruction quality.

Figure 5.19 Progress of the Bayesian optimization for the search of optimal λ values. The Final Score varies across iterations, showing a relatively stable trend with minor oscillations. Notably, all iterations exceed the baseline value (16.1027), indicating that the optimization has improved reconstruction quality compared to the initial configuration.

- $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$ has a weak positive correlation with the Final Score (0.1164): Encouraging diversity in reconstructed features has a minor but beneficial effect, though other losses play a more critical role in optimization.

It is worth noting that despite the negative correlation of -0.1628 for $\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$, its optimized value at the best iteration is 0.91, indicating a high weight for the depth loss. This demonstrates that correlation does not imply direct causality, as these trends reflect general patterns, and the optimal combination of λ values is determined collectively rather than in isolation.

Table 5.7 presents the metrics obtained at iteration 118, which can be compared with the baseline values from Test 1. The following conclusions are drawn:

- **Total Time:** Using InDeform3DGS with optimized weights results in a 79.1% increase in processing time due to the inclusion of Model Optimization, which enhances visual reconstruction quality.
- **avg_niqe:** A 6.52% improvement, suggesting that noise and texture perception is more natural in InDeform3DGS.
- **avg_brisque:** A 1.78% deterioration, indicating a slight increase in image artifacts or distortions.
- **avg_musiq:** A 4.14% improvement, implying a more coherent and natural visual perception with optimization.

Figure 5.20 Correlation heatmap between the λ values used in the final Bayesian optimization and the Final Score. $\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$ shows a slight negative correlation with the Final Score, suggesting its contribution to optimization should be handled cautiously. Conversely, $\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$ exhibits a moderate positive correlation, indicating that promoting diversity in reconstruction can enhance final quality. $\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$ does not show a clear relationship with the Final Score, suggesting its impact depends on context and combinations with other hyperparameters.

- **avg_psnr**: A 0.17% improvement, maintaining a stable signal-to-noise ratio in the tissue region without structural fidelity loss from incorporating new components in Deform3DGS.
- **avg_final_score**: A 5.97% improvement, confirming that the optimized InDeform3DGS model provides better overall quality.

Tabla 5.7 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for iteration 118 of the final Bayesian optimization.

Metric	Value
Total Time (s)	218.69
avg_niqe	8.7176
avg_brisque	89.4123
avg_musiq	71.5362
avg_psnr	40.3705
avg_final_score	17.0625

Regarding qualitative analysis, Figure 5.21 reveals significant improvements in recovering previously occluded regions with InDeform3DGS. In frame 0, Deform3DGS shows a completely black area due to prolonged surgical tool occlusion, while InDeform3DGS achieves a more coherent reconstruction, preserving texture without abrupt discontinuities.

In frame 27, Deform3DGS introduces unnatural saturation in the reconstructed region, displaying a purple-blue tone inconsistent with the actual structure. In contrast, InDeform3DGS maintains a pinkish tone more faithful to the original image, although with slight granularity in rendering.

5.2.5 Test 5: Baseline with Deform3DGS (Cutting - EndoNeRF)

For Test 5, the Cutting dataset from EndoNeRF is used, and reconstruction is performed using the original Deform3DGS. Table 5.8 presents the results for Cutting with the original Deform3DGS, corresponding to the same PSNR value shown in Table 3.1.

Tabla 5.8 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 5.

Metric	Value
Total Time (s)	165.09
avg_niqe	16.9773
avg_brisque	100.9413
avg_musiq	71.2515
avg_psnr	28.8801
avg_final_score	10.6929

Figure 5.21 Qualitative comparison between Deform3DGS (Test 1) and InDeform3DGS with optimized weights (Test 4) in frames 0 and 27. InDeform3DGS corrects the issue in Deform3DGS, where prolonged occlusion results in a black region. Additionally, InDeform3DGS preserves the texture of the affected area, avoiding excessive over-simplification. In frame 27, Deform3DGS introduces anomalous color saturation, generating a purple-blue tone in the reconstructed region, while InDeform3DGS maintains a pinkish tone more faithful to the original structure, although with slight granularity in rendering.

5.2.6 Test 6: InDeform3DGS with Optimized Weights (Cutting - EndoNeRF)

For this test, the optimized λ values from Figure 5.6 are applied in the InDeform3DGS process. The results, shown in Table 5.9, lead to the following observations:

- **Total Time:** Using InDeform3DGS results in a 66% increase in computation time due to the inclusion of Model Optimization, which enhances visual reconstruction quality.
- **avg_niqe:** A 7.97% improvement, indicating that the optimization in InDeform3DGS generates more natural and less artificial reconstructions.
- **avg_brisque:** A 0.48% improvement, representing a negligible change in high-frequency artifacts.
- **avg_musiq:** A 0.94% improvement, showing a slight increase in the aesthetic visual perception of the reconstructed video.
- **avg_psnr:** A 35.24% improvement, reflecting a notable enhancement in reconstruction fidelity in tissue areas. This resolves the error observed in Figure 3.19c, where Deform3DGS failed to complete the reconstruction in the Cutting dataset.

- `avg_final_score`: A 24.99% improvement, indicating a global enhancement in reconstruction quality and demonstrating that InDeform3DGS provides a more balanced and optimal solution.

Tabla 5.9 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 6.

Metric	Value
Total Time (s)	274.03
<code>avg_niqe</code>	15.6292
<code>avg_brisque</code>	100.4602
<code>avg_musiq</code>	71.9242
<code>avg_psnr</code>	39.0595
<code>avg_final_score</code>	13.3637

In the qualitative evaluation, Figure 5.22 shows that in frame 0, Deform3DGS fails to reconstruct the region occluded by the surgical tool, resulting in a black area. In contrast, InDeform3DGS reconstructs the region, albeit with a dark tone due to the inpainting process mistakenly interpreting the tool’s shadow as part of the structure. This results in a visually coherent but illumination-inaccurate reconstruction.

In frame 70, Deform3DGS introduces artificial and unnatural textures, generating artifacts that compromise visual quality. InDeform3DGS, however, provides a cleaner reconstruction with better structural continuity, though some granularity remains, as observed in the qualitative evaluation of Test 4.

Figure 5.22 Qualitative comparison between Deform3DGS (Test 5) and InDeform3DGS (Test 6) in the Cutting - EndoNeRF dataset, showing frames 0 and 70. In frame 0, Deform3DGS fails to reconstruct the occluded region, resulting in a black area, while InDeform3DGS reconstructs the surface, albeit with a dark tone due to the inpainting process incorporating the tool’s shadow. In frame 70, Deform3DGS introduces artificial textures, while InDeform3DGS generates a more realistic reconstruction, though with noticeable granularity, consistent with observations in Test 4.

5.2.7 Test 7: Baseline with Deform3DGS (Scene 1 - Keio University)

This is the first test corresponding to a "custom" dataset, where the process starts from a monocular endoscopic video without pre-existing tool masks, camera pose estimation, or depth estimation. The results of applying Deform3DGS to this new dataset are shown in Table 5.10.

Tabla 5.10 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 7.

Metric	Value
Total Time (s)	122.31
avg_niqe	100.3998
avg_brisque	100.4602
avg_musiq	65.3116
avg_psnr	13.9607
avg_final_score	5.2173

5.2.8 Test 8: InDeform3DGS with Optimized Weights (Scene 1 - Keio University)

Following Test 7, a comparative analysis is conducted using the Scene 1 - Keio University dataset with the optimized weights tuned for the Pulling dataset (Table 5.6), applied within the proposed InDeform3DGS framework. The results are presented in Table 5.11, from which the following conclusions can be drawn when compared to Test 7:

- **Total Time:** Using InDeform3DGS results in a 24.2% increase in computation time due to the inclusion of Model Optimization, which enhances visual reconstruction quality.
- **avg_niqe:** An 82.6% improvement, confirming that InDeform3DGS generates significantly more natural reconstructions.
- **avg_brisque:** A 1.22% improvement, suggesting a slight reduction in artifacts.
- **avg_musiq:** A 3.83% improvement, enhancing the aesthetic perception of the reconstructed video.
- **avg_psnr:** A 0.03% improvement, indicating no significant changes in structural fidelity in non-occluded regions.
- **avg_final_score:** A 26.1% improvement, demonstrating the superiority of InDeform3DGS in terms of overall visual quality.

Tabla 5.11 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 8.

Metric	Value
Total Time (s)	151.95
avg_niqe	17.4650
avg_brisque	99.2313
avg_musiq	67.8157
avg_psnr	13.9649
avg_final_score	6.5800

Regarding qualitative evaluation, Figure 5.23 compares Test 7 and Test 8. The figure reveals that in frame 0, Deform3DGS exhibits artifacts in the region where the surgical tool was located, resulting in imprecise segmentation and darkened areas. In contrast, InDeform3DGS integrates tissue information more effectively, removing the tool and restoring the underlying tissue texture.

In frame 70, Deform3DGS continues to display black regions due to prolonged occlusion, highlighting its inability to adequately reconstruct hidden areas. On the other hand, InDeform3DGS achieves a more coherent reconstruction, removing the tool and restoring the edge of the yellow tissue with greater structural continuity.

Figure 5.23 Qualitative comparison between Deform3DGS (Test 7) and InDeform3DGS (Test 8) in the Scene 1 - Keio University dataset for frames 0 and 70. In frame 0, Deform3DGS fails to manage the tool correctly, leaving visible artifacts, while InDeform3DGS reconstructs the area and reveals the underlying red tissue. In frame 70, Deform3DGS retains a black region due to prolonged occlusion, while InDeform3DGS removes the tool and recreates the edge of the yellow tissue with greater visual coherence.

5.2.9 Test 9: Baseline with Deform3DGS (Scene 3 - Keio University)

The tests are repeated for the Scene 3 dataset from Keio University. The results of applying Deform3DGS to this second Keio University dataset are shown in Table 5.12.

Tabla 5.12 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 9.

Metric	Value
Total Time (s)	150.77
avg_niqe	17.9491
avg_brisque	102.6347
avg_musiq	67.7909
avg_psnr	33.1073
avg_final_score	9.6210

5.2.10 Test 10: InDeform3DGS with Optimized Weights (Scene 3 - Keio University)

For the comparative analysis of Scene 3 - Keio University, Test 10 is conducted using the optimized weights tuned for the Pulling dataset (Table 5.6) within the InDeform3DGS framework. The results are presented in Table 5.13, and the following observations are made when compared to Test 9:

- **Total Time:** Using InDeform3DGS results in a 48.8% increase in computation time due to the inclusion of Model Optimization, which enhances visual reconstruction quality.
- **avg_niqe:** A 0.36% improvement, representing a minimal enhancement.
- **avg_brisque:** A 0.04% improvement, indicating similar performance in the occlusion regions of surgical tools.
- **avg_musiq:** A 1.2% improvement, showing a minor but consistent increase in aesthetic perception with InDeform3DGS.
- **avg_psnr:** A 0.18% decrease, representing a negligible reduction in structural fidelity in non-occluded regions.
- **avg_final_score:** A 3.46% improvement, confirming that, despite marginal changes in other metrics, InDeform3DGS provides a globally better result.

Regarding qualitative evaluation, Figure 5.24 shows that InDeform3DGS improves reconstruction compared to Deform3DGS, particularly in previously occluded regions. In

Tabla 5.13 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 10.

Metric	Value
Total Time (s)	224.35
avg_niqe	17.8851
avg_brisque	102.5973
avg_musiq	68.6024
avg_psnr	33.0475
avg_final_score	9.9539

frame 0, Deform3DGS generates visible artifacts and unnatural textures, while InDeform3DGS achieves a more homogeneous reconstruction with smoother transitions. In frame 135, the difference persists, with Deform3DGS exhibiting texture inconsistencies and deformations that affect visual coherence.

Figure 5.24 Qualitative comparison between Deform3DGS (Test 9) and InDeform3DGS (Test 10) in the Scene 3 - Keio University dataset. In frame 0, Deform3DGS generates visible artifacts and unnatural textures, while InDeform3DGS achieves a more homogeneous reconstruction. In frame 135, the difference persists, with Deform3DGS exhibiting texture inconsistencies and deformations, while InDeform3DGS maintains smoother transitions and better visual coherence.

5.2.11 Test 11: Baseline with Deform3DGS (Scene 4 - Keio University)

Finally, the comparison for Scene 4 is conducted. Unlike Scene 1 and Scene 3, which use a resolution of 512×512 , Scene 4 is resized to 224×224 . The results of applying Deform3DGS are shown in Table 5.14.

Tabla 5.14 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 11.

Metric	Value
Total Time (s)	45.48
avg_niqe	26.6234
avg_brisque	103.3252
avg_musiq	74.6136
avg_psnr	26.0991
avg_final_score	9.0755

5.2.12 Test 12: InDeform3DGS with Optimized Weights (Scene 4 - Keio University)

The comparative analysis for Scene 4 - Keio University is presented below, comparing the results from Table 5.14 with those from Table 5.15:

- **Total Time:** Using InDeform3DGS results in a 28.5% increase in computation time due to the inclusion of Model Optimization. Note that the time is significantly lower compared to Tests 7-10, as the resolution is 224×224 instead of 512×512 .
- **avg_niqe:** A 0.82% deterioration, indicating a slight reduction in naturalness perception with InDeform3DGS in this experiment. This is attributed to the lower resolution limiting the effectiveness of inpainting and smoothing adjustments.
- **avg_brisque:** A 1.19% deterioration, showing an increase in visual artifacts.
- **avg_musiq:** Despite the slight deterioration in NIQE and BRISQUE, the overall aesthetic perception still favors InDeform3DGS, with a 0.42% improvement.
- **avg_psnr:** A 0.0096% improvement, representing a negligible difference, suggesting that non-occluded regions maintain the same structural quality in both methods.
- **avg_final_score:** A 1.79% deterioration, marking the first experiment where InDeform3DGS achieves a lower Final Score than Deform3DGS. This reinforces the hypothesis that reducing resolution limits the effectiveness of the penalties used in InDeform3DGS.

Regarding qualitative evaluation, Figure 5.25 shows that in frame 0, Deform3DGS introduces erroneous textures with irregularities, while InDeform3DGS achieves a more homogeneous reconstruction, although with some simplification. In frame 55, both methods produce visually acceptable reconstructions, but InDeform3DGS stands out by better closing edges and providing smoother transitions in tissue geometry.

Tabla 5.15 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 12.

Metric	Value
Total Time (s)	58.41
avg_niqe	26.8408
avg_brisque	104.5496
avg_musiq	74.9262
avg_psnr	26.1016
avg_final_score	8.9127

Figure 5.25 Qualitative comparison between Deform3DGS (Test 11) and InDeform3DGS (Test 12) in Scene 4 - Keio University. In frame 0, Deform3DGS generates erroneous textures with inconsistencies in tissue structure, while InDeform3DGS shows a more simplified reconstruction. In frame 55, both methods achieve acceptable reconstructions; however, InDeform3DGS performs better by closing tissue edges and maintaining smoother transitions in the reconstructed geometry.

5.2.13 Global Analysis of Results

After completing all tests, a summary table comparing the original Deform3DGS model with the proposed InDeform3DGS model is presented (Table 5.16). Green cells indicate improvements, while red cells indicate deteriorations. From this summary, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- InDeform3DGS increases computation time in all experiments. Note that the green cell in the *Total Time* column corresponds to Test 2, where Modified Deform3DGS is used, which directly processes the inpainted video without requiring tool masks, thus reducing time.
- NIQE, BRISQUE, and MUSIQ improve in most InDeform3DGS experiments, indicating more natural and visually coherent reconstructions.
- PSNR remains stable in almost all experiments, validating that improvements in occluded regions do not negatively affect non-occluded regions.

- InDeform3DGS improves overall reconstruction quality in most tests, validating its effectiveness. However, the use of 224×224 resolution is not recommended, as lower resolution limits the effectiveness of the Model Optimization used in InDeform3DGS.

Test	Total Time	NIQE	BRISQUE	MUSIQ	PSNR	Final Score
Test 1 → Test 2	-22.45%	+6.01%	+7.51%	+3.35%	-2.59%	-4.46%
Test 1 → Test 4	+79.1%	-6.52%	+1.78%	+4.14%	+0.17%	+5.97%
Test 5 → Test 6	+66.0%	-7.97%	-0.48%	+0.94%	+35.24%	+24.99%
Test 7 → Test 8	+24.2%	-82.6%	-1.22%	+3.83%	+0.03%	+26.1%
Test 9 → Test 10	+48.8%	-0.36%	-0.04%	+1.2%	-0.18%	+3.46%
Test 11 → Test 12	+28.5%	+0.82%	+1.19%	+0.42%	+0.0096%	-1.79%

Tabla 5.16 Percentage comparison of using the **Deform3DGS** model versus **InDeform3DGS** for all presented datasets. Green cells indicate improvements, while red cells indicate deteriorations.

Additionally, it is worth reiterating the conclusions from Test 3, as shown in Table 5.4, where $\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$, $\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$ and λ_{noise} were found to have a positive impact on metrics. In contrast, penalties such as $\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$ y $\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$ should be avoided, as they negatively affect visual perception and structural quality in the reconstructed model.

Conclusions

6.1 Main Achievements

The reconstruction of monocular endoscopic videos into Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting representations requires a specialized processing pipeline. Prior to this work, **no comprehensive framework** existed to preprocess and structure such videos into a dataset fully compatible with 3D Gaussian Splatting approaches. This project successfully addresses this gap by developing an **end-to-end pipeline** that processes monocular endoscopic videos and generates a structured dataset optimized for 3D Gaussian Splatting. This constitutes Stage 1 of the project and represents a fundamental contribution, enabling the application of Gaussian splatting techniques in surgical video reconstruction.

With Stage 1 in place, monocular endoscopic videos can be effectively processed in Stage 2, which corresponds to the development of **InDeform3DGS**, the method proposed in this work. InDeform3DGS directly addresses the **challenge of prolonged occlusions**, significantly improving reconstruction quality and enabling the generation of deformable 3D Gaussian splatting models from monocular endoscopic videos. In doing so, it completes the primary objective of this research by providing a fully integrated approach to reconstructing surgical scenes with higher fidelity and robustness.

Given the complexity of the system, the main conclusions are presented separately for each module, providing a detailed analysis of the contributions and insights obtained.

6.1.1 Dehazing Module

1. **Selection of Dehazing Method:** A comparative analysis of traditional computer vision-based and deep learning-based dehazing methods was conducted. Despite their superior performance on standard datasets, deep learning approaches were discarded due to the lack of specific datasets for surgical environments.

2. **Adoption of Dark Channel Prior (DCP):** Among traditional methods, the Dark Channel Prior (DCP) with Guided Filtering was selected as the most effective approach.
3. **Successful Implementation:** The DCP-based dehazing method was adapted and integrated into the pipeline, enhancing the visibility and contrast of anatomical structures and surgical tools.
4. **Development of an Interactive Module:** The `dehaze_video.py` script was created with a Tkinter-based interactive interface for real-time parameter adjustment.
5. **Quantitative and Qualitative Evaluation:** Dehazing significantly improved image clarity, but color alterations and increased saturation were observed.
6. **Processing Time:** The method achieved a processing speed of 4.50 seconds per frame, which, although efficient, requires further optimization for real-time surgical applications.

6.1.2 Feature Detection Module

1. **Selection of YOLOv11 for Surgical Tool Detection:** YOLOv11 was chosen after a comparative study, demonstrating superior precision and latency over previous YOLO versions.
2. **Challenges in Joint Detection and Segmentation:** An attempt to integrate detection and segmentation in a single model was unsuccessful, leading to separate optimization strategies.
3. **Hyperparameter Optimization with Optuna:** A Bayesian Optimization approach using the Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) was employed to fine-tune model performance.
4. **Identification of Key Hyperparameters:**
 - Translation (25%) and shearing (23%) were identified as the most influential factors, highlighting the importance of positional variability in tool detection.
 - Image resolution (20%) also had a significant impact on capturing essential details.
5. **Evaluation of Model Precision and Recall:**
 - Achieved a mAP@[0.50:0.95] of 0.752.
 - Optimal confidence threshold set at 0.6.

- The class *Cautery* exhibited the best performance, while *Forceps* had issues with background confusion, and *Suction* suffered from dataset imbalance.

6. Detection Challenges Identified:

- Redundant detections due to deficiencies in Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS).
- Background confusion, particularly for *Forceps*.
- Missing detections affecting frame continuity.

7. Improvements Implemented:

- Enhanced NMS filtering.
- Expansion of detection bounding boxes for better segmentation alignment.

6.1.3 Image Segmentation Module

1. **Selection of SAM2:** The Segment Anything Model v2 was chosen for its superior segmentation performance in video-based datasets.
2. **Temporal Validation Algorithm:** Implemented using Intersection over Union (IoU) over a four-frame sliding window.
3. **Batch Processing for Efficiency:**
 - Segmentation was optimized using batches of 50 frames.
 - Redefined bounding boxes per batch to improve tracking of reappearing tools.
 - Addressed potential limitations where new tools appearing mid-batch may not be segmented immediately.
4. **Validation on Real Surgical Videos:**
 - Tested on seven surgeries from Keio University.
 - Ensured consistent segmentation across consecutive frames.

6.1.4 Video Inpainting Module

1. **Evaluation of Traditional Methods:** Techniques such as Fast Marching Method, Navier-Stokes Fluid Dynamics, and Fast Structure Reconstruction were tested but discarded due to their inability to maintain anatomical consistency.
2. **Selection of Deep Learning-Based Methods:**

- DeepFillv2 introduced artifacts and inconsistent textures.
- Spatial-Temporal Transformer Network (STTN) provided the best temporal and anatomical coherence.

3. Implementation Enhancements:

- Adjustable parameters for scene-specific adaptation.
- Batch processing reduced processing time by 22.46%, RAM usage by 82.42%, and peak GPU memory by 35.57%.

4. Limitations:

- Some anatomical details were not fully reconstructed due to missing contextual information.
- Certain regions exhibited color inconsistencies.

6.1.5 Depth Estimation Module

1. **Adoption of Depth Anything V2:** This model demonstrated superior depth estimation accuracy.
2. **Batch Processing for Efficiency:**
 - Reduced execution time by 41.3%.
 - Increased GPU memory usage by 164.8%, highlighting a trade-off between speed and computational demand.
3. **Validation on Surgical Scenes:**
 - Accurate depth estimation was achieved in most cases.
 - Some inconsistencies observed due to propagated inpainting artifacts.

6.1.6 Camera Pose Estimation Module

1. **Selection of MonST3R:** Chosen for its superior pose estimation in dynamic scenes.
2. **Batch Processing Implementation:**
 - Reduced execution time by 40.64%.
 - Decreased RAM usage by 45.68%.
 - Lowered peak GPU memory by 51.34%.

6.1.7 Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting Module

1. Comparison of SurgicalGaussian vs. Deform3DGS:

- Deform3DGS was selected for its 62.93% reduction in processing time and 35.88% PSNR improvement.

2. Extension to Address Prolonged Occlusions:

- The original method struggled with reconstructing persistently occluded areas.
- **InDeform3DGS** was proposed, integrating video inpainting to enhance reconstruction quality.

3. Comparison of Two Approaches:

- **Modified Deform3DGS:** Direct use of inpainted video improved visual coherence but over-simplified occluded regions.
- **InDeform3DGS:** A hybrid method integrating inpainted and original videos, depth maps, segmentation masks, and camera poses.

4. **Results of Modified Deform3DGS:** Although the direct use of the inpainted video in the Deform3DGS pipeline without segmentation masks improves visual coherence and accelerates processing, it also introduces over-simplification issues, removing critical details in previously occluded regions.

5. Results of InDeform3DGS:

- Enhanced structural and visual fidelity in all datasets, except for the 224×224 resolution case, where the lower resolution limits reconstruction quality.
- Increased processing time justified by improved reconstruction quality.

6.2 Evaluation of Objectives Achievement

The objectives outlined in this thesis were systematically addressed through the design and implementation of an end-to-end pipeline that reconstructs monocular endoscopic videos into Deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting representations. A detailed assessment of each objective's fulfillment is presented below:

- The **review of state-of-the-art 3D** reconstruction methods was successfully conducted, with a focus on techniques addressing tissue deformation. This provided a comprehensive foundation for the methodological framework and guided algorithm selection.

- The **selection and integration** of key algorithms for object detection (YOLOv11), segmentation (SAM2), depth estimation (Depth Anything V2), video inpainting (STTN), and camera pose estimation (MonST3R) were successfully achieved. Additionally, these methodologies were optimized to ensure compatibility and optimal performance.
- A **fully automated preprocessing pipeline** was developed, effectively handling raw monocular endoscopic videos to generate inpainted frames, depth maps, and camera poses. This facilitated the structured processing required for Gaussian splatting.
- The **computational efficiency and scalability** of the pipeline were optimized, with substantial reductions in processing time and resource consumption observed across modules.
- The **generation of deformable 3D Gaussian Splatting representations** was successfully implemented, resulting in a novel approach—InDeform3DGS—which effectively reconstructs surgical scenes while handling prolonged occlusions.
- The system was evaluated across **multiple MIS scenarios** using both standard performance metrics and a custom metric specifically designed for this work.

6.3 Future Work

While the proposed pipeline successfully enables the generation of deformable 3D Gaussian splatting models from monocular endoscopic videos, several areas for future research and development remain open to further enhance its accuracy, efficiency, and generalization capabilities. The following outlines potential directions for future work:

1. Independence from Fixed Resolution in MonST3R:

- **Challenge:** The current implementation relies on MonST3R, which operates at fixed resolutions (e.g., 224×224 or 512×512) and is computationally demanding.
- **Future Work:** Explore alternative camera pose estimation methods that are resolution-agnostic and less GPU-intensive. Investigate lightweight architectures or hybrid approaches that can handle variable input sizes without compromising accuracy.

2. Deep Learning-Based Dehazing for Natural Color Preservation:

- **Challenge:** The current dehazing module, based on traditional methods like Dark Channel Prior (DCP), introduces color alterations and increased saturation.
- **Future Work:** Develop a deep learning-based dehazing model specifically trained on surgical endoscopic datasets. This approach could better preserve natural colors and improve overall visual quality, addressing the limitations observed in the current implementation.

3. Robust Inpainting for Contextual and Color Consistency:

- **Challenge:** The current inpainting module, while effective, struggles with reconstructing missing contextual information and exhibits color inconsistencies in certain regions.
- **Future Work:** Investigate advanced inpainting techniques, such as generative adversarial networks (GANs) or diffusion models, to achieve more realistic reconstructions. Focus on improving temporal coherence and anatomical accuracy while maintaining natural color tones.

4. Incorporation of Longer Videos and SLAM for Human Body Tracking:

- **Challenge:** The current pipeline is optimized for short video segments, limiting its applicability to longer surgical procedures.
- **Future Work:** Extend the system to handle longer videos by incorporating Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) techniques. This would enable continuous tracking of the human body, facilitating the creation of a digital twin of the internal anatomy over extended periods.

5. Optimization for Real-Time Applications:

- **Challenge:** The current pipeline, while efficient, is not yet suitable for real-time surgical applications due to processing time constraints.
- **Future Work:** Optimize each module for real-time performance. Explore hardware acceleration techniques, such as GPU-optimized algorithms or edge computing, to reduce latency.

6. Integration with Augmented Reality (AR) and Surgical Navigation Systems

- **Challenge:** The current system focuses on offline reconstruction, limiting its immediate applicability in real-world surgical settings.

- **Future Work:** Integrate the pipeline with AR and surgical navigation systems to provide real-time 3D visualizations during procedures. This could enhance surgical precision and decision-making, particularly in minimally invasive surgeries.

7. Multi-Modal Data Fusion for Enhanced Reconstruction:

- **Challenge:** The current pipeline relies solely on monocular endoscopic video data, which may not capture the full complexity of surgical scenes, particularly in differentiating tissues or identifying critical structures.
- **Future:** Integrate additional imaging modalities, such as near-infrared fluorescence imaging or ultrasound data, into the reconstruction pipeline. This multi-modal fusion would enable the generation of anatomically enriched 3D reconstructions, improving tissue differentiation and enhancing surgical navigation.

8. Automated Hyperparameter Tuning and Self-Optimizing Models:

- **Challenge:** The performance of the pipeline, particularly in modules like InDeform3DGS, is highly sensitive to hyperparameter settings. Manual tuning is time-consuming and may not generalize well across diverse surgical scenarios.
- **Future Work:** Develop self-optimizing models capable of dynamically adjusting hyperparameters based on input data characteristics. Techniques such as reinforcement learning-based tuning or meta-learning approaches could be employed to automate this process. For instance, a reinforcement learning agent could iteratively adjust loss function weights in InDeform3DGS to maximize reconstruction quality, while meta-learning could enable the model to quickly adapt to new surgical scenes with minimal manual intervention.

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Temporal Planning and Budget

A.1 Project Breakdown

In Figure A.1, the Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) used for the planning and execution of this study is illustrated. This hierarchical structure breaks down the project into different levels, modularly organizing the tasks and deliverables required for the implementation of InDeform3DGS.

A.2 Gantt Chart

A.3 Budget and Cost Analysis

A.3.1 Detailed Breakdown

Tabla A.1 Budget for the Thesis Project

Item	Details	Cost (€)
Project Author	360 h @ 12 €/h	4,320.00
Project Director	10 h @ 40 €/h	400.00
Second Director	5 h @ 40 €/h	200.00
Computer (Acquisition)	—	1,577.73
Electricity Consumption	$0.4 \text{ kWh} \times 360 \text{ h} \times 0.2 \text{ €/kWh}$	28.80
TOTAL		6,526.53

Note: The electricity consumption cost is estimated based on the average electricity rate in the Tokyo metropolitan area, where this work is carried out.

Figure A.1 Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) of the project, outlining the hierarchical decomposition of tasks and deliverables.

Figure A.2 Gantt Chart.

A.3.2 Calculation Details

1. Personnel Costs:

$$\text{Author: } 360 \times 12 e/h = 4,320 e,$$

$$\text{Project Director: } 10 \times 40 e/h = 400 e,$$

$$\text{Second Director: } 5 \times 40 e/h = 200 e.$$

2. Hardware and Energy Costs:

$$\text{Computer (Acquisition)} = 1,577.73 e$$

$$\text{Electricity} = 0.4 \text{ kWh} \times 360 \text{ h} \times 0.2 e/\text{kWh} = 28.8 e$$

3. Grand Total:

$$4,320 + 400 + 200 + 1,577.73 + 28.8 = 6,526.53 e$$

Applications and Impact Assessment

B.1 Professional and Industrial Relevance

As outlined in the *Introduction* section, **Minimally Invasive Surgeries (MIS)** offer numerous advantages over traditional open surgery, including reduced trauma, shorter recovery times, and lower risk of complications. Given these benefits, the adoption of MIS has been steadily increasing, with an annual growth in the number of procedures performed worldwide. However, to ensure that these techniques can reach the largest number of patients and become more accessible globally, it is crucial to optimize and enhance their execution.

The present work represents a significant advancement in this direction, introducing a new step toward the ultimate goal of developing a **real-time digital twin** from a monocular endoscopic video. This achievement has the potential to unlock a range of critical applications, particularly in surgical training, simulation, and automation. By leveraging this technology, it becomes possible to create **virtual reality (VR)-based simulations** for surgeon training, allowing medical professionals to practice complex procedures in a risk-free environment. Additionally, it enables the use of reinforcement learning to train **autonomous robotic systems**, paving the way for AI-assisted surgical interventions.

Beyond training applications, this research holds great promise in both preoperative and intraoperative planning. A high-fidelity digital twin of the internal anatomy can significantly enhance preoperative planning, providing a more accurate and realistic representation of patient-specific structures. This can lead to **optimized surgical strategies** and a **reduction in unforeseen complications**. During the surgery itself, the reconstructed 3D model can provide real-time intraoperative insights, assisting the surgeon by offering continuous updates on the patient's condition and anatomical variations.

The benefits of such optimizations extend to the postoperative phase as well. Shorter

recovery periods translate into lower hospitalization costs, improved bed availability, and reduced financial burden for **both patients and healthcare institutions**. Additionally, more efficient surgeries mean reduced operation times, ultimately enabling a higher daily throughput of MIS procedures. As a result, the widespread adoption of this approach could contribute to an overall **increase in the number of MIS performed globally**, reinforcing their role as a superior alternative to traditional surgical methods.

By addressing key challenges in real-time endoscopic reconstruction, this work lays the groundwork for a more accessible, efficient, and technologically advanced future for minimally invasive surgery.

B.2 Legal Aspects

The development of a real-time digital twin for minimally invasive surgery (MIS) based on monocular endoscopic video involves several critical legal considerations, particularly regarding data protection, digital twin creation, and medical device regulations. Since this research utilizes databases containing actual surgical procedures, strict adherence to **data privacy laws** is essential to ensure the ethical and lawful handling of patient information. Additionally, the potential implementation of this technology in a clinical setting may be subject to regulatory frameworks governing medical devices and AI-driven healthcare solutions.

First, it is important to address data protection and patient privacy. In this work, the use of real surgical datasets requires compliance with regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union and the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) in the United States. These regulations mandate that **data must be anonymized**, its use must be limited to research purposes, and protocols must be implemented to prevent unauthorized access to the database used.

On the other hand, the creation of a digital twin of human anatomy based on real surgical video introduces additional legal and ethical concerns. It must be legally clarified whether the future development of the digital twin belongs to the patient, the medical institution, or the technology provider. Furthermore, if a digital twin is used for planning, training, or even intraoperative purposes, it must be determined who bears responsibility in cases where the model contains inaccuracies that could affect medical decisions. Lastly, patients must have **the right to refuse** the use of their surgical data for generating the digital twin, and if they consent, the specific uses of the data must be clearly defined, establishing limits on its application.

Additionally, if the proposed system evolves into a clinically deployable tool, the relevant regulatory framework in the intended region of use must be considered. In the United States, compliance with the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) – Class II or III Medical Devices is required, while in Europe, adherence to the European Med-

ical Device Regulation (MDR – Regulation (EU) 2017/745) is necessary. International standards such as ISO 13485 and IEC 62304 Compliance must also be taken into account.

B.3 Economic, Social, and Environmental Impact

B.3.1 Economic Impact

In relation to what has been discussed in the *Professional and Industrial Relevance* section, this work entails economic implications in terms of cost reductions, efficiency improvements, and the potential for increased access to minimally invasive surgeries (MIS).

Since this project can contribute to improvements in preoperative planning and intraoperative assistance, the system can optimize minimally invasive surgeries, leading to a reduction in costs per surgery. This is due to shorter operation times resulting from fewer unforeseen complications and, by performing better surgeries, minimizing the time needed for hospital stays. This translates into lower costs for healthcare institutions as well as for the patients themselves.

By reducing patient costs in combination with increased efficiency per operation, creating greater available supply, this enables **more people to access this type of surgery**, improving the current healthcare context.

B.3.2 Social Impact

The social impact is closely linked to the economic impact, as mentioned in the previous section. A reduction in costs for both patients and healthcare institutions has the potential to **democratize access** to high-quality surgical care and improve patient outcomes.

The development of this technology also has an impact on the education of healthcare professionals, as the realistic digital twin can be used for VR-based training simulations. Ultimately, this could lead to training robotic systems to create fully autonomous systems, **minimizing the risk of error** by removing human error, making these surgeries safer.

Furthermore, considering a more immediate scope, this system could open a new avenue for remote surgeries, where the surgeon can perform the operation from any location using haptic systems while visualizing the patient's VR environment.

B.3.3 Environmental Impact

The development and implementation of the discussed technology can bring sustainability benefits related to resource efficiency, reduced medical waste, and optimized surgical processes.

First, currently, professionals are trained using cadaveric dissection, synthetic models, and disposable medical instruments, which generates significant waste. Replacing

these types of training methods with VR-based simulations reduces the need for physical materials, leading to a **lower environmental footprint**.

Similarly, in relation to the points discussed in the other two impact sections, shorter surgeries result in **reduced energy consumption** associated with operating rooms, anesthesia, and intensive care units (ICUs) per patient.

Ultimately, developing AI-assisted surgical interventions can contribute to more precise and targeted interventions, **reducing the need for exploratory procedures and excessive resource consumption**.

B.4 Contribution to Sustainable Development Goals

Below are the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to which the proposed work contributes:

1. **SDG3: Good Health and Well-being:** Since the work aims to improve the quality of minimally invasive surgeries (MIS).
2. **SDG4: Quality Education:** Because the work enables the generation of digital twins for the development of advanced surgical simulations in virtual reality (VR).
3. **SDG9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure:** As the presented project contributes to innovation in artificial intelligence applied to surgery and the development of new medical technologies.
4. **SDG12: Responsible Consumption and Production:** Due to the substantial reduction in waste generation resulting from the optimization of surgeries and the enabling of training in virtual environments, reducing the use of disposable surgical materials. Additionally, a reduction in the environmental footprint of healthcare systems can be expected if the need for long hospital stays and operating room energy consumption is minimized.

Figure B.1 The 17 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), aimed at eradicating poverty, safeguarding the planet, and ensuring prosperity for all by 2030 (United Nations in Malaysia 2020).

Code Repository and Experimental Results

The codebase used to execute all the processes presented in this work is available in the official GitHub repository: . This repository contains the implementation of InDeform3DGS, dataset processing scripts, and all the modules required for the reconstruction pipeline. The organization of files within the repository follows a structured format, as illustrated in the *Project Structure Diagram* in Figure 4.17, ensuring a modular and scalable approach to code management.

Figures C.1 and C.2 present the results of the evaluation metrics used in the tests for the complete Test 3. For the other tests conducted in this study, their corresponding logs can be accessed here: .

It is important to note that only log files are provided due to legal constraints associated with the dataset used in this study.

Tabla C.1 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 3 (Part 1).

Lambda	Value	NIQE	BRISQUE	MUSIQ	PSNR	Final Score	Time (s)
baseline	0.0	9.33	87.85	68.69	40.30	16.10	122.10
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	0.1	9.14	87.21	69.15	40.32	16.45	148.19
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	0.2	9.14	86.20	70.22	40.32	17.08	147.50
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	0.3	9.22	87.27	70.15	40.26	16.82	147.08
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	0.4	9.11	86.14	69.89	40.39	16.99	149.50
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	0.5	9.10	86.72	70.16	40.36	16.97	152.20
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	0.6	8.86	87.49	69.89	40.36	16.76	148.91
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	0.7	9.20	86.88	69.92	40.30	16.81	150.54
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	0.8	9.04	87.38	67.67	40.36	15.86	148.87
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	0.9	9.21	87.03	69.77	40.23	16.71	148.01
$\lambda_{\text{depth-inpaint}}$	1.0	9.22	86.12	70.39	40.33	17.16	145.74
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	0.1	9.10	87.46	70.35	40.32	16.89	233.37
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	0.2	9.36	87.34	69.88	40.37	16.69	232.85
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	0.3	9.62	86.72	69.68	40.36	16.68	221.87
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	0.4	9.20	87.74	69.95	40.30	16.65	227.27
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	0.5	8.99	86.71	67.89	40.38	16.09	220.14
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	0.6	9.32	86.56	69.65	40.33	16.75	222.74
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	0.7	9.74	86.99	69.05	40.36	16.35	222.61
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	0.8	9.16	85.44	70.17	40.31	17.21	220.05
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	0.9	9.13	87.74	69.64	40.36	16.55	222.83
$\lambda_{\text{diversity}}$	1.0	9.74	87.94	68.05	40.36	15.76	219.63
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	0.1	9.17	87.13	69.08	40.32	16.44	174.42
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	0.2	9.15	86.53	69.25	40.32	16.63	161.09
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	0.3	9.03	87.08	69.64	40.30	16.70	158.98
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	0.4	9.31	86.17	69.84	40.34	16.91	153.72
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	0.5	9.17	87.33	68.80	40.33	16.28	165.09
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	0.6	8.99	85.62	70.10	40.35	17.19	161.06
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	0.7	9.13	86.51	69.50	40.36	16.74	157.53
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	0.8	9.14	85.62	69.72	40.34	17.00	162.06
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	0.9	9.21	86.09	69.26	40.32	16.71	165.31
$\lambda_{\text{edge-smoothing}}$	1.0	8.88	86.53	69.16	40.31	16.64	155.22
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	0.1	9.65	93.34	69.96	40.33	15.45	156.43
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	0.2	9.69	93.90	69.92	40.38	15.32	148.58
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	0.3	10.16	94.49	69.95	40.33	15.12	158.12
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	0.4	10.21	94.78	70.00	40.37	15.07	154.01

Tabla C.2 Processing time and average evaluation metrics for Test 3 (Part 2).

Lambda	Value	NIQE	BRISQUE	MUSIQ	PSNR	Final Score	Time (s)
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	0.5	10.27	94.76	69.88	40.32	15.01	147.83
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	0.6	10.26	94.71	70.06	40.29	15.09	149.35
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	0.7	10.29	95.07	69.99	40.22	14.97	149.60
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	0.8	10.17	95.00	70.17	40.19	15.07	155.38
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	0.9	10.34	94.95	69.98	40.12	14.96	156.47
$\lambda_{\text{illumination}}$	1.0	10.35	95.29	69.83	40.11	14.82	164.10
λ_{noise}	0.1	8.82	87.35	68.61	40.32	16.27	163.22
λ_{noise}	0.2	9.48	87.06	69.82	40.31	16.68	160.10
λ_{noise}	0.3	9.10	86.63	69.65	40.29	16.77	166.94
λ_{noise}	0.4	9.03	87.59	69.38	40.31	16.49	197.14
λ_{noise}	0.5	9.04	86.56	69.43	40.30	16.71	194.15
λ_{noise}	0.6	9.09	86.07	69.31	40.30	16.75	185.89
λ_{noise}	0.7	9.11	87.21	70.16	40.26	16.85	178.14
λ_{noise}	0.8	9.34	86.31	68.19	40.37	16.22	197.23
λ_{noise}	0.9	9.25	86.72	69.82	40.33	16.80	171.63
λ_{noise}	1.0	9.09	87.72	69.70	40.35	16.59	171.63
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	0.1	9.36	92.49	71.25	40.41	16.21	153.11
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	0.2	9.90	93.66	71.31	40.42	15.90	148.31
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	0.3	9.96	94.05	70.90	40.35	15.63	149.36
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	0.4	10.28	94.45	70.91	40.40	15.50	147.23
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	0.5	10.22	94.57	71.09	40.38	15.55	147.47
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	0.6	10.18	94.82	71.14	40.33	15.52	149.01
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	0.7	10.41	94.95	70.95	40.29	15.37	149.17
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	0.8	10.41	95.09	70.93	40.25	15.32	157.48
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	0.9	10.36	94.97	70.97	40.27	15.38	156.64
$\lambda_{\text{similarity}}$	1.0	10.55	95.12	71.15	40.15	15.36	152.61
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	0.1	9.36	90.33	68.72	40.34	15.62	161.24
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	0.2	9.58	90.50	68.11	40.21	15.27	169.29
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	0.3	9.74	90.85	67.86	40.32	15.09	147.17
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	0.4	9.78	91.25	68.27	40.27	15.16	165.21
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	0.5	9.81	91.18	68.88	40.21	15.40	160.80
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	0.6	9.80	91.20	68.13	40.23	15.10	172.05
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	0.7	9.80	91.73	67.81	40.18	14.85	146.99
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	0.8	9.78	91.30	67.94	40.10	14.98	170.55
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	0.9	9.62	91.32	67.79	40.06	14.94	165.36
$\lambda_{\text{time-consistency}}$	1.0	9.65	91.67	67.66	39.96	14.80	157.12